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Essays on Sparse-Grids and Statistical-
Learning Methods in Economics

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Tesis

Doctorales

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UNIVERSIDAD de ALICANTE

Universitat d'Alacant
Universidad de Alicante

Departamento de Fundamentos del Análisis Económico

Facultad de Ciencias Económicas y Empresariales

**Essays on Sparse-Grids and
Statistical-Learning Methods in
Economics**

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Memoria presentada para aspirar al grado de
DOCTOR POR LA UNIVERSIDAD DE ALICANTE

Mención de Doctor Internacional

Doctorado en Economía Cuantitativa

Dirigida por: Dr. Lilia Maliar, Dr. Seguei Maliar and
Dr. Gabriel Pérez-Quirós

Financiado a través de las Ayudas para la Formación de Profesorado Universitario (FPU) del Ministerio de Educación, Cultura y Deporte (MECD) de España.

Para mis padres, hermanos y mi tía María.

To all my teachers.

To the happiness and prosperity of the world.

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Acknowledgements

Looking back it is impossible to mention all people that in one way or another has helped me in my way to finish my PhD and become the person I am today, to all of them I am thankful.

Overall, I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my advisors Dr Lilia Maliar, Dr Serguei Maliar and Dr Gabriel Pérez Quirós for sharing with me their thoughts, teaching, experience and guidance, and for their mentorship and care. I have enjoyed their different views and styles, each of them unique, each of them wonderful. I believe that Lilia and Serguei are my academic parents, they have devoted to me time and resources in an extension that it is challenging to pay back their consideration and kindness. Gabriel has enlightened me with his truly astonishing passion and vision for research, I hope it is contagious and it grows in me.

The first person who introduced me into the research world in Economics was Ramón María-Dolores, may he rests in peace.

I have had the university atmosphere of scientific reasoning, research, formation, and teaching. I am thankful to Juan Mora for his advice and great facilitation of the road, Alfredo Massó for his help and teaching me how to teach, and Pedro Albarrán for his sharp comments. I am grateful for to Francesco Turino, Kenneth L. Judd, M. Angeles Carnero, Anna Sanz-de-Galdeano, Francesco Serti, Mihaly Borsi, Germán López Buenache, Inna Tsenner and Rebecca Gidman. I thank the administrative staff Mariló Rufete and Josefa Zaragoza for their help and support.

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Introduction

This thesis is split into three chapters: chapter 1 is about the efficient implementation of the Smolyak Method; chapter 2 proposes alternatives ways to synthetic series with Statistical Learning to assess policies, with two cases of unemployment; and chapter 3 uses the proposals in chapter 2 and applies them to discern the effects of the points based driving licenses in different countries.

The first chapter goes in the direction of getting a step closer to the implementation of large economic models in more efficient ways; as will be illustrated, large economic models can be computed in a standard computer. To make this possible the chapter is focused on Smolyak methods, which makes the results applicable not only for economics but for engineering and other fields with large dimensional interpolation problems. It is explained in very simple terms the implementations of Smolyak method. This leads to easy and more efficient implementations by avoiding repetitions that come from the mathematical expressions. Also are studied other techniques for further reduction of the cost of the implementations by stressing the most important dimensions and regions to work with.

The main focus of the second chapter is the creation of synthetic or counterfactual series in order to asses policies. Synthetic or counterfactual series are series that express what could have happened if variables had not been introduced, for example changes in policies. In order to evaluate a policy in unemployment, for example, we observe the unemployment, GDP, and other indicators. However we can estimate the synthetic or counterfactual ones for

unemployment, GDP or other, and through this difference figure out the effects. In order to do that we currently have different techniques, as Synthetic Control (SC) methods. The role of this chapter is to reinforce previous literature by introducing in the field Statistical Learning techniques, already developed and used for other purposes. This is true until the point that most of these techniques are broadly implemented in scientific software packages making their implementation simple. In this chapter I explain how to apply them for the particular purpose of creating synthetic and counterfactual series and I illustrate that with two real cases of unemployment: a) a reduction of maximum work week hours, from the example of Portugal in 1996; and b) the reduction of firing cost, the example is Spain in 2010. In previous works there is no strong evidence that these types of labor reforms were effective or have a macroeconomic impact. The results are that Portugal enjoyed a reduction of unemployment. For the Spanish case the law showed an apparent increase in unemployment.

In the third chapter I study the effect of the Third European Road Safety Action Program (3ERSAP) is studied here. Not only respect when it started to work but, also regarding what would had happened if it had not been implemented. This is a novel assessment of the 3ERSAP, and helps to distinguish effects coming from European collaboration and within each country. Three methods are compared: synthetic control methods (SC), synthetic control with statistical learning (SCSL) and interactive counterfactual effects (ICE). The overall view is that the implementation of the road safety program at European level had larger effects than if the countries had continued their own paths. This paper provides quantitative estimates for each country. At European level it is possible to say that the 3ERSAP in the year 2010 helped to avoid between 13900 and 19400 fatalities. Regarding the different methodologies, an easy way to compare them is provided. In this particular case SCSL tends to perform better than SC and ICE.

Introduccion

Vivimos en un entorno complejo: muchas son las variables que explican los fenómenos sociales de nuestras sociedades. El científico debe modelizar y simplificar la realidad para obtener un mejor entendimiento de la misma, pero conforme más entendimiento queremos alcanzar más complejidad debemos ir introduciendo. Simultáneamente el incremento del poder computacional de los ordenadores, así como la capacidad de almacenar y tratar datos crece de una manera inimaginable hace unos años. La conjunción de la necesidad de incrementar la complejidad de los modelos y la capacidad computacional para resolverlos hace que las resoluciones numéricas sean cada vez más solventes y por lo tanto más demandadas. En modelos macroeconómicos solemos encontrar que solamente se tiene en cuenta dos economías: la interior y la exterior. Pensando detenidamente esto equivaldría por ejemplo a pensar en los Estados Unidos, como economía interior y la economía exterior, sería el resto del mundo, esta simplificación puede tener mucho sentido según en qué aplicación, sin embargo con los modernos avances tanto tecnológicos y algorítmicos podemos pensar en realizar simulaciones con mas de dos economías interactuando. Este es un ejemplo que es tratado el la primera parte de esta tesis, haciendo hincapié en la mejora y simplificación de los algoritmos.

Por otro lado, cada dia nuevas políticas se ponen en funcionamiento bajo la premisa de que va a haber un cambio deseado, pero ¿este cambio realmente se produce?. Para poder estudiar este punto necesitamos tener en cuenta todos los detalles de su implementación, de hecho esta es una diferencia clave entre la

ciencias sociales y las naturales. En las naturales nuestras hipótesis pueden ser evaluadas mediante experimentos. Aunque bajo ciertos supuestos también se pueden realizar experimentos en las ciencias sociales esto no responde ni mucho menos a la realidad cotidiana ni la mayoría de los casos. De manera que en muchos casos debemos utilizar la estadística para abrirnos paso y poder decir algo sobre los resultados tras la implementación de la reforma y el cumplido tiempo para recolectar los apropiados datos. Aquí se inserta el segundo y tercer capítulo. En ellos discuto sobre algunas de las metodologías que tratan de medir los efectos de cambios y en concreto de la implementación de políticas. Propongo sencillas alternativas basadas en “Statistical Learning” y las aplico a distintos casos en algunos de los cuales las previas metodologías simplemente no podrían decir nada. La aplicación de estas técnicas es sencilla, ya que vienen implementadas en la mayoría de paquetes de software estadísticos tales como Stata, Python, R y Matlab, además las técnicas han sido utilizadas en otras ramas de la ciencia, ver Hastie et al 2003. Estas técnicas las aplicó a relevantes cuestiones empíricas: desempleo y muertes por accidente de tráfico. En el segundo capítulo se habla de desempleo, en particular el efecto de la introducción de dos tipos de leyes: a) reducción del máximo de horas que se puede trabajar por semana, como ejemplo tenemos Portugal en 1996 y b) reducción del coste del despido, como ejemplo tenemos España en 2010. En el tercer capítulo se estudia los efectos de la implementación del tercer Programa de Acción de Seguridad Vial (Third European Road Safety Action Program, 3TERSAP) concluyendo que ayudó a salvar entre 13900 y 19400 vidas en el año 2010. Además comparo con otra metodología conocida como Interactive Effects como se puede encontrar en Gobillon and Magnac 2016.

1) Smolyak Method for Solving Dynamic Economic Models: Lagrange Interpolation, Anisotropic Grid and Adaptive Domain o “El método de Smolyak aplicado a la resolución de modelos económicos dinámicos: interpolación de Lagrange, grid anisotrópico and dominio adaptable” o 2) “Synthetic Control Method with Statistical Learning Techniques: a Comparison for Labor Market Reforms” “Método de Control sintético con técnicas estadísticas de apren-

dizaje” y 3) “Effects from the Implementation of Third European Road Safety Action Program using Synthetic Control Methods and Interactive Effects Counterfactual Approaches” o “Efectos debidos a la implementacion del Programa de Accion por la Seguridad Vial Europeo usando Método de Control Sintético y Efectos Interactivos Contrafactuales”.

Paso a describir brevemente los tres capítulos. El primer capítulo propone versátiles y eficientes maneras de aplicar la metodología de Smolyak de manera versátil y eficiente. Generalmente hablando, la metodología de Smolyak permite aproximar funciones en regiones donde la función no cambia muy drásticamente y está especialmente pensada para cuando esta función depende de muchas variables, teniendo así la “maldición de la dimensionalidad” (término aplicado para cuando se trabaja con muchas dimensiones a la vez y es técnicamente imposible trabajar). En este capítulo se mejora la implementación de la metodología de Smolyak, como mencionaré más adelante, además es aplicada para un casos en problemas candentes en macroeconomía comparando con las previas implementaciones. Las mejoras propuestas aquí son no solo aplicables dentro del ámbito de la economía pero de las matemáticas en general o allí donde el método de Smolyak sea aplicado.

En concreto se muestra como mejorar el rendimiento del método de Smolyak para resolver modelos económicos dinámicos (o DSGE models). Primero, se introduce una implementación más sencilla para interpolación, la manera en la que esto se consigue es evitando la costosa, en términos computacionales, evaluación de funciones base repetidas en la convencional fórmula de Smolyak. Segundo, se extiende el método de Smolyak para incluir construcciones anisotrópicas que permiten centrarse en las dimensiones que requieren mayor esfuerzo. Tercero, se muestra como seleccionar la mejor dominio para trabajar. Finalmente, se aplica a casos de gran dimensionalidad en economía, una solución basada en Smolyak la interpolación de Smolyak es sustancialmente más eficiente que cuando usa libre de derivada derivada punto fijo iteraciones en vez de las standard time iterations. En el contexto de modelos de crecimiento con uno y múltiples agentes.

El segundo capítulo “Synthetic Control Method with Statistical Learning

Techniques: a Comparison for Labor Market Reforms”, pretende adentrarse en cómo evaluar políticas o cambios de leyes. Este temática es clave si se quiere saber si la introducción de una nueva ley es efectiva o no. En este capítulo uso, como ejemplo, reformas laborales, en concreto reducción de la jornada laboral para Portugal en 1996 y una reducción del coste del despido en España en 2010. La estrategia seguida en ambos casos es básicamente construir unas series que representen lo que hubiera ocurrido si no se hubiera introducido la reforma. De esta manera se puede comparar y valorar el efecto de la reforma. En la literatura se ha utilizado Synthetic Control (SC) methods como en Abadie et al. (2010), sin embargo esta metodología no puede aplicarse propiamente en estos casos. Investigo los detalles del porqué no se pueden obtener resultados y propongo alternativas, la utilización de herramientas standard (en otras ramas, diferentes a la economía) de estadística. En el capítulo comparo y describir las diferencias en la teoría y la práctica.

En el tercer capítulo “Effects from the Implementation of Third European Road Safety Action Program using Synthetic Control Methods and Interactive Effects Counterfactual Approaches”, hay un nuevo caso de estudio pero también se consideran otras técnicas metodológicas. Se estudia los efectos del tercer Programa de Acción por la Seguridad Vial Europeo (3ERSAP). En este trabajo me centro en buscar los efectos y las duraciones de los mismos, para lo cual utilizó los mismos métodos que en el segundo capítulo, i.e. SC y SCSL y otra metodología introducida por Gobillon and Magnac 2016 y que llaman Interactive Effect Counterfactual (IEC), la principal ventaja de estos es que permiten, de una manera muy visual ver los efectos. Comparó las distintas metodologías entre sí, y proveo los resultados empíricos.

Ahora paso a describir cada capítulo de manera más completa.

1) Smolyak Method for Solving Dynamic Economic Models: Lagrange Interpolation, Anisotropic Grid and Adaptive Domain o “El método de Smolyak aplicado a la resolución de modelos económicos dinámicos: interpolación de Lagrange, grid anisotrópico and dominio adaptable” o 2) “Synthetic Control Method with Statistical Learning Techniques: a Comparison for Labor Mar-

ket Reforms” “Método de Control sintético con técnicas estadísticas de aprendizaje” y 3) “Effects from the Implementation of Third European Road Safety Action Program using Synthetic Control Methods and Interactive Effects Counterfactual Approaches” o “Efectos debidos a la implementacion del Programa de Accion por la Seguridad Vial Europeo usando Método de Control Sintético y Efectos Interactivos Contrafactuales”

Capítulo 1) "Smolyak Method for Solving Dynamic Economic Models: Lagrange Interpolation, Anisotropic Grid and Adaptive Domain" o “El método de Smolyak aplicado a la resolución de modelos económicos dinámicos: interpolación de Lagrange, grid anisotrópico y dominio adaptable”.

En su trabajo seminal, Sergey Smolyak (1963) propuso método para crear un grid (una selección de puntos) lo más pequeño posible que permiten, de manera eficiente representar, integrar e interpolar funciones en hipercubos multidimensionales. El trabajo pionero de Krueger and Kubler (2004) introduce el método de Smolyak en economía en el contexto de un estilo de proyección iterativo para resolver modelos de generaciones solapadas. La metodología se utiliza también para los problemas de selección de cartera (Gavilan-Gonzalez y Rojas 2009); para desarrollar filtros tratables en problemas con muchas dimensiones (Winschel and Krätzig 2010), para resolver modelos con agentes heterogéneos con vidas infinitas (Malin et al. (2011), Gordon 2011, Brumm and Scheidegger 2013), y la resolución de modelos neokeynesianos (Fernández-Villaverde et al. 2012).

El método de Smolyak permite estudiar problemas mayores que con los usuales productos tensoriales métodos, cuyo coste computacional crece rápidamente con la dimensionalidad del problema. En particular Krueger y Kubler (2004) and (Malin et al., 2011) documentan un coste computacional alto para sus soluciones cuando el número de variables de estado es mayor a veinte. En este trabajo, mostramos una implementación de la metodología de Smolyak que reduce su coste computacional, y proponemos extensiones del método de Smolyak que nos permiten resolver eficientemente modelos dinámicos económicos.

Primero, la implementación de la fórmula de Smolyak es ineficiente. Para in-

terpolar una función en un punto dado, esto hace que el algoritmo cree y evalúe una larga y repetida lista de bases funcionales, y entonces construye combinaciones lineales de las mismas para eliminarlas. En problemas con muchas dimensiones, el número de repeticiones es grande y reduce dramáticamente el número de cálculos. Nosotros ofrecemos una manera de evitar la costosa repetición de evaluaciones de las repetidas funciones básicas: en vez de de los convencionales generadores basados en grupos anidados, nosotros introducimos generadores basados en conjuntos no repetidos. En los conjuntos anidados un conjunto contiene a otro, y como resultado, su producto tensorial contiene elementos repetidos pero nuestra propuesta no. Este es el porqué nuestra propuesta de implementación de la fórmula de Smolyak no tiene repeticiones.

Una eficiente implementación del método de Smolyak es especialmente importante en el contexto de los métodos numéricos para resolver modelos económicos dinámicos que requieren interpolación y evaluación de funciones muchas veces, por ejemplo, en cada punto de nuestro grid, nodos de integración o periodos de tiempo. Cada vez que se evalúan los interpolates de Smolyak más recursos ahorramos.

Para calcular los coeficientes de interpolaciones, nosotros usamos la universidad técnica de interpolación de Lagrange en vez de la la convencional forma analítica. Procedemos in tres pasos: (i) construir M Smolyak grid points; (ii) construir las M correspondientes bases funciones de smolyak, y (iii) interpolar los valores de la función verdadera en los puntos considerados. Entonces resolvemos el sistema lineal con M ecuaciones y M incógnitas. El coste de resolver este sistema puede ser grande pero es un coste fijo en el contexto del proceso iterativo para resolver modelos económicos dinámicos. Mostramos que una matriz inversa puede ser precalculada al principio, ya que esta no cambia con las iteraciones para efectuar los cálculos más eficientemente, además utilizamos como base funciones ortogonales, como por ejemplo los polinomios de Chebyshev.

Segundo, la fórmula convencional de Smolyak es simétrica en el sentido de que tiene el mismo número de puntos en el grid y de bases de funciones para todas las variables. Para incrementar la calidad de la aproximaciones, uno

tiene que incrementar el número de puntos y bases para todas las variables, lo cual puede ser costoso e imposible en casos con muchas dimensiones. En este trabajo se presenta una versión anisotrópica del método de Smolyak que permite tratar de manera diferente cada dimensión con la finalidad que incrementar la calidad de la aproximación. En aplicaciones económicas, las variables no entran simétricamente: decisiones o funciones de utilidad pueden tener una mayor curvatura en unas variables que en otras, algunas pueden operar en rangos diferentes a otros; y finalmente, algunas variables puede ser más importantes que otras. Por ejemplo, en el caso de economías con agentes heterogéneos, la decisión de un agente, puede depender más de su propio capital que el de otros agentes, e.g., Kollman et al 2011; o podríamos necesitar más puntos en el grid para tener una mejor aproximación de variables de estado endógenas que exógenas (e.g., modelos basados en Tuachen y Hussy's 1991 para la aproximación de shocks). Una versión anisotrópica del método de Smolyak nos permiten tener en consideración un estructura específica de decisión o funciones de utilidad para resolver el modelo económico más eficientemente.

Tercero, el método de Smolyak selecciona los puntos en un hipercubo normalizado multidimensional. En aplicaciones económicas, tenemos además que especificar cómo las variables de estado del modelos son transformadas en el dominio. La manera en que esta transformación es construida puede dramáticamente afectar el dominio de la solución, y por lo tanto, la calidad de la aproximación. En el trabajo se muestra cómo efectivamente adaptar el grid en el método de Smolyak a el dominio de una solución de un modelo económico dato. Especialmente se construye un paralelotopo (generalización de paralelepipedo para n dimensiones), que contiene un área en las que la solución recae con mayor probabilidad, y se reduce el tamaño del paralelotopo al mínimo reorientando con una transformación de componentes principales. En Judd et al 2011 se encuentra que las soluciones centradas en ese dominio son más precisas que las que se centran en mayores dominios y existe un trade off entre obtener soluciones dentro y fuera del dominio relevante. Por esta razón el dominio adaptado incrementa la solución del método de Smolyak.

Finalmente, el método de Smolyak utilizado para la interpolación es solamente un ingrediente más para resolver modelos dinámicos económicos. En particular, Krueger y Kubler (2004), y (Malin et al., 2011) complementaron la interpolación de Smolyak con otras técnicas computacionales para problemas con gran dimensionalidad como: los polinómicas de Chebyshev, integración monomial y el procedimiento para crear los coeficientes de los polinomios. Sin embargo, utilizan una técnica – time iteration– que es costosa en su versión. Time iteration es tradicionalmente usada en programación dinámica: dadas formas funcionales para valores futuros, se resuelve para el presente valor de función usando una resolución numérica (solvers). Sin embargo, hay una simple manera de sustituir time iteration sin usar resolución numéricas - fixed point iteration- la cual puede resolver grandes sistemas de ecuaciones rápidamente usando cálculos muy sencillos. En el presente trabajo, se reemplaza time iteration usada en las versiones existentes del métodos de Smolyak en economía con fixed-point iteration, evitando el uso de resolución numéricas (solvers).

Capítulo 2) “Synthetic Control Method with Statistical Learning Techniques: a Comparison for Labor Market Reforms” o “Método de Control sintético con técnicas estadísticas de aprendizaje”

El objeto de estudio de un economista no puede ser implementado normalmente como un experimento con la finalidad de obtener datos y poder contrastar teorías y resultados, como ocurre en otras ciencias. Sin embargo con el uso de la estadística, en algunos casos, se pueden obtener conclusiones.

Imagina que hay un cambio, por ejemplo, un cambio de ley o un huracán. Algunas preguntas importantes son: ¿qué es lo que hubiera ocurrido si no hubiera habido ningún cambio?, ¿hubiera habido alguna diferencia en algunas de las variables relevantes?, si sí, ¿en qué dirección? y ¿cuánto?: En otras palabras, la evaluación de una política u otros eventos. Para responder esas preguntas se pueden construir Counterfactual Series, esto es, series de datos artificiales que expresaran lo que hubiera ocurrido y no hubiera habido ningún cambio. Una metodología reciente es la llama Synthetic Control (SC introducida por (Abadie and Gardeazabal, 2003) y desarrollada en (Abadie et al., 2010)).

Metodologías alternativas explotan la estructura de datos de panel del problema genérico, cuya propiedad son bien conocidas, como se ven en (Pesaran, 2006) y (Bai, 2009), y un número cada vez mayor de trabajos en esta dirección con el objetivo de evaluar ciertas políticas como en (Kim and Oka, 2014), donde los cambios en las leyes de divorcio es estudiada; (Ching et al., 2011a), donde el efecto de la inclusión de China en la Organización Mundial del Comercio es estudiada, or (Hsiao et al., 2012), donde la adhesión de Hong Kong con China es estudiada. Otros trabajos estudian modelos con factores lineales, con o sin efectos fijos, para la evaluación de políticas see (Gobillon and Magnac, 2015) and (Xu, 2015).

El propósito de este trabajo es crear series sintéticas o contrafactuales, para ello se introducen técnicas ampliamente utilizadas en Statistical Learning. La idea de crear series sintéticas o contrafactuales, puede ser vista como la creación de un predicción en lo que Statistical Learning tiene un amplia arsenal de metodologías. Dado que hay distintas metodologías que pueden tratar de distintas maneras la creación de series contrafactuales o sintéticas también voy a pedir prestado la manera de seleccionar entre distintas metodologías que normalmente se utiliza en Statistical Learning.

Es importante explicar que aunque aquí se considere las técnicas presentadas como una ampliación de SC métodos la filosofía detrás cambia. Particular SC methods fue creado de manera que no se extrapola o, en otras palabras, se evitan utilizar unidades comparativas que no son similares. La finalidad era utilizar unidades suficientemente similares para poder comparar. Sin embargo con la introducción de Statistical Learning aquí se prioriza la habilidad de unas unidades para explicar otras independientemente del grado de similitud.

En economía laboral hay muchos estudios en los que los efectos de las diferentes leyes han sido estudiados. Debe tenerse en cuenta que estas pueden variar mucho, pero incluso si se implementa la misma ley en entornos distintos el resultado podría variar. Supongamos que queremos estudiar la reducción del número de horas que se puede trabajar. Por ejemplo, el cambio de la ley laboral en Corea del Sur fue implementado en seis pasos desde 2004 hasta 2011, también tenemos

los distintos casos que se han llevado a cabo en Francia después de una relativamente limpia implementación en 2000. De manera que no hay condiciones ideales para investigar. En general es difícil encontrar resultados a nivel macroeconómicos en la literatura, la cual es vasta y completa, dada no solamente las diferentes leyes implementadas sino también las diferentes circunstancias acaecidas. Conclusiones a nivel microeconómico podemos encontrar, por ejemplo, que hay efectos sobre parejas, ver (Askenazy, 2013) y (Rudolf et al., 2011).

Si los empleados son altamente cualificados y escasos los efectos pueden ser que se deben recurrir a horas extra, see (Askenazy, 2013)), y de esta manera ellos pueden aumentar su renta mientras la empresa incrementa sus costes. También es posible que personas que ya tienen empleo busquen un segundo trabajo, see (Askenazy, 2013) . Si los sindicatos son muy poderosos puede reclamar el salario completo aunque se trabajen menos horas, reduciendo posibles efectos positivos en la creación de empleo, ver (Hunt, 1996a), para Alemania, y este caso concreto. Distinguir entre todos los efectos anteriores puede ser difícil. En general, no hay evidencia de cambio dramáticos en el largo plazo, ver (Jacobson and Ohlsson, 2000) para el caso de Suecia, y (Kapteyn et al., 2004) para los países de la OCDE.

Para el segundo caso de estudio, España en 2010, hay una ley orientada a la reducción del coste del despido. Generalmente la reducción de en los coste de despido se ve como un intento de flexibilizar el mercado de trabajo. Hay modelos que de manera teórica soportan esta idea como en Burda (1989). Sin embargo hay otros modelos que atenúan lo efectos a medio y largo plazo como en Bentolila and Bertola (1990). En la literatura empírica no hay un claro consenso, aunque si nos concentramos en trabajo a nivel nacional y en casos en los que hay dos sectores (data que la el mercado laboral Español esta dualizado entre trabajadores fijos y temporales) parece que la respuesta seria que el efecto es positivo. En Dolado et al. (2002) donde el mercado laboral español es estudiado tras la reforma laboral de 1997, se muestran resultados preliminares positivos en cuanto a la composición del mercado laboras, esto es, la proporción de trabajos fijos se incrementa. De manera similar en Kugler (1999), la reforma del mercado

laboral de Colombia en 1990 es estudiada and se distingue entre trabajadores informales e informales. Se muestra un incremento del empleo tras la reducción de los costes de despido, y un aumento de la proporción de los mejores puestos de trabajo (formales).

La contribución empírica de este trabajo incluye el uso de ambas técnicas, esto es, SC y LASSO con CV en casos reales. Los ejemplos empíricos son aplicados a dos reformas laborales: a) una reducción de la jornada laboral, en concreto Portugal en 1996; y b) la reducción del coste de despido, el caso de España en 2010. En trabajos previos no hay evidencia de que, en general, estas reformas fueran efectivas o tuvieran un efecto macroeconómico. Los resultados señalan que Portugal disfruto una reducción de desempleo. Para el caso de España se muestra un incremento de desempleo.

Para garantizar la calidad de los resultados se implementan también diversas pruebas. De esta manera se puede encontrar evidencia empírica y teórica de la eficacia de la metodología sugerida.

Capítulo 3) “Effects from the Implementation of Third European Road Safety Action Program using Synthetic Control Methods and Interactive Effects Counterfactual Approaches” o “Efectos debidos a la implementacion del Tercer Programa de Accion por la Seguridad Vial Europeo usando Método de Control Sintético y Efectos Interactivos Contrafactuales”.

“Mas de 1.2 millones de personas mueren cada año en las carreteras del mundo, millones más sufren lesiones serias con consecuencias a largo plazo. Globalmente, accidentes en tráfico de carreras es la principal causa de muerte de la población entre 15 y 29 años” de acuerdo con “Global Status on Road Safety” estudio realizado por la Organización Mundial de la Salud en 2015. Sin embargo los accidentes de coche puede potencialmente ser evitados. La mayoría de los países de la OCDE tratan, de una manera u otra de minimizar este problema. Las políticas empleadas son muy variadas: desde promover la obligatoriedad de equipación en los coches hasta cambios de leyes, educación, mejora de las carreteras, nuevas señalización or propaganda entre otras. Algunas de las cuales pueden ser implementadas de manera simultánea, haciendo su valoración más

difficil.

A nivel legal la implementación de diferentes los para la seguridad vial entre los países de la Unión Europea (UE) puede ser muy complejo dadas las dificultades para combinar toas las instituciones implicadas de una manera u otra. Para homogeneizar el transporte in the UE se creó el "Transpor White paper" que aparecio en 2001, con la meta inicial de reducir a la mitad el número de victimas mortales en las carreteras en 2010. Esta misma meta aparecerá en el Tercer Programa de Accion por la Seguridad Vial Europeo (3ERSAP), desde el 2003 al 2010, lo cual es el principal objetivo de estudio de este trabajo. En el año 2010 la meta no se cumplió pero las victimas mortales de carretera disminuyeron en un 43% entre 2001 y 2010, en TRT et al. (2009), IRTAD (2010), IRTAD (2012a) y IRTAD (2013) es posible encontrar un informacion sobre de los resultados en cada país. La evaluación llevada a cabo en este trabajo distingue entre los efectos del ERSAP en cada país. Las preguntas que se tratan de resolver son: ¿tuvo efecto el 3ERSAP?, ¿cuál fue el efecto del 3ERSAP en cada país? o ¿la lucha contra los accidentes de tráfico es más eficiente con o sin coordinación a nivel europeo?.

En este trabajo se intenta responder a estas cuestiones con la utilización de nueva metodología que explícitamente permite for short and long term comparison, llamada Synthetic Control (SC) methods, synthetic control methods with Statistical Learning (SCSL) y Interactive Effect (IE) como se describen en (Abadie et al., 2010), (Gobillon and Magnac, 2015) y el capítulo anterior de esta tesis. Todas estas técnicas tratan de construir, a su manera, series contrafactuales haciendo posible la comparación entre la realidad observada y la que hubiera pasadía si una ley no se hubiera implementado o algo no hubiera ocurrido (en este caso, si no se hubieran implementado sistemas de carnet por puntos). La diferencia es el efecto de la ley, suponiendo los demás efectos sean constantes. Se encuentra que las metodologías pueden ser útiles para la resolución de estas cuestiones. No hay una que sea mejor que la otra de manera absoluta, así que se recomienda usar todas y utilizar tests para quedarse con la mejor.

La investigación más cercana en término de metodología y de estudio en el caso europeo son Campos et al. (2014) y Fernández and Garcia-Perea (2015). En Campos et al. (2014) hay una cuantificación de la variación de la renta per capita por unirse a la Unión Europea en comparación con el contrafactual equivalente a quedarse fuera de la UE. Los resultados muestran un efecto positivo del 12%. En Fernández and Garcia-Perea (2015) se estudia la inclusión en la Euro Área, en este caso los resultados indican una mejora, en términos de renta per capita, muy ligera y que además tiende a desaparecer en unos pocos años. En ambos casos se implementó SC, en este trabajo también se trabaja con SCSL and ICE.

Si nos centramos en la UE y en la seguridad vial los dos trabajos más próximos a éste serían Castillo-Manzano et al. (2014b) y Castillo-Manzano et al. (2014a). En Castillo-Manzano et al. (2014b) es posible encontrar detalles acerca de la legislación sobre seguridad vial en la UE. Los autores describen un efecto positivo de *europaización*, esto es: hay una correlación negativa entre el número de años de pertenencia a la UE y la mortalidad en las carreteras. Hay evidencias de convergencia en la mayor parte de los países de la UE como se describe en Castillo-Manzano et al. (2014a). En esta línea este trabajo contribuye a la literatura cuantificando el efecto debido a el 3ERSAP.

Los resultados empíricos muestran que hay un efecto positivo general por el 3ERSAP. A nivel europeo solamente en el año 2010 se evitaron entre 13900 y 19400 nuevas víctimas. La mayoría de los países disminuyeron más las víctimas mortales en accidentes de tráfico que si hubieran actuado en solitario. SCSL resultado más efectivo en la mayoría de los casos.

Para resumir los puntos claves de esta tesis se puede decir que se presentan y evalúan diversos métodos y aplicaciones de los mismos.

A) El método de Smolyak fue diseñado de manera teórica para reducir la repercusión de los problemas de gran dimensionalidad. En este trabajo proponemos maneras más eficientes para implementar esta metodología que las existentes, con la finalidad de reducir el coste computacional del mismo. Las técnicas implementadas en este trabajo no están limitadas al marco económico. Primero,

se propone una implementación más eficiente que la actual de la metodología de Smolyak, en concreto, se evitan reiterativas evaluaciones innecesarias de las funciones bases a la hora de formar los interpolantes de Smolyak. La eficiente implementación del cálculo de los interpolantes es especialmente importante en el contexto de métodos numéricos para la resolución de modelos de sistemas dinámicos en economía en los cuales las funciones de decisión funciones de utilidad necesitan ser interpolados muchas veces durante la resolución de problemas, i.e. en cada punto del grid, periodo de tiempo y en cada punto de integración. Segundo, se propone una versión anisotrópica del grid de Smolyak en el cual se cambia el número de puntos y de funciones base necesarias en cada dimensión. En la aplicación económica típica, se conocen algunas propiedades y funciones de utilidad, y se podría utilizar este conocimiento para representar esas funciones de manera más eficiente usando las técnicas aquí propuestas. Tercero, se muestra un efectiva transformación del espacio de estado, dado un modelo económico, dentro de un hipercubo usado como dominio por el método de Smolyak. Se encuentra que hay una mayor precios de las aproximaciones cuando se utiliza el hipercubo más pequeño que contiene el conjunto de soluciones más probable de un modelo dado.

Las tres mejoras anteriores están relacionadas a interpolación. La última mejora se centra en un proceso iterativo para la resolución de modelos dinámicos. Time iteration es usado en la existente literatura con la metodología de Smolyak, la cual, depende de algoritmos numéricos para su resoluciones (muchas veces necesitando la primera y la segunda derivadas), sin embargo en este trabajo se utiliza una versión con fixed-point iteration la cual solamente involucra sencillos cálculos. Esta mejora, aunque menor en substancia, permite un buen ahorro, especialmente en aplicaciones con muchas dimensiones.

B) Las principales contribuciones del tercer capítulo son: a) la inclusión de métodos estadísticos estándar para la creación de series contrafactuales, con soporte teórico (desde el punto de vista del error con anterioridad el tratamiento y la habilidad predictiva) junto con la inclusión de casos reales y diferentes tests; b) modificaciones a la anterior metodología SCM; y c) el estudio de distintos

cambios en el mercado de trabajo, en particular dos: la reducción de la horas de trabajo por semana, en particular el caso de Portugal en 1996; y la reducción de los costes de despido, en particular en España en 2010. La metodología, a efectos prácticos, se basa en LASSO y Cross Validation para la creación de series contrafactuales o sintéticas por cada unidad (por ejemplo, un país o región) mediante una cuidadosa selección de otras unidades. Las series contrafactuales es comparada con la real, haciendo posible apreciar la dirección y magnitud de un cambio, como por ejemplo la introducción de una nueva ley o de un desastre natural. La implementación es sencilla dado que en la mayoría de paquetes estadísticos, tales como Matlab, R, Python o Stata, se encuentran las bases. En la parte empírica del capítulo se aprecia que para el caso de Portugal la reducción del número de horas de trabajo por semana llevo a una reducción del desempleo con respecto a lo que hubiera pasado si no se hubiera hecho. Para el caso español la reducción del coste de despido parece incrementar el desempleo en pocos meses. Sin embargo más investigación es necesaria para garantizar la inferencia de las series contrafactuales, mejoras en los placebo tests y otros test para seleccionar modelos.

C) El problema de accidentes de carretera es global y muchas países y distintas organizaciones están tratando continuamente de mitigarlo de distintas maneras. Este trabajo se centra en la evaluación de los efectos del 3ERSAP en cada país europeo. Los resultado empíricos muestran que hay un efecto positivo general por el 3ERSAP. A nivel europeo solamente en el año 2010 se evitaron entre 13900 y 19400 nuevas victimas. Este trabajo introduce satisfactoriamente nueva metodología en la literatura. A la hora de decir entre las tres metodologías es posible implementar tests para seleccionar la mejor. En todos los casos estudiados aquí SCSL fue más efectivo.

Por todo estos motivos la presente tesis puede suponer un avance para diversas ramas de la economía.

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Chapter 1

Smolyak Method for Solving Dynamic Economic Models: Lagrange Interpolation, Anisotropic Grid and Adaptive Domain

1.1 Abstract

We show how to enhance the performance of a Smolyak method for solving dynamic economic models. First, we propose a more efficient implementation of the Smolyak method for interpolation, namely, we show how to avoid costly evaluations of repeated basis functions in the conventional Smolyak formula. Second, we extend the Smolyak method to include anisotropic constructions that allow us to target higher quality of approximation in some dimensions than in others. Third, we show how to effectively adapt the Smolyak hyper-

cube to a solution domain of a given economic model. Finally, we argue that in large-scale economic applications, a solution algorithm based on Smolyak interpolation has substantially lower expense when it uses derivative-free fixed-point iteration instead of standard time iteration. In the context of one- and multi-agent optimal growth models, we find that the proposed modifications to the conventional Smolyak method lead to substantial increases in accuracy and speed.

JEL classification : C63, C68

Key Words : Smolyak method; sparse grid; adaptive domain; projection; anisotropic grid; collocation; high-dimensional problem

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1.2 Introduction

In a seminal paper, Sergey Smolyak (1963) proposed a sparse-grid method that allows to efficiently represent, integrate and interpolate functions on multidimensional hypercubes. The Smolyak method is not subject to the curse of dimensionality and can be used to solve large-scale applications. A pioneering work of Krueger and Kubler (2004) introduced the Smolyak method to economics in the context of a projection-style iterative method for solving multi-period overlapping generation models. Smolyak methods have been also used to solve portfolio-choice problems (Gavilan-Gonzalez and Rojas (2009)); to develop state-space filters tractable in large-scale problems (Winschel and Kräitzig (2010)); to solve models with infinitely lived heterogeneous agents (Malin et al. (2011), Gordon (2011), Brumm and Scheidegger (2013)); and to solve new Keynesian models (Fernández-Villaverde et al. (2012)).

While the Smolyak method enables us to study far larger problems than do tensor-product methods, its computational expense still grows rapidly with the dimensionality of the problem. In particular, Krueger and Kubler (2004) and Malin et al. (2011) document a high computational cost of their solution methods when the number of state variables exceeds twenty. In the paper, we show a more efficient implementation of the Smolyak method that reduces its computational expense, and we propose extensions of the Smolyak method that enable us to more effectively solve dynamic economic models.¹

First, the conventional Smolyak formula is inefficient. To interpolate a function in a given point, it first causes the computer to create and evaluate a long list of repeated basis functions, and it then constructs linear combinations of such functions to get rid off repetitions. In high-dimensional problems, the number of repetitions is large and slows down computations dramatically. We offer a way to avoid costly evaluations of the repeated basis functions: Instead of

¹We provide a MATLAB code that implements the computational techniques developed in the article. Also, Coleman and Lyon (2013) provide Python and Julia codes that implements some of these techniques.

conventional nested-set generators, we introduce disjoint-set generators. Nested sets include one another, and as a result, their tensor products contain repeated elements but our disjoint sets do not. This is why our implementation of the Smolyak formula does not have repetitions.²

An efficient implementation of the Smolyak method is especially important in the context of numerical methods for solving dynamic economic models which require us to interpolate decision and value functions a very large number of times, e.g., in each grid point, integration node or time period. We save on cost every time when we perform an evaluation of the Smolyak interpolant.

To compute the interpolation coefficients, we use a universal Lagrange interpolation technique instead of the conventional closed-form expressions. Namely, we proceed in three steps: (i) construct M Smolyak grid points; (ii) construct M corresponding Smolyak basis functions; and (iii) interpolate the values of the true function at the grid points using the basis functions. We then solve a system of M linear equations in M unknowns. The cost of solving this system can be high but it is a fixed cost in the context of iterative methods for solving dynamic economic models. Namely, we argue that an expensive inverse in the Lagrange inverse problem can be precomputed up-front (as it does not change along iterations). Furthermore, to ensure numerical stability of a solution to the Lagrange inverse problem, we use families of orthogonal basis functions, such as a Chebyshev family.

Second, the conventional Smolyak formula is symmetric in a sense that it has the same number of grid points and basis functions for all variables. To increase the quality of approximation, one must equally increase the number of grid points and basis functions for all variables, which may be costly or even infeasible in large-scale applications. In the paper, we present an anisotropic version of the Smolyak method that allows for asymmetric treatments of variables, namely, it enables us to separately choose the accuracy level for each dimension with the aim of increasing the quality of approximation. In economic applications, variables do not enter symmetrically: decision or value functions may have more

²Our exposition was informed by our personal communication with Sergey Smolyak.

curvature in some variables than in others; some variables may have larger ranges of values than others; and finally, some variables may be more important than the others. For example, in heterogeneous-agent economies, an agent's decision functions may depend more on her own capital stock than on the other agents' capital stocks (e.g., Kollmann et al. (2011)); also, we may need more grid points for accurate approximation of endogenous than exogenous state variables (e.g., models based on Tauchen and Hussy's (1991) approximation of shocks). An anisotropic version of the Smolyak method allows us to take into account a specific structure of decision or value functions to solve economic models more efficiently.

Third, the Smolyak method constructs grid points within a normalized multidimensional hypercube. In economic applications, we must also specify how the model's state variables are mapped into the Smolyak hypercube. The way in which this mapping is constructed can dramatically affect the effective size of a solution domain, and hence, the quality of approximation. In the paper, we show how to effectively adapt the Smolyak grid to a solution domain of a given economic model. We specifically construct a parallelotope that encloses a high-probability area of the state space of the given model, and we reduce the size of the parallelotope to minimum by reorienting it with a principle-component transformation of state variables. Judd et al. (2011) find that solution algorithms that focus on "a relevant domain" are more accurate (in that domain) than solution algorithms that focus on a larger (and partially irrelevant) domain and that face therefore a trade off between the fit inside and outside the relevant domain. For the same reason, an adaptive domain increases the accuracy of the Smolyak method.

Finally, the Smolyak method for interpolation is just one ingredient of a numerical method for solving dynamic economic models. In particular, Krueger and Kubler (2004) and Malin et al. (2011) complemented Smolyak interpolation with other computational techniques that are tractable in large-scale problems, such as Chebyshev polynomials, monomial integration and a learning-style procedure for finding polynomial coefficients. Nonetheless, there is one technique –

time iteration – that is expensive in their version of their numerical procedure. Time iteration is traditionally used in dynamic programming: given functional forms for future value function, it solves for current value function using a numerical solver. It works similarly in the context of the Euler equation methods: given functional forms for future decision functions, it solves for current decision functions using a numerical solver. However, there is a simple derivative-free alternative to time iteration – fixed point iteration – that can solve large systems of equations using only straightforward calculations, avoiding thus the need of a numerical solver. Fixed-point iteration is commonly used in the context of solution methods for dynamic economic models; see, e.g., Wright and Williams (1984), Miranda and Helmberger (1988), Marcet (1988), Den Haan (1990), Marcet and Lorenzoni (1999), Gaspar and Judd (1997), Judd et al. (2010, 2011), Maliar and Maliar (2014b). We assess how the cost of a Smolyak-based projection method for solving dynamic economic models depends on a specific iterative scheme used. We find that time iteration may dominate fixed-point iteration in small-scale applications but the situation reverses when the dimensionality increases. Therefore, we advocate the use of fixed-point iteration instead of time iteration in large-scale applications.

We assess the performance of the Smolyak-based projection method in the context of one- and multi-agent neoclassical stochastic growth models with up to 20 state variables. Our analysis shows that there are substantial accuracy gains from using anisotropic grid and adaptive domain even in the simplest case with two state variables: the maximum residuals in the Euler equations can be reduced by an order of magnitude compared to those produced by the baseline isotropic Smolyak method with the standard hypercube domain (holding the number of the coefficients roughly the same). In multidimensional problems – the real interest of our analysis – the accuracy gains from using anisotropic grid and adaptive domain reach two orders of magnitude in some examples. Our cost grows fairly slowly with the dimensionality of the problem. In particular, our MATLAB code delivers a second-level Smolyak approximation to a model with ten countries (twenty state variables) in about 45 minutes. For comparison,

a Fortran code of Malin et al. (2011), based on the conventional Smolyak method, solves a similar model in about 10 hours. Moreover, we are able to produce a very accurate third-level polynomial approximation to a ten-country model; however, such an approximation is computationally demanding even for our efficient implementation of the Smolyak method (our running time increases to nearly 45 hours).

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: In Section 1.3, we illustrate the inefficiency of the conventional Smolyak formula. In Section 1.4, we introduce an alternative implementation of the Smolyak method based on disjoint-set unidimensional generators and Lagrange interpolation. In Sections 1.5 and 1.6, we develop versions of the Smolyak method with anisotropic grid and adaptive domain, respectively. In Section 1.7, we assess the performance of the Smolyak-based projection method in the context of one- and multi-agent optimal growth models. Finally, in Section 1.8, we conclude.

1.3 Conventional Smolyak method for interpolation

In this section, we describe the conventional Smolyak method for interpolation. In Section 1.3.1, we outline the idea of the Smolyak method and review the related literature. In Sections 1.3.2, 1.3.3 and 1.3.4, we show how to construct the Smolyak grid points, Smolyak polynomial and Smolyak interpolating coefficients, respectively. Finally, in Section 1.3.5, we argue that the conventional Smolyak method is inefficient.

1.3.1 Smolyak method at glance

The problem of representing and interpolating multidimensional functions commonly arises in economics. In particular, when solving dynamic economic models, one needs to represent and interpolate decision and value functions in terms of state variables. With few state variables, one can use tensor-product rules but

such rules become intractable when the number of state variables increases. For example, if there are five grid points per each variable, a tensor product grid for d variables contains 5^d grid points, which is a large number even for moderately large d . Bellman (1961) referred to exponential growth in complexity as a curse of dimensionality.

Smolyak (1963) introduced a numerical technique for representing multidimensional functions, which is tractable in problems with high dimensionality. The key idea of Smolyak's (1963) analysis is that some elements produced by tensor-product rules are more important for representing multidimensional functions than the others. The Smolyak method orders all elements produced by a tensor-product rule by their potential importance for the quality of approximation and selects a relatively small number of the most important elements. A parameter, called a *level of approximation*, controls how many tensor-product elements are included into the Smolyak grid. By increasing the level of approximation, one can add new elements and improve the quality of approximation.³

Examples of Smolyak grids under approximation levels $\mu = 0, 1, 2, 3$ are illustrated in Figure 1.1 for the two-dimensional case. For comparison, we also show a tensor-product grid of 5^2 points.

Figure 1.1: Smolyak grids versus a tensor-product grid

In Table 1.1, we compare the number of points in the Smolyak grid and that in the tensor-product grid with five grid points in each dimension. The

³The level of approximation plays the same role in the Smolyak construction as the order of expansion in the Taylor series, i.e. we include the terms up to a given order, and we neglect

Table 1.1: Number of grid points: tensor-product grid with 5 points in each dimension versus Smolyak grids

d	Tensor-product grid with 5^d points	Smolyak grid		
		$\mu = 1$	$\mu = 2$	$\mu = 3$
1	5	3	5	9
2	25	5	13	29
10	9,765,625	21	221	1581
20	95,367,431,640,625	41	841	11561

number of points in a Smolyak grid grows polynomially with dimensionality d , meaning that the Smolyak method is not subject to the curse of dimensionality. In particular, for $\mu = 1$ and $\mu = 2$, the number of the Smolyak grid points grows as $1 + 2d$ and $1 + 4d + \frac{4d(d-1)}{2}$, i.e. linearly and quadratically, respectively. A relatively small number of points in Smolyak grids sharply contrasts with a huge number of points in tensor-product grids in a high-dimensional case. Because of this, Smolyak grids are also called *sparse grids*.

To interpolate multidimensional functions off the Smolyak grid, two broad classes of interpolants are used in mathematical literature. One class uses hierarchical surplus formulas and piecewise local basis functions; see, e.g., Griebel (1998), Bungartz and Griebel (2004), Klimke and Wohlmuth (2005) and Jakeman and Roberts (2011) for related mathematical results, and see Brumm and Scheidegger (2013) for an economic application. Piecewise functions are very flexible and make it possible to vary the quality of approximations over different areas of the state space as needed. However, the resulting approximations are non-smooth and non-differentiable and also, they have a high computational expense (this interpolation technique is still subject to the curse of dimensionality).

the remaining high-order terms.

The other class of Smolyak interpolants includes global polynomial functions; see, e.g., Delves (1982), Wasilkowski and Woźniakowski (1999) and Barthelmann et al. (2000) for a mathematical background. Global polynomial approximations are smooth and continuously differentiable and also, they are relatively inexpensive. However, their flexibility and adaptivity are limited. In economics, global polynomial approximations are used in Krueger and Kubler (2004), Gavilan-Gonzalez and Rojas (2009), Winschel and Krätzig (2010), Gordon (2011), Malin et al. (2011) and Fernández-Villaverde et al. (2012). In the present paper, we also confine our attention to global polynomial approximations. Below, we show the conventional Smolyak method for interpolation in line with Malin et al. (2011).

1.3.2 Construction of Smolyak grids using unidimensional nested sets

To construct a Smolyak grid, we generate unidimensional sets of grid points, construct tensor products of unidimensional sets and select a subsets of grid points satisfying the Smolyak rule.

Unidimensional nested sets of points

The Smolyak construction begins with one dimension. To generate unidimensional grid points, we use extrema of Chebyshev polynomials (also known as Chebyshev-Gauss-Lobatto points or Clenshaw-Curtis points); see Appendix A. We do not use all consecutive extrema but those that form a sequence S_1, S_2, \dots satisfying two conditions:

Condition 1. A set S_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots$, has $m(i) = 2^{i-1} + 1$ points for $i \geq 2$ and $m(1) \equiv 1$.

Condition 2. Each subsequent set contains all points of the previous set, $S_i \subset S_{i+1}$. Such sets are called *nested*.⁴

⁴There are many other ways to construct sets of points that have a nested structure. For example, we can use subsets of equidistant points; see Appendix A for a discussion. Gauss-

Below, we show the first four nested sets composed of extrema of Chebyshev polynomials:

$$i = 1 : S_1 = \{0\};$$

$$i = 2 : S_2 = \{0, -1, 1\};$$

$$i = 3 : S_3 = \left\{0, -1, 1, \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right\};$$

$$i = 4 : S_4 = \left\{0, -1, 1, \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{-\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}}{2}, \frac{-\sqrt{2-\sqrt{2}}}{2}, \frac{\sqrt{2-\sqrt{2}}}{2}, \frac{\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}}{2}\right\}.$$

Tensor products of unidimensional nested sets of points

Next, we construct tensor products of unidimensional sets of points. As an illustration, we consider a two-dimensional case with $i = 1, 2, 3$ in each dimension.

Table 1.2: Tensor products of disjoint sets of unidimensional grid points for the two-dimensional case

		$i_2 = 1$	$i_2 = 2$	$i_2 = 3$
$S_{i_1} \mid S_{i_2}$		0	0, -1, 1	0, -1, 1, $\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$
$i_1 = 1$	0	(0, 0)	(0, 0), (0, -1), (0, 1)	(0, 0), (0, -1), (0, 1), (0, $\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}), (0, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}})$
$i_1 = 2$	0 -1 1	(0, 0) (-1, 0) (1, 0)	(0, 0), (0, -1), (0, 1) (-1, 0), (-1, -1), (-1, 1) (1, 0), (1, -1), (1, 1)	(0, 0), (0, -1), (0, 1), (0, $\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}), (0, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}})$ (-1, 0), (-1, -1), (-1, 1), (-1, $\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}), (-1, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}})$ (1, 0), (1, -1), (1, 1), (1, $\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}), (1, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}})$
$i_1 = 3$	0 -1 1 $\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}$ $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$	(0, 0) (-1, 0) (1, 0) $(\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, 0)$ $(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, 0)$	(0, 0), (0, -1), (0, 1) (-1, 0), (-1, -1), (-1, 1) $(\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, 0), (\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, -1), (\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, 1)$ $(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, 0), (\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, -1), (\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, 1)$ (1, 0), (1, -1), (1, 1)	(0, 0), (0, -1), (0, 1), (0, $\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}), (0, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}})$ (-1, 0), (-1, -1), (-1, 1), (-1, $\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}), (-1, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}})$ (1, 0), (1, -1), (1, 1), (1, $\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}), (1, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}})$ $(\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, 0), (\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, -1), (\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, 1), (\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}), (\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}})$ $(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, 0), (\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, -1), (\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, 1), (\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}), (\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}})$

In Table 1.2, i_1 and i_2 are indices that correspond to dimensions one and

Patterson points also lead to nested sets, however, the number of points in such sets is different, namely, $m(i) = 2^{i-1} - 1$; see Patterson (1968).

two respectively; a column S_{i_1} and a row S_{i_2} (see $S_{i_1} | S_{i_2}$) show the sets of uni-dimensional elements that correspond to dimensions one and two, respectively.

Smolyak sparse grids

Smolyak (1963) offers a rule that tells us which tensor products must be selected from the table. For the two-dimensional case, we must select tensor products (cells of Table 1.2) for which the following condition is satisfied:

$$d \leq i_1 + i_2 \leq d + \mu, \quad (1.1)$$

where $\mu \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ is the approximation level, and d is the dimensionality (in Table 1.2, $d = 2$). In other words, the sum of a column i_1 and a row i_2 , must be between d and $d + \mu$.

Let $\mathcal{H}^{d,\mu}$ denote a Smolyak grid for a problem with dimensionality d and approximation level μ . Let us construct Smolyak grids for $\mu = 0, 1, 2$ and $d = 2$ using Smolyak rule (1.1).

- If $\mu = 0$, then $2 \leq i_1 + i_2 \leq 2$. The only cell in Table 1.2 that satisfies this restriction is $i_1 = 1$ and $i_2 = 1$, so that the Smolyak grid has just one grid point,

$$\mathcal{H}^{2,0} = \{(0, 0)\}. \quad (1.2)$$

- If $\mu = 1$, then $2 \leq i_1 + i_2 \leq 3$. The three cells that satisfy this restriction are (a) $i_1 = 1, i_2 = 1$; (b) $i_1 = 1, i_2 = 2$; (c) $i_1 = 2, i_2 = 1$, and the corresponding five Smolyak grid points are

$$\mathcal{H}^{2,1} = \{(0, 0), (-1, 0), (1, 0), (0, -1), (0, 1)\}. \quad (1.3)$$

- If $\mu = 2$, then $2 \leq i_1 + i_2 \leq 4$. There are six cells that satisfy this restriction: (a) $i_1 = 1, i_2 = 1$; (b) $i_1 = 1, i_2 = 2$; (c) $i_1 = 2, i_2 = 1$; (d) $i_1 = 1, i_2 = 3$; (e) $i_1 = 2, i_2 = 2$; (f) $i_1 = 3, i_2 = 1$, and there are thirteen

Smolyak grid points,

$$\mathcal{H}^{2,2} = \left\{ (-1, 1), (0, 1), (1, 1), (-1, 0), (0, 0), (1, 0), (-1, -1), (0, -1), \right. \\ \left. (1, -1), \left(\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, 0\right), \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, 0\right), \left(0, \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}\right), \left(0, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \right\}. \quad (1.4)$$

Smolyak grids $\mathcal{H}^{2,0}$, $\mathcal{H}^{2,1}$ and $\mathcal{H}^{2,2}$ are those that are shown in the first three subplots of Figure 1.1.

1.3.3 Smolyak formula for interpolation using unidimensional nested sets

The conventional technique for constructing a Smolyak polynomial function also builds on unidimensional nested sets and mimics the construction of a Smolyak grid.

Smolyak polynomial

Let $\widehat{f}^{d,\mu}$ denote a Smolyak polynomial function (interpolant) in dimension d , with approximation level μ . The Smolyak interpolant is a linear combination of tensor-product operators $p^{|\mathbf{i}|}$ given by

$$\widehat{f}^{d,\mu}(x_1, \dots, x_d; b) = \sum_{\max(d, \mu+1) \leq |\mathbf{i}| \leq d+\mu} (-1)^{d+\mu-|\mathbf{i}|} \binom{d-1}{d+\mu-|\mathbf{i}|} p^{|\mathbf{i}|}(x_1, \dots, x_d), \quad (1.5)$$

where $|\mathbf{i}|$ is defined as $|\mathbf{i}| \equiv i_1 + \dots + i_d$ and $(-1)^{d+\mu-|\mathbf{i}|} \binom{d-1}{d+\mu-|\mathbf{i}|}$ is a counting coefficient. For each $|\mathbf{i}|$ satisfying $\max(d, \mu+1) \leq |\mathbf{i}| \leq d+\mu$, a tensor-product operator $p^{|\mathbf{i}|}(x_1, \dots, x_d)$ is defined as

$$p^{|\mathbf{i}|}(x_1, \dots, x_d) = \sum_{i_1 + \dots + i_d = |\mathbf{i}|} p^{i_1, \dots, i_d}(x_1, \dots, x_d), \quad (1.6)$$

and p^{i_1, \dots, i_d} is defined as

$$p^{i_1, \dots, i_d}(x_1, \dots, x_d) = \sum_{\ell_1=1}^{m(i_1)} \dots \sum_{\ell_d=1}^{m(i_d)} b_{\ell_1 \dots \ell_d} \psi_{\ell_1}(x_1) \cdots \psi_{\ell_d}(x_d), \quad (1.7)$$

where $m(i_j)$ is the number of basis functions in dimension j , with $m(i_j) \equiv 2^{i_j-1}+1$ for $i_j \geq 2$ and $m(1) \equiv 1$; $\psi_{\ell_j}(x_j)$ is a ℓ_j th unidimensional basis function in dimension j with $\ell_j = 1, \dots, m(i_j)$; $\psi_{\ell_1}(x_1) \cdots \psi_{\ell_d}(x_d)$ is a d -dimensional basis function and $b_{\ell_1 \dots \ell_d}$ s are the corresponding polynomial coefficients.

Example of Smolyak polynomial under $d = 2$ and $\mu = 1$

We now illustrate the construction of Smolyak polynomial function (1.5) under $d = 2$ and $\mu = 1$; in Appendix B, we show the construction of such a function under $d = 2$ and $\mu = 2$.

For the case of $\mu = 1$, we have that $2 \leq |i| \leq 3$. This is satisfied in three cases: (a) $i_1 = i_2 = 1$; (b) $i_1 = 1, i_2 = 2$; (c) $i_1 = 2, i_2 = 1$. From (1.7), we obtain

$$(a) \ p^{1,1} = \sum_{\ell_1=1}^{m(1)} \sum_{\ell_2=1}^{m(1)} b_{\ell_1 \ell_2} \psi_{\ell_1}(x) \psi_{\ell_2}(y) = b_{11}, \quad (1.8)$$

$$(b) \ p^{1,2} = \sum_{\ell_1=1}^{m(1)} \sum_{\ell_2=1}^{m(2)} b_{\ell_1 \ell_2} \psi_{\ell_1}(x) \psi_{\ell_2}(y) = b_{11} + b_{12} \psi_2(y) + b_{13} \psi_3(y), \quad (1.9)$$

$$(c) \ p^{2,1} = \sum_{\ell_1=1}^{m(2)} \sum_{\ell_2=1}^{m(1)} b_{\ell_1 \ell_2} \psi_{\ell_1}(x) \psi_{\ell_2}(y) = b_{11} + b_{21} \psi_2(x) + b_{31} \psi_3(x), \quad (1.10)$$

where we assume that $\psi_1(x) = \psi_1(y) \equiv 1$. Collecting the elements p^{i_1, i_2} with the same sum $i_1 + i_2 \equiv |i|$, we obtain

$$p^{2,1} \equiv p^{1,1}, \quad (1.11)$$

$$p^{3,1} \equiv p^{2,1} + p^{1,2}. \quad (1.12)$$

Smolyak polynomial function (1.5) for the case of $d = 2$ and $\mu = 1$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\widehat{f}^{2,1}(x, y; b) &= \sum_{\max(d, \mu+1) \leq |i| \leq d+\mu} (-1)^{d+\mu-|i|} \binom{d-1}{d+\mu-|i|} p^{|i|} \\
&= \sum_{2 \leq |i| \leq 3} (-1)^{3-|i|} \binom{1}{3-|i|} p^{|i|} = \sum_{2 \leq |i| \leq 3} (-1)^{3-|i|} \frac{1}{(3-|i|)!} p^{|i|} \\
&= (-1) \cdot p^{|2|} + 1 \cdot p^{|3|} \\
&= (-1) \cdot p^{1,1} + 1 \cdot (p^{2,1} + p^{1,2}) \\
&= -b_{11} + b_{11} + b_{21}\psi_2(x) + b_{31}\psi_3(x) + b_{11} + b_{12}\psi_2(y) + b_{13}\psi_3(y) \\
&= b_{11} + b_{21}\psi_2(x) + b_{31}\psi_3(x) + b_{12}\psi_2(y) + b_{13}\psi_3(y). \quad (1.13)
\end{aligned}$$

By construction, the number of basis functions in Smolyak polynomial $\widehat{f}^{2,1}(x, y; b)$ is equal to the number of points in Smolyak grid $\mathcal{H}^{2,1}$. The same is true for a Smolyak grid $\mathcal{H}^{d,\mu}$ and Smolyak polynomial $\widehat{f}^{d,\mu}$ under any $d \geq 1$ and $\mu \geq 0$.

1.3.4 Smolyak interpolation coefficients

Polynomial coefficients $b_{\ell_1 \dots \ell_d}$ s in (1.5) must be constructed so that Smolyak polynomial $\widehat{f}^{d,\mu}$ matches the true function f in all points of Smolyak grid $H^{d,\mu}$. In the present paper, we construct multidimensional Smolyak polynomials using unidimensional Chebyshev polynomial basis functions.

Closed-form expression for Smolyak interpolation coefficients

There is a closed-form formula for the polynomial coefficients in (1.5) if multidimensional Smolyak grid points and basis functions are constructed using unidimensional Chebyshev polynomials and their extrema, respectively; see Quarteroni et al. (2000) for a derivation of such formulas. Consider a grid that has $m(i_1), \dots, m(i_d)$ grid points and basis functions in dimensions 1, ..., d , respec-

tively. Then, the corresponding coefficients are given by

$$b_{\ell_1 \dots \ell_d} = \frac{2^d}{(m(i_1) - 1) \dots (m(i_d) - 1)} \cdot \frac{1}{c_{\ell_1} \dots c_{\ell_d}} \times \sum_{j_1=1}^{m(i_1)} \dots \sum_{j_d=1}^{m(i_d)} \frac{\psi_{\ell_1}(\zeta_{j_1}) \dots \psi_{\ell_d}(\zeta_{j_d}) \cdot f(\zeta_{j_1}, \dots, \zeta_{j_d})}{c_{j_1} \dots c_{j_d}}, \quad (1.14)$$

where $\zeta_{j_1}, \dots, \zeta_{j_d}$ are grid points in dimensions j_1, \dots, j_d , respectively; $c_2 = 1$; $c_2 = c_3 = 2$; and $c_j = 1$ for $j = 4, \dots, m(i_d)$. If along any dimension d , we have $m(i_d) = 1$, this dimension is dropped from computation, i.e. $m(i_d) - 1$ is set to 1 and $c_{j_d} = c_1$ is set to 1.

We shall comment on the following notational issue. We ordered the Smolyak elements so that we do not need to distinguish between grid points and basis functions corresponding to different levels of approximation. This simplifies notation considerably. For example, for $i_d = 1$, the node is $\zeta_1^1 = 0$, and for $i_2 = 2$, we write the nodes as $\{\zeta_1^2, \zeta_2^2, \zeta_3^2\} = \{0, -1, 1\}$; we set $\zeta_1^1 = \zeta_1^2 \equiv \zeta_1$ and we omit the approximation-level superscript. We do the same for the basis functions, for example, we set $\psi_1^1 = \psi_1^2 \equiv \psi_1$, etc. Finally, we define $c_{j_1} \dots c_{j_d}$ in a way that allows us to omit the approximation-level superscript. Note that under other orderings of Smolyak elements we need to keep the approximation-level superscript, for example, if we set $\zeta_1^1 = 0$, and $\{\zeta_1^2, \zeta_2^2, \zeta_3^2\} = \{-1, 0, 1\}$, then we have $\zeta_1^1 \neq \zeta_1^2$.

Example of the Smolyak coefficients under $d = 2$ and $\mu = 1$

We must compute the coefficients $\{b_{11}, b_{21}, b_{31}, b_{12}, b_{13}\}$ so that polynomial function $\hat{f}^{2,1}$, given by (1.13), matches true function f on Smolyak grid $\mathcal{H}^{2,1}$ given by (1.3). For $\mu = 1$, the set of Chebyshev polynomial basis are $\{\psi_1(x), \psi_2(x), \psi_3(x)\} = \{1, x, 2x^2 - 1\}$ (and we have the same polynomial basis for y , namely, $\{1, y, 2y^2 - 1\}$); the extrema of Chebyshev polynomials are $\{\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \zeta_3\} = \{0, -1, 1\}$; and finally, we have $c_1 = 1, c_2 = c_3 = 2$.

For b_{21} , formula (1.14) implies

$$\begin{aligned} b_{21} &= \frac{2}{3-1} \cdot \frac{1}{c_2} \sum_{j_1=1}^3 \frac{\psi_2(\zeta_{j_1}) \cdot f(\zeta_{j_1}, 0)}{c_{j_1} \cdot 1} \\ &= \frac{\psi_2(\zeta_1) \cdot f(\zeta_1, 0)}{c_1} + \frac{\psi_2(\zeta_2) \cdot f(\zeta_2, 0)}{c_2} + \frac{\psi_2(\zeta_3) \cdot f(\zeta_3, 0)}{c_3} \\ &= \frac{-1 \cdot f(-1, 0)}{2} + \frac{1 \cdot f(1, 0)}{2}; \end{aligned}$$

similarly, for b_{12} , we get

$$b_{12} = -\frac{f(0, -1)}{2} + \frac{f(0, 1)}{2}.$$

Coefficient b_{31} is given by

$$\begin{aligned} b_{31} &= \frac{2}{3-1} \cdot \frac{1}{c_3} \sum_{j_1=1}^3 \frac{\psi_3(\zeta_{j_1}) \cdot f(\zeta_{j_1}, 0)}{c_{j_1}} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{1 \cdot f(-1, 0)}{2} - f(0, 0) + \frac{1 \cdot f(1, 0)}{2} \right] \\ &= -\frac{f(0, 0)}{2} + \frac{f(-1, 0) + f(1, 0)}{4}, \end{aligned}$$

and b_{13} is obtained similarly

$$b_{13} = -\frac{f(0, 0)}{2} + \frac{f(0, -1) + f(0, 1)}{4}.$$

Formula (1.14) does not apply to a constant term b_{11} . To find b_{11} , observe that (1.13) implies

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{f}^{2,1}(0, 0; b) &= \\ b_{11} + \frac{f(0, 0)}{2} - \frac{f(-1, 0) + f(1, 0)}{4} + \frac{f(0, 0)}{2} - \frac{f(0, -1) + f(0, 1)}{4}. \end{aligned}$$

Since under interpolation, we must have $\widehat{f}^{2,1}(0, 0; b) = f(0, 0)$, the last formula yields

$$b_{11} = \frac{f(-1, 0) + f(1, 0) + f(0, -1) + f(0, 1)}{4}.$$

Note that to compute the coefficients, we need to evaluate function f in five Smolyak grid points of $\mathcal{H}^{2,1}$.

1.3.5 Shortcomings of the conventional Smolyak method

The conventional Smolyak method using nested sets is inefficient. First, it creates a list of tensor products with many repeated elements and then, it eliminates the repetitions. In high-dimensional applications, the number of repetitions is large and increases with both μ and d , which leads to a considerable increase in computational expense.

Repetitions of grid points can be appreciated by looking at Table 1.2. For example, when constructing $\mathcal{H}^{2,1}$, we list a grid point $(0,0)$ in three different cells, and hence, we must eliminate two grid points out of seven; when constructing $\mathcal{H}^{2,2}$, we must eliminate thirteen repeated points out of twenty six points, etc. However, the repeated grid points are not a critical issue for computational expense. This is because grid points must be constructed just once (it is a one-time fixed cost), and it is not so important if they are constructed efficiently or not.

Unfortunately, the Smolyak formula (1.5) involves the same kind of repetitions, and it is not a fixed cost. For example, $\hat{f}^{2,1}$, given by (1.13), lists seven basis functions $\{1\}$, $\{1, \psi_2(x), \psi_3(x)\}$ and $\{1, \psi_2(y), \psi_3(y)\}$ in (1.8)–(1.10), respectively, and eliminates two repeated functions $\{1\}$ by assigning a weight (-1) to $p^{|2|}$; furthermore, $\hat{f}^{2,2}$, derived in Appendix B, creates a list of twenty six basis functions and removes thirteen repeated basis function by assigning appropriate weights, etc. We suffer from repetitions every time we evaluate a Smolyak polynomial function. This is an especially important issue in the context of numerical methods for solving dynamic economic models, since we must interpolate decision and value functions in a very large number of points, e.g., grid points, integration nodes and time periods. Moreover, we must repeat interpolation each time when the decision and value functions change in the iterative cycle. The overall cost of repetitions in the Smolyak formula can be very large.

1.4 Efficient implementation of the Smolyak method for interpolation

We have argued that the Smolyak (1963) sparse-grid structure is an efficient choice for high-dimensional interpolation. However, the existing implementation of the Smolyak method does not arrive to this structure directly. Instead, it produces such a structure using a linear combinations of sets with repeated elements, which is inefficient and expensive. In this section, we propose a more efficient implementation of the Smolyak method that avoids costly repetitions of elements and arrives to the Smolyak structure directly. Our key novelty is to replace the conventional nested-set generators with equivalent disjoint-set generators. We use the disjoint-set generators not only for constructing Smolyak grids but also for constructing Smolyak basis functions; as a result, we do not make use of the conventional interpolation formula of type (1.7). Furthermore, to identify the interpolating coefficients, we use a canonical Lagrange interpolation; thus, we also do not make use of formula (1.14) for the coefficient. We find it easiest to present our implementation of the Smolyak method starting from a description of the Lagrange interpolation framework.

1.4.1 Multidimensional Lagrange interpolation

We consider the following interpolation problem. Let $f : [-1, 1]^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a smooth function defined on a normalized d -dimensional hypercube, and let $\hat{f}(\cdot; b)$ be a polynomial function of the form

$$\hat{f}(x; b) = \sum_{n=1}^M b_n \Psi_n(x), \quad (1.15)$$

where $\Psi_n : [-1, 1]^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $n = 1, \dots, M$, are d -dimensional basis functions, and $b \equiv (b_1, \dots, b_M)$ is a coefficient vector.

We construct a set of M grid points $\{x_1, \dots, x_M\}$ in $[-1, 1]^d$, and we compute b so that the true function, f , and its approximation, $\hat{f}(\cdot; b)$ coincide in all grid

points:

$$\begin{bmatrix} f(x_1) \\ \dots \\ f(x_M) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \widehat{f}(x_1; b) \\ \dots \\ \widehat{f}(x_M; b) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \Psi_1(x_1) & \dots & \Psi_M(x_1) \\ \dots & \ddots & \dots \\ \Psi_1(x_M) & \dots & \Psi_M(x_M) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} b_1 \\ \dots \\ b_M \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1.16)$$

Approximation $\widehat{f}(\cdot; b)$ is used to interpolate (infer, reconstruct) f in any point $x \in [-1, 1]^d$.

To implement the above interpolation method, we must perform three steps:

- (i) Choose M grid points $\{x_1, \dots, x_M\}$.
- (ii) Choose M basis functions for forming $\widehat{f}(x; b)$.
- (iii) Compute b that makes f and $\widehat{f}(\cdot; b)$ coincide in all grid points.

Lagrange interpolation allows for many different choices of grid points and basis functions. We will use grid points and basis functions produced by the Smolyak method. In Section 1.4.2, we construct the Smolyak grid points; in Section 1.4.3, we produce the Smolyak basis functions; in Section 1.4.4, we identify the interpolation coefficients; in Section 1.4.5, we compare our implementation of the Smolyak method with the conventional implementation described in Section 1.3; and finally, in Section 1.4.6, we show an efficient formula for Smolyak interpolation.

1.4.2 Construction of Smolyak grids using unidimensional disjoint sets

To construct a Smolyak grid, we proceed as in the conventional Smolyak method, namely, we produce sets of unidimensional grid points, compute tensor products of such sets and select an appropriate subsets of tensor-product elements for constructing a multidimensional grid. The difference is that we operate with unidimensional disjoint sets instead of unidimensional nested sets. This allows us to avoid repetitions of grid points.

Unidimensional disjoint sets of grid points

Let us define a sequence of disjoint sets A_1, A_2, \dots using the sequence of nested sets S_1, S_2, \dots of Section 1.3.2 such that $A_1 = S_1$ and $A_i = S_i \setminus S_{i-1}$ for $i \geq 2$:

$$i = 1 : A_1 = \{0\};$$

$$i = 2 : A_2 = \{-1, 1\};$$

$$i = 3 : A_3 = \left\{ \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \right\};$$

$$i = 4 : A_4 = \left\{ \frac{-\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}}{2}, \frac{-\sqrt{2-\sqrt{2}}}{2}, \frac{\sqrt{2-\sqrt{2}}}{2}, \frac{\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}}{2} \right\}.$$

By definition, A_i is a set of points in S_i but not in S_{i-1} , i.e. $S_i \setminus S_{i-1}$. The constructed sets are disjoint, $A_i \cap A_j = \{\emptyset\}$ for any $i \neq j$ and their unions satisfy $A_1 \cup \dots \cup A_i = S_i$. The number of elements in A_i is $m(i) - m(i-1) = 2^{i-2}$ points for $i \geq 3$, and the number of elements in A_1 and A_2 is 1 and 2, respectively.

Tensor products of unidimensional disjoint sets of points

Next, we construct tensor products of disjoint sets of unidimensional grid points.

Again, we consider the two-dimensional case, with $i = 1, 2, 3$ in each dimension.

Table 1.3: Tensor products of disjoint sets of unidimensional grid points for the two-dimensional case

		$i_2 = 1$	$i_2 = 2$	$i_2 = 3$
	$A_{i_1} \mid A_{i_2}$	0	-1, 1	$\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$
$i_1 = 1$	0	(0, 0)	(0, -1), (0, 1)	$\left(0, \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}\right), \left(0, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)$
$i_1 = 2$	-1 1	(-1, 0) (1, 0)	(-1, -1), (-1, 1) (1, -1), (1, 1)	$\left(-1, \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}\right), \left(-1, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)$ $\left(1, \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}\right), \left(1, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)$
$i_1 = 3$	$\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}$ $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$	$\left(\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, 0\right)$ $\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, 0\right)$	$\left(\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, -1\right), \left(\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, 1\right)$ $\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, -1\right), \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, 1\right)$	$\left(\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}\right), \left(\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)$ $\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}\right), \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)$

In Table 1.3, i_1 and i_2 are indices that correspond to dimensions one and two, respectively; a column A_{i_1} and a row A_{i_2} (see $A_{i_1} \setminus A_{i_2}$) show the sets of unidimensional elements that correspond to dimensions one and two, respectively; (ζ_ℓ, ζ_n) denotes a two-dimensional grid point obtained by combining a grid point ζ_ℓ in dimension one and a grid point ζ_n in dimension two. Thus, the table shows incremental grid points, and we can easily see which grid points are added when we increase the approximation level.

Smolyak sparse grids

We use the same Smolyak rule (1.1) for constructing multidimensional grid points. That is, we select elements that belong to the cells in Table 1.3 for which the sum of indices of a column and a row, $i_1 + i_2$, is between d and $d + \mu$. This leads to the same Smolyak grids $\mathcal{H}^{2,0}$, $\mathcal{H}^{2,1}$ and $\mathcal{H}^{2,2}$ as is shown in (1.2), (1.3), and (1.4), respectively. However, in our case, no grid point is repeated in Table 1.3. Furthermore, note that the multidimensional grids $\mathcal{H}^{2,0}$, $\mathcal{H}^{2,1}$ and $\mathcal{H}^{2,2}$ are nested $\mathcal{H}^{2,0} \subset \mathcal{H}^{2,1} \subset \mathcal{H}^{2,2}$ even though their unidimensional generators are disjoint (i.e. not nested).

1.4.3 Construction of Smolyak polynomials using unidimensional disjoint sets

Our construction of Smolyak polynomials parallels our construction of Smolyak grids using unidimensional disjoint sets. To be specific, we produce disjoint sets of unidimensional basis functions, compute tensor products of such sets and select an appropriate subset of tensor-product elements for constructing a multidimensional polynomial function. Again, using disjoint-set generators instead of nested-set generators allows us to avoid repetitions of basis functions.

Unidimensional disjoint sets of basis functions

We first construct disjoint sets F_1, \dots, F_i, \dots that contain unidimensional basis functions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 i = 1 : F_1 &= \{1\}; \\
 i = 2 : F_2 &= \{\psi_2(x), \psi_3(x)\}; \\
 i = 3 : F_3 &= \{\psi_4(x), \psi_5(x)\}. \\
 i = 4 : F_4 &= \{\psi_6(x), \psi_7(x), \psi_8(x), \psi_9(x)\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Tensor products of unidimensional disjoint sets of basis functions

We next construct the two-dimensional basis functions using tensor products of unidimensional basis functions.

Table 1.4: Tensor products of disjoint sets of Chebyshev polynomial basis for the two-dimensional case

		$i_2 = 1$	$i_2 = 2$	$i_2 = 3$
	$F_{i_1} \mid F_{i_2}$	1	$\psi_2(y), \psi_3(y)$	$\psi_4(y), \psi_5(y)$
$i_1 = 1$	1	1	$\psi_2(y), \psi_3(y)$	$\psi_4(y), \psi_5(y)$
$i_1 = 2$	$\psi_2(x)$ $\psi_3(x)$	$\psi_2(x)$ $\psi_3(x)$	$\psi_2(x)\psi_2(y), \psi_2(x)\psi_3(y)$ $\psi_3(x)\psi_2(y), \psi_3(x)\psi_3(y)$	$\psi_2(x)\psi_4(y), \psi_2(x)\psi_5(y)$ $\psi_3(x)\psi_4(y), \psi_3(x)\psi_5(y)$
$i_1 = 3$	$\psi_4(x)$ $\psi_5(x)$	$\psi_4(x)$ $\psi_5(x)$	$\psi_4(x)\psi_2(y), \psi_4(x)\psi_3(y)$ $\psi_5(x)\psi_2(y), \psi_5(x)\psi_3(y)$	$\psi_4(x)\psi_4(y), \psi_4(x)\psi_5(y)$ $\psi_5(x)\psi_4(y), \psi_5(x)\psi_5(y)$

By construction, all elements in Table 1.4 appear just once and therefore, are non-repeated. Note that Table 1.4 looks exactly like Table 1.3 (but for basis functions).

Smolyak polynomial basis functions

We apply the same Smolyak rule (1.1) to produce a list of basis function as we used for producing grid points. Let $\mathcal{P}^{d,\mu}$ denote a Smolyak basis function with dimensionality d and approximation level μ .

- If $\mu = 0$, then $2 \leq i_1 + i_2 \leq 2$. The only cell that satisfies this restriction is $i_1 = 1$ and $i_2 = 1$, so that the set of Smolyak basis functions has just one element

$$\mathcal{P}^{2,0} = \{1\}. \quad (1.17)$$

- If $\mu = 1$, then $2 \leq i_1 + i_2 \leq 3$. The three cells that satisfy this restriction are (a) $i_1 = 1, i_2 = 1$; (b) $i_1 = 1, i_2 = 2$; (c) $i_1 = 2, i_2 = 1$, and the corresponding five Smolyak basis functions are

$$\mathcal{P}^{2,1} = \{1, \psi_2(x), \psi_3(x), \psi_2(y), \psi_3(y)\}. \quad (1.18)$$

- If $\mu = 2$, then $2 \leq i_1 + i_2 \leq 4$. There are six cells that satisfy this restriction: (a) $i_1 = 1, i_2 = 1$; (b) $i_1 = 1, i_2 = 2$; (c) $i_1 = 2, i_2 = 1$; (d) $i_1 = 1, i_2 = 3$; (e) $i_1 = 2, i_2 = 2$; (f) $i_1 = 3, i_2 = 1$, and there are thirteen Smolyak basis functions

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}^{2,2} = \{ & 1, \psi_2(x), \psi_3(x), \psi_2(y), \psi_3(y), \psi_4(x), \psi_5(x), \psi_4(y), \psi_5(y) \\ & \psi_2(x)\psi_2(y), \psi_2(x)\psi_3(y), \psi_3(x)\psi_2(y), \psi_3(x)\psi_3(y)\}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.19)$$

The sets of Smolyak basis functions $\mathcal{P}^{2,0}$, $\mathcal{P}^{2,1}$ and $\mathcal{P}^{2,2}$ defined in (1.17), (1.18), and (1.19) are used respectively with the grids $\mathcal{H}^{2,0}$, $\mathcal{H}^{2,1}$ and $\mathcal{H}^{2,2}$ defined in (1.2), (1.3), and (1.4). To form a Smolyak polynomial function, one just needs to use the elements satisfying condition (1.1) since no element is repeated in Table 1.4 by construction.

1.4.4 Construction of Smolyak coefficients using Lagrange interpolation

Recall that coefficients $b_{\ell_1 \dots \ell_d}$ s in (1.5) must be constructed so that the Smolyak polynomial $\hat{f}^{d,\mu}$ matches the true function f on the Smolyak grid $\mathcal{H}^{d,\mu}$. We construct the Smolyak interpolating coefficients solving the inverse problem (1.16) numerically.

Solution to the inverse problem

Provided that the matrix of basis functions in the right side of (1.16) has full rank, we obtain a system of M linear equations with M unknowns that admits a unique solution for b :

$$\begin{bmatrix} b_1 \\ \dots \\ b_M \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \Psi_1(x_1) & \dots & \Psi_M(x_1) \\ \dots & \ddots & \dots \\ \Psi_1(x_M) & \dots & \Psi_M(x_M) \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} f(x_1) \\ \dots \\ f(x_M) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1.20)$$

By construction, the approximating polynomial \hat{f} coincides with the true function f in all grid points, i.e. $\hat{f}(x_n; b) = f(x_n)$ for all $x_n \in \{x_1, \dots, x_M\}$.

Example of interpolation coefficients under $d = 2$ and $\mu = 1$ revisited

Let us now construct the Smolyak polynomial coefficients under $d = 2$ and $\mu = 1$ by solving the inverse problem as shown in (1.20). We again use unidimensional Chebyshev polynomials and extrema of Chebyshev polynomials. As follows from (1.18), the Smolyak polynomial function is given by

$$\hat{f}(x, y; b) \equiv b_{11} \cdot 1 + b_{21}x + b_{31}(2x^2 - 1) + b_{12}y + b_{13}(2y^2 - 1), \quad (1.21)$$

where $b \equiv (b_{11}, b_{21}, b_{31}, b_{12}, b_{13})$ is a vector of five unknown coefficients on five basis functions. We identify the coefficients such that the approximation $\hat{f}(x, y; b)$ matches the true function $f(x, y)$ in five Smolyak grid points distinguished in (1.3), namely, $\{(0, 0), (-1, 0), (1, 0), (0, -1), (0, 1)\}$.

This yields a system of linear equations $Bb = w$, where

$$B \equiv \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & 1 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 & -1 & -1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & -1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}; \quad b \equiv \begin{bmatrix} b_{11} \\ b_{21} \\ b_{31} \\ b_{12} \\ b_{13} \end{bmatrix}; \quad w \equiv \begin{bmatrix} f(0, 0) \\ f(-1, 0) \\ f(1, 0) \\ f(0, -1) \\ f(0, 1) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1.22)$$

The solution to this system is given by $b = \mathcal{B}^{-1}w$,

$$\begin{bmatrix} b_{11} \\ b_{21} \\ b_{31} \\ b_{12} \\ b_{13} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{4} & \frac{1}{4} & \frac{1}{4} & \frac{1}{4} \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{4} & \frac{1}{4} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ -\frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{4} & \frac{1}{4} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f(0,0) \\ f(-1,0) \\ f(1,0) \\ f(0,-1) \\ f(0,1) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{f(-1,0)+f(1,0)+f(0,-1)+f(0,1)}{4} \\ \frac{-f(-1,0)+f(1,0)}{2} \\ -\frac{f(0,0)}{2} + \frac{f(-1,0)+f(1,0)}{4} \\ \frac{-f(0,-1)+f(0,1)}{2} \\ -\frac{f(0,0)}{2} + \frac{f(0,-1)+f(0,1)}{4} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.23)$$

As expected, the coefficients in (2.7.2) coincide with those produced by conventional formula (1.14).

1.4.5 Comparison to the conventional Smolyak method

We compare our implementation of the Smolyak method with the conventional implementation described in Section 1.3. First, we quantify the reduction in cost of the Smolyak interpolant's evaluation that we achieve by avoiding the repetitions and then, we compare the Lagrange interpolation method with explicit formulas for the interpolating coefficients.

Nested-set versus disjoint-set constructions of the Smolyak interpolant

First, consider the conventional construction of the Smolyak polynomial in (1.5) based on unidimensional nested sets; see Section 1.3.3. By (1.5), the number of terms which we list to evaluate $\hat{f}^{d,\mu}$ is $\sum_{\max(d,\mu+1) \leq |i| \leq d+\mu} \prod_{j=1}^d m(i_j)$. Note that the counting coefficient $(-1)^{d+\mu-|i|} \binom{d-1}{d+\mu-|i|}$ is not relevant for computation of the number of terms because it does not add new terms but only counts the number of repetitions to be cancelled out.

Second, consider our alternative construction of the Smolyak polynomial function based on unidimensional disjoint sets; see Section 1.4.3. The number of basis functions in $\mathcal{P}^{d,\mu}$ is equal to $\sum_{d \leq |i| \leq d+\mu} \prod_{j=1}^d [m(i_j) - m(i_j - 1)]$. To assess the difference in costs between the two constructions, we consider a ratio of the

Figure 1.2: The ratio of the number of basis functions under two alternative implementations of the Smolyak method

number of terms under the two constructions:

$$R^{d,\mu} \equiv \frac{\sum_{\max(d,\mu+1) \leq |i| \leq d+\mu} \prod_{j=1}^d m(i_j)}{\sum_{d \leq |i| \leq d+\mu} \prod_{j=1}^d [m(i_j) - m(i_j - 1)]} = \frac{\sum_{\max(d,\mu+1) \leq |i| \leq d+\mu} \prod_{j=1}^d m(i_j)}{\sum_{d \leq |i| \leq d+\mu} \prod_{j=1}^d m(i_j) \prod_{j=1}^d \left(1 - \frac{m(i_j - 1)}{m(i_j)}\right)}, \quad (1.24)$$

where $m(0) = 0$. In Figure 1.2, we represent the ratio $R^{d,\mu}$ for $1 \leq d \leq 10$ and $0 \leq \mu \leq 5$. The "iso-function-count" in the graph shows the number of the Smolyak elements.

The higher is the level of approximation, the larger are the savings due to a more efficient evaluation of the Smolyak interpolant. In particular, under $\mu = 1$, the conventional nested-set construction of the Smolyak interpolant is up to 50 percent more expensive than our construction, while under $\mu = 5$, it can be more than 700 percent more expensive. For high-dimensional applications, the

tractable level of approximation is $1 \leq \mu \leq 3$, so that the savings vary from 1.5 to 4. However, we shall emphasize that our construction saves on cost every time when the Smolyak interpolant is evaluated, i.e. in every grid point, integration node or time period.

Some qualitative assessment of $R^{d,\mu}$ can be derived for the case when $\max(d, \mu + 1) = d$ (this is the most relevant case for high-dimensional problems in which high-order polynomial approximations are infeasible). Consider the term $\prod_{j=1}^d \left(1 - \frac{m(i_j-1)}{m(i_j)}\right)$ in the denominator of (1.24). If $i_j = 1$, we have $1 - \frac{m(0)}{m(1)} = 1$, and if $i_j \geq 2$, we have $1 - \frac{m(i_j-1)}{m(i_j)} = \left(1 - \frac{2^{i_j-2}+1}{2^{i_j-1}+1}\right) = \frac{2^{i_j-2}}{2^{i_j-1}+1}$. Observe that $\frac{1}{3} \leq \frac{2^{i_j-2}}{2^{i_j-1}+1} \leq \frac{1}{2}$ for $i_j \geq 2$, and that the limits are reached under $i_j = 2$ and $i_j \rightarrow \infty$, respectively. This means that for any $i_j \geq 2$, our disjoint-set construction reduces the number of terms by at least a factor of $\frac{1}{3}$ compared to the conventional nested-set construction. For higher approximation levels, the savings are larger, for example, for $i_j \geq 3$, we have $\frac{2}{5} \leq \frac{2^{i_j-2}}{2^{i_j-1}+1} \leq \frac{1}{2}$, etc.

Analytical expression for interpolation coefficients versus numerical Lagrange interpolation

The Lagrange interpolation method is universal: it can be applied to any sets of grid points and basis functions provided that the inverse problem (1.20) is well-defined (the matrix of basis functions evaluated in grid points has full rank). In turn, the formula of type (1.14) is a special case of Lagrange interpolation in which the solution to the inverse problem can be derived in a closed form. Using closed-form expressions to calculate the Smolyak interpolation coefficients is relatively inexpensive. Furthermore, Petras (2001) proposes a "divide and conquer" method that allows to reduce even further the cost of evaluating closed-form expressions for the coefficients. His method exploits the fact that expressions of type (1.14) contain repeated computations; it stores the repeated elements in a tree and uses them as needed.

Our numerical implementation of Lagrange interpolation using (1.20) has two potential shortcomings compared to the closed-form expression: first, it

Figure 1.3: Condition number of the matrix of basis functions in the inverse problem

can be numerically unstable and second, it can be expensive.

To attain numerical stability, we use families of grid points and basis functions that do not lead to ill-conditioned inverse problems. Chebyshev polynomials and their extrema are one example but many other choices are possible.⁵ In Figure 3, we report a condition number of the matrix of basis functions in the associated inverse problem. As a condition number, we use a ratio of the largest to the smallest eigenvalue. In all the cases considered, the condition number is always smaller than 10^5 while an inverse problem is ill-conditioned when the condition number is of order 10^{15} on a 16-digit machine.

To reduce the computational expense, we use the following precomputation technique in the context of numerical algorithm for solving dynamic economic models. We compute an inverse of the matrix of basis functions in (1.20) at

⁵See Judd et al. (2011) for a discussion of numerical techniques for dealing with ill-conditioned problems.

the initialization stage, before entering the main iterative cycle. In this way, the expensive part of Lagrange interpolation becomes a fixed cost. In the main iterative cycle, computing the interpolation coefficients requires only inexpensive matrix multiplications, which can be easily parallelized for a further reduction in cost if needed. This precomputation technique allows us to reconstruct the polynomial coefficients at a low cost each time when decision and value functions change along iterations.⁶

1.4.6 Smolyak formula for interpolation revisited

It is relatively straightforward to write a computer code that automates the construction of the Smolyak interpolant under our disjoint-set generators described in Section 1.4.3. We just have to sum up all the basis functions that appear in a table like Table 1.4 since no basis function is repeated by construction. Nonetheless, we were also able to derive a formula for Smolyak interpolation using disjoint sets, which is parallel to the conventional formula (1.5) using nested sets. We show such a formula below.

Smolyak polynomial: efficient construction

The formula for constructing a Smolyak polynomial function using unidimensional disjoint sets is as follows:

$$\widehat{f}^{d,\mu}(x_1, \dots, x_d; b) = \sum_{d \leq |i| \leq d+\mu} q^{|i|}(x_1, \dots, x_d); \quad (1.25)$$

for each $|i|$ satisfying $d \leq |i| \leq d + \mu$, a tensor-product operator $q^{|i|}(x_1, \dots, x_d)$ is defined as

$$q^{|i|}(x_1, \dots, x_d) = \sum_{i_1 + \dots + i_d = |i|} q^{i_1, \dots, i_d}(x_1, \dots, x_d), \quad (1.26)$$

⁶See Maliar et al. (2011) and Judd et al. (2011) for other precomputation techniques that reduce the computational expense of numerical solution methods, precomputation of intertemporal choice functions and precomputation of integrals, respectively.

and $q^{i_1, \dots, i_d}(x_1, \dots, x_d)$ is defined as

$$q^{i_1, \dots, i_d}(x_1, \dots, x_d) = \sum_{\ell_1=m(i_1-1)+1}^{m(i_1)} \dots \sum_{\ell_d=m(i_d-1)+1}^{m(i_d)} b_{\ell_1 \dots \ell_d} \psi_{\ell_1}(x_1) \dots \psi_{\ell_d}(x_d), \quad (1.27)$$

where $\psi_{\ell_1}(x_1), \dots, \psi_{\ell_d}(x_d)$ are unidimensional basis functions, in dimensions $1, \dots, d$, respectively; $\psi_{\ell_1}(x_1) \dots \psi_{\ell_d}(x_d)$ is a d -dimensional basis function; $\ell_d = 1, \dots, m(i_d)$; $b_{\ell_1 \dots \ell_d}$ is a coefficients vector. We use the convention that $m(0) = 0$ and $m(1) = 1$. By construction of (1.27), there are no repeated terms across different q^{i_1, \dots, i_d} 's.

Formula (1.25) sums up all the terms in Table 1.4 (recall that all the sets in Table 1.4 are disjoint and basis functions are never repeated by construction). The economization from our more efficient alternative Smolyak formula is described by (1.24) and is shown in Figure 1.2. To compute coefficients $b_{\ell_1 \dots \ell_d}$'s, we can use either the conventional closed-form expression (1.14) or a numerical solution using (1.20) to the Lagrange interpolation problem.

Example of Smolyak polynomial under $d = 2$ and $\mu = 1$ revisited

We now illustrate the construction of the Smolyak polynomial function (1.25) by revisiting an example with $d = 2$ and $\mu = 1$ studied in Section 1.3.3 (in Appendix B, we also show the construction of such a function with $d = 2$ and $\mu = 2$).

For the case of $\mu = 1$, we have $i_1 + i_2 \leq 3$. This restriction is satisfied in three cases: (a) $i_1 = i_2 = 1$; (b) $i_1 = 1, i_2 = 2$; (c) $i_1 = 2, i_2 = 1$. Thus, using (1.27), we obtain

$$(a) \quad q^{1,1} = \sum_{\ell_1=m(0)+1}^{m(1)} \sum_{\ell_2=m(0)+1}^{m(1)} b_{\ell_1 \ell_2} \psi_{\ell_1}(x) \psi_{\ell_2}(y) = b_{11}, \quad (1.28)$$

$$(b) \quad q^{1,2} = \sum_{\ell_1=m(0)+1}^{m(1)} \sum_{\ell_2=m(1)+1}^{m(2)} b_{\ell_1 \ell_2} \psi_{\ell_1}(x) \psi_{\ell_2}(y) = b_{12} \psi_2(y) + b_{13} \psi_3(y), \quad (1.29)$$

$$(c) \quad q^{2,1} = \sum_{\ell_1=m(1)+1}^{m(2)} \sum_{\ell_2=m(0)+1}^{m(1)} b_{\ell_1 \ell_2} \psi_{\ell_1}(x) \psi_{\ell_2}(y) = b_{21} \psi_2(x) + b_{31} \psi_3(x). \quad (1.30)$$

Collecting elements q^{i_1, i_2} with the same $i_1 + i_2 \equiv |i|$, we have

$$q^{|2|} \equiv q^{1,1}, \quad (1.31)$$

and

$$q^{|3|} \equiv q^{2,1} + q^{1,2}. \quad (1.32)$$

The Smolyak polynomial function (1.27) for the case of $\mu = 1$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}^{2,1}(x, y; b) &= \sum_{|i| \leq d+\mu} q^{|i|} = q^{1,1} + q^{2,1} + q^{1,2} \\ &= b_{11} + b_{21}\psi_2(x) + b_{31}\psi_3(x) + b_{12}\psi_2(y) + b_{13}\psi_3(y). \end{aligned} \quad (1.33)$$

This formula coincides with (1.13). Thus, we obtain the same Smolyak polynomial function as the one produced by the conventional Smolyak formula but we avoid forming lists of repeated basis functions.

1.5 Anisotropic Smolyak method

In economic applications, variables often enter asymmetrically in decision or value functions. For example, in a heterogeneous-agent economy studied in Kollmann et al. (2011), the individual choices depend more on her own variables than on variables of other agents; and the literature, based on Tauchen and Hussy's (1991) discretizations uses many grid points for endogenous state variables and few grid points for exogenous state variables.

However, the Smolyak method, studied in Sections 1.3 and 1.4, treats all dimensions equally in the sense that it uses the same number of grid points and basis functions for all variables. To increase the quality of approximation under such a method, we must equally increase the number of grid points and basis functions in all dimensions. This may be too costly to do in large-scale applications. An alternative is to increase the number of grid points and basis functions only in those dimensions that are most important for the overall quality of approximation. In this section, we show a variant of the Smolyak method that allows for a differential treatment of variables, specifically, it enables us to

separately choose accuracy levels for each dimension by taking into account a specific structure of decision functions in a given economic model. We refer to such a method as a *Smolyak method with anisotropic grid*.

1.5.1 Definition of anisotropy

The term *anisotropic* comes from mathematical literature and refers to functions that are "asymmetric" in some respect, for example, have more curvature in some variables than in others, or have a larger range in some variables than in others. Gerstner and Griebel (1998, 2003) propose dimension-adaptive grids for numerical integration of multivariate anisotropic functions; see also Bungartz and Griebel (2004), Garcke (2011) and Jakeman and Roberts (2011). In particular, the last paper develops a sparse grid technique for both integration and interpolation that combines local and dimension adaptivities. We introduce the Smolyak anisotropic constructions for interpolation in line with this literature.

As a starting point, consider a standard (isotropic) Smolyak grid with a level of approximation μ , as defined in Sections 1.3 and 1.4. Observe that for each dimension $j = 1, \dots, d$, index i_j varies from 1 to $\mu + 1$. For example, in Table 1.2, i_1 and i_2 vary from 1 to 3, and μ varies from 0 to 2, respectively (i.e. μ is equal to a maximum index minus 1).

For the anisotropic case, let us denote by μ_j an approximation level in dimension j . If in a dimension j , the maximum index admitted is i_j^{\max} , i.e. $i_j = 1, \dots, i_j^{\max}$, then $\mu_j = i_j^{\max} - 1$. A Smolyak grid is called *anisotropic* if there is at least one two-dimensional pair j, k such that $\mu_j \neq \mu_k$; otherwise, it is called *isotropic*. We denote an anisotropic Smolyak grid, Smolyak basis functions and Smolyak interpolant as $\mathcal{H}^{d,(\mu_1, \dots, \mu_d)}$, $\mathcal{P}^{d,(\mu_1, \dots, \mu_d)}$ and $\widehat{f}^{d,(\mu_1, \dots, \mu_d)}$, respectively.

1.5.2 Anisotropic Smolyak grid

Our design of an anisotropic variant of the Smolyak method parallels the design of the isotropic Smolyak method described in Sections 1.4. Namely, we first produce an anisotropic Smolyak grid, we then produce an anisotropic Smolyak

polynomial function, and we finally compute polynomial coefficients using Lagrange interpolation. Our anisotropic construction also builds on disjoint-set generators, which allow us to avoid costly repetitions of elements in the Smolyak interpolant.

Tensor products of unidimensional sets of points

The two-dimensional tensor products, constructed from the unidimensional sets up to $i = 4$ and $i = 2$ in the dimensions x and y , respectively, are summarized in Table 1.5. By construction, the table contains only non-repeated elements.

Table 1.5: Tensor products of unidimensional disjoint sets of grid points in the two-dimensional case

		$i_2 = 1$	$i_2 = 2$
$A_{i_1} A_{i_2}$		0	-1, 1
$i_1 = 1$	0	(0, 0)	(0, -1), (0, 1)
$i_1 = 2$	-1 1	(-1, 0) (1, 0)	(-1, -1), (-1, 1) (1, -1), (1, 1)
$i_1 = 3$	$\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}$ $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$	$\left(\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, 0\right)$ $\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, 0\right)$	$\left(\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, -1\right), \left(\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, 1\right)$ $\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, -1\right), \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, 1\right)$
$i_1 = 4$	$\frac{-\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}}{2}$ $\frac{-\sqrt{2-\sqrt{2}}}{2}$ $\frac{\sqrt{2-\sqrt{2}}}{2}$ $\frac{\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}}{2}$	$\left(\frac{-\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}}{2}, 0\right)$ $\left(\frac{-\sqrt{2-\sqrt{2}}}{2}, 0\right)$ $\left(\frac{\sqrt{2-\sqrt{2}}}{2}, 0\right)$ $\left(\frac{\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}}{2}, 0\right)$	$\left(\frac{-\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}}{2}, -1\right), \left(\frac{-\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}}{2}, 1\right)$ $\left(\frac{-\sqrt{2-\sqrt{2}}}{2}, -1\right), \left(\frac{-\sqrt{2-\sqrt{2}}}{2}, 1\right)$ $\left(\frac{\sqrt{2-\sqrt{2}}}{2}, -1\right), \left(\frac{\sqrt{2-\sqrt{2}}}{2}, 1\right)$ $\left(\frac{\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}}{2}, -1\right), \left(\frac{\sqrt{2+\sqrt{2}}}{2}, 1\right)$

Smolyak sets of multidimensional elements under anisotropic construction

The Smolyak rule tells us which tensor products must be selected. For the two-dimensional case, it is as follows: Select elements that belong to the cells in Table 1.5 for which the following conditions are satisfied

$$d \leq i_1 + i_2 \leq d + \mu^{\max}, \quad (1.34)$$

$$i_1 \leq \mu_1 + 1, i_2 \leq \mu_2 + 1, \quad (1.35)$$

where $\mu^{\max} \equiv \max\{\mu_1, \mu_2\}$ is a maximum level of approximation across the two dimensions, and the dimensionality is $d = 2$. In other words, the sum of indices of a column and a row, $i_1 + i_2$, must be between d and $d + \mu^{\max}$ subject to additional dimension-specific restrictions $i_1 \leq \mu_1 + 1, i_2 \leq \mu_2 + 1$.

Let us construct examples of Smolyak anisotropic grids using the anisotropic version of the Smolyak rule (1.34).

- If $(\mu_1, \mu_2) = (1, 0)$, then $\mu^{\max} = 1$ and the anisotropic Smolyak rule implies $2 \leq i_1 + i_2 \leq 3, i_1 \leq 2$ and $i_2 \leq 1$. The two cells that satisfy this restriction are (a) $i_1 = 1, i_2 = 1$; (b) $i_1 = 2, i_2 = 1$, and the corresponding three Smolyak grid points are

$$\mathcal{H}^{2,(1,0)} = \{(0, 0), (-1, 0), (1, 0)\}. \quad (1.36)$$

- If $(\mu_1, \mu_2) = (2, 1)$, then $\mu^{\max} = 2$ and $2 \leq i_1 + i_2 \leq 4, i_1 \leq 3$ and $i_2 \leq 2$. There are five cells that satisfy this restriction (a) $i_1 = 1, i_2 = 1$; (b) $i_1 = 1, i_2 = 2$; (c) $i_1 = 2, i_2 = 1$; (d) $i_1 = 3, i_2 = 1$; (e) $i_1 = 2, i_2 = 2$; and there are eleven Smolyak grid points

$$\mathcal{H}^{2,(2,1)} = \left\{ (-1, 1), (0, 1), (1, 1), (-1, 0), (0, 0), (1, 0), (-1, -1), (0, -1), (1, -1), \left(\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}, 0\right), \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, 0\right) \right\}. \quad (1.37)$$

- If $(\mu_1, \mu_2) = (3, 1)$, then $\mu^{\max} = 3$ and $2 \leq i_1 + i_2 \leq 5, i_1 \leq 4$ and $i_2 \leq 2$. There are seven cells in the table that satisfy this restriction, and $\mathcal{H}^{3,(3,1)}$ consists of nineteen grid points (see Table 1.5).

The three Smolyak anisotropic grids constructed in the above two-dimensional example are shown in Figure 1.4.

Figure 1.4: Examples of Smolyak anisotropic grids

We do not elaborate the construction of the anisotropic Smolyak polynomial function because such a construction trivially repeats the construction of grid points. Furthermore, to find the interpolation coefficients, we use the Lagrange interpolation approach described in Section 1.4.4, which applies to anisotropic construction without changes. Finally, we can adapt Smolyak interpolation formula (1.25) to the anisotropic case by imposing restrictions on i_1, \dots, i_d .

1.5.3 Advantages of anisotropic Smolyak method

The anisotropic class of methods involves the following trade-off: from one side, decreasing the number of grid points and basis functions reduces the computational expense but from the other side, it also reduces the quality of approximation. This trade-off suggests that anisotropic methods must be used when the former effect outweighs the latter. Using anisotropic methods in practice would require us either to have certain knowledge of the function that we want to interpolate or to do some experimentation. Namely, we can keep adding or removing grid points and basis functions in different dimensions until the target level of accuracy is attained. Maliar et al. (2014) construct error bounds for a variant of the Smolyak anisotropic method.

Let us compare the number of elements in an isotropic Smolyak grid $\mathcal{H}^{d,\mu}$

with the number of elements in an anisotropic Smolyak grid $\mathcal{H}^{d,(\mu_1,\dots,\mu_d)}$; we assume that $\mu = \max\{\mu_1, \dots, \mu_d\}$; and in both cases, we use the disjoint-set construction with no elements repeated:

$$R^{d,\mu} = \frac{\sum_{d \leq |i| \leq d+\mu} \prod_{j=1}^d m(i_j) \left(1 - \frac{m(i_j-1)}{m(i_j)}\right)}{\sum_{d \leq |i| \leq d+\mu, \{i_j \leq \mu_j+1\}_{j=1}^d} \prod_{j=1}^d m(i_j) \left(1 - \frac{m(i_j-1)}{m(i_j)}\right)}.$$

The above ratio depends on the specific assumption about the approximation level in each dimension (μ_1, \dots, μ_d) . Let us assume that the true function is completely flat in all dimensions except in dimension one. To accurately approximate such a function, we can use an anisotropic Smolyak method in which $\mu_1 = \mu$ in dimension 1 and $\mu_j = 1$ for all other dimensions, $j = 2, \dots, d$. In Figure 5, we show the corresponding ratio of the number of points under isotropic and anisotropic versions of the Smolyak method. Again, the "iso-function-count" curves show the number of the Smolyak elements.

Gains from anisotropic constructions may vary depending on the anisotropy of specific decision or value functions in economic models. In our example, the savings are sizable when d and μ are large. For example, when $d = 6$ and $\mu = 5$ for dimension 1, the number of grid points and basis functions is reduced by about 4 times compared to the isotropic grid.

1.6 Smolyak method with adaptive domain

The Smolyak construction tells us how to represent and interpolate functions defined on a normalized d -dimensional hypercube. However, the solution domain of a typical dynamic economic model does not have the shape of a hypercube but can be a set of any shape in a d -dimensional space. We now describe how to effectively adapt a multidimensional Smolyak hypercube to an unstructured solution domain of a given economic model.

Figure 1.5: The ratio of the number of basis functions under isotropic and anisotropic versions of the Smolyak method

1.6.1 Adaptive parallelotope

The ergodic set (i.e. the support of the ergodic distribution) of a dynamic economic model can have any shape in a d -dimensional space. It may be even an unbounded set such as \mathbb{R}_+^d . We must first construct a d -dimensional parallelotope to enclose the relevant area of the state space of the studied model, typically, a high-probability area of the ergodic set. We must then match the parallelotope to a normalized hypercube $[-1, 1]^d$ used by the Smolyak method.

As an example, in Figure 1.6, we plot a simulation of 10,000 observations for capital and productivity level in a representative-agent neoclassical stochastic growth model with a closed-form solution (see Section 1.7.1 for a detailed description of this model).

We show two possible rectangles in the figure that enclose the given set of simulated point: one is a conventional rectangle in the original coordinates, and the other is a rectangle obtained after a change of variables (both rectangles are minimized subject to including all the simulated points).

Our example shows that the way in which the rectangle is adapted to the state space of an economic model can matter a lot for the size of the resulting rectangle. How much the rectangle can be reduced by changing the system of coordinates will depend on the shape of the high-probability set. In particular, all rectangles will have the same size when simulated data are of the shape of a perfect sphere, however, the reduction in size can be fairly large if such the high-probability set is inclined (as is shown in the figure). The reduction in size can be especially large in problems with high dimensionality.

1.6.2 Smolyak grid on principal components

There are many ways to match a parallelotope into a normalized hypercube in the context of the Smolyak method. We propose an approach that relies on a principle component (PC) transformation and that is convenient to use in economic applications. Namely, we first use simulation to determine the high-probability area of the model's state space (for a sufficiently accurate initial

Figure 1.6: Two rectangular domains enclosing a set of simulated points.

guess), and we then build a parallelotope surrounding the cloud of simulated points. The PC approach was previously used by Judd et al. (2010) and Maliar and Maliar (2014b) in the context of simulation-based methods in order to define a distance between simulated points. In the present paper, the PC approach is used to re-orientate the parallelotope.

Let $X \equiv (x^1, \dots, x^\mathcal{L}) \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times \mathcal{L}}$ be a set of simulated data, i.e. we have T observations on \mathcal{L} variables. Let the variables $(x^1, \dots, x^\mathcal{L})$ be normalized to zero mean and unit variance. Consider the singular value decomposition of X , defined as $X = USV^\top$, where $U \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times \mathcal{L}}$ and $V \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{L} \times \mathcal{L}}$ are orthogonal matrices, and $S \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{L} \times \mathcal{L}}$ is a diagonal matrix with diagonal entries $s_1 \geq s_2 \geq \dots \geq s_\mathcal{L} \geq 0$, called *singular values* of X . Perform a linear transformation of X using the matrix of singular vectors V as follows: $Z \equiv XV$, where $Z = (z^1, \dots, z^\mathcal{L}) \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times \mathcal{L}}$. The variables $z^1, \dots, z^\mathcal{L}$ are called *principal components* of X , and are orthogonal (uncorrelated), $(z^{\ell'})^\top z^\ell = 0$ for any $\ell' \neq \ell$ and $(z^\ell)^\top z^\ell = s_\ell^2$. The sample variance of z^ℓ is s_ℓ^2/T , and, thus, z^1 and $z^\mathcal{L}$ have the largest and smallest sample variances, respectively.

In Figure 1.7, we illustrate the four steps of construction of the adaptive parallelotope using PCs.

In the upper-left panel, we show a set of simulated points; in the upper-right panel, we translate the origin to the center of the cloud, rotate the system of coordinates, renormalize the principal components to have a unit variance in both dimensions and surround it with a hypercube $[-1, 1]^2$. In the lower-left panel, we show thirteen Smolyak points with the approximation level $\mu = 2$ for the PCs of the data. Finally, in the lower-right panel, we plot the corresponding thirteen Smolyak points for the original data after computing an inverse PC transformation. In Appendix C, we provide additional details on how to construct the rectangular domain for this particular example.

Figure 1.7: Smolyak grid on PCs

1.6.3 Advantages and possible pitfalls of adaptive parallelotopes

The size of a parallelotope on which a function is approximated is translated into either higher quality or lower costs of the resulting approximation. For a fixed cost of approximation (i.e. for a given level of approximation), fitting a polynomial on a relevant domain gives us a better fit inside the relevant domain than fitting a polynomial on a large but partially irrelevant domain; this is because in the latter case we face a trade-off between the fit inside and outside the relevant domain. In turn, if we solve the model on a larger domain, we can attain the given quality of approximation in the relevant domain by computing a more expensive approximation (characterized by a higher approximation level).

However, the technique of an adaptive parallelotope has also a potential pitfall. Specifically, in addition to the size of the domain on which a function is approximated, the accuracy of the Smolyak method depends critically on the

relative importance of cross terms. In particular, a Smolyak method with the level of approximation $\mu = 1$ has no cross terms and cannot accurately approximate decision or value functions with non-negligible cross-variable interactions. In certain economic models, such interactions can be either absent or small in the original coordinates but may become important when we rotate the system of coordinates and as a result, the quality of approximation can decrease rather than increase. It is also possible to have the opposite effect, namely, the importance of cross terms can decrease after we rotate the system of coordinates. Some experimentation may help us to decide whether to use the adaptive parallelotope technique or not. Finally, we should point out that it is possible to combine an asymmetric treatment of variables with an adaptive parallelotope. This could be a potentially useful extension for some applications but we do not pursue it in the present paper.

1.7 Smolyak method for solving dynamic economic models

The Smolyak method for interpolation is just one specific ingredient of a method for solving dynamic economic models. We need to complement it with other ingredients, such as a procedure for approximation of integrals, a procedure that solves for fixed point coefficients, a procedure that updates the functions along iterations, a procedure that maps the state space of a given economic model into the Smolyak hypercube, etc. In this section, we incorporate the Smolyak method for interpolation into a projection methods for solving dynamic economic models. We assess the performance of the studied Smolyak-based solution method in the context of one- and multi-agent optimal growth models.

1.7.1 The representative agent model

Our first example is the standard representative agent neoclassical stochastic growth model:

$$\max_{\{c_t, k_{t+1}\}_{t=0}^{\infty}} E_0 \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \beta^t u(c_t) \quad (1.38)$$

$$\text{s.t. } c_t + k_{t+1} = (1 - \delta)k_t + \theta_t f(k_t), \quad (1.39)$$

$$\ln \theta_t = \rho \ln \theta_{t-1} + \sigma \varepsilon_t, \quad \varepsilon_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2), \quad (1.40)$$

where $c_t, k_{t+1} \geq 0$, and k_0 and θ_0 are given. Here, c_t and k_t are consumption and capital, respectively; $\beta \in (0, 1)$ is the discount factor; $u(c_t)$ is the utility function, which is assumed to be increasing and concave; $\delta \in (0, 1]$ is the depreciation rate of capital; $f(k_t, \theta_t)$ is the production function with $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ being the capital share in production; and E_t is the operator of expectation conditional on state (k_t, θ_t) . The productivity level θ_t in (1.40) follows a first-order autoregressive process with $\rho \in (-1, 1)$ and $\sigma > 0$.

1.7.2 Time iteration versus fixed-point iteration

Our implementation of the Smolyak method also differs from the one in Krueger and Kubler (2004) and Malin et al. (2011) in the technique that we use to iterate on decision functions. Specifically, they use time iteration that solves a system of non-linear equations using a numerical solver, whereas we use derivative-free fixed-point iteration that does so using only straightforward calculations. As an illustration, suppose we need to solve a non-linear equation $f(x) = x$; then time iteration finds $\min_x |f(x) - x|$ using a solver, while fixed-point iteration constructs a sequence like $x^{(i+1)} = f(x^{(i)})$, $i = 0, 1, \dots$, starting from some initial guess $x^{(0)}$ with the hope that this sequence will converge to a true solution. See Wright and Williams (1984), Miranda and Helmberger (1988), Marcet (1988) for early applications of fixed-point iteration to economic problems. Den Haan (1990) proposed a way to implement fixed-point iteration in models with multiple Euler equations; see also Marcet and Lorenzoni (1999) for related examples.

Gaspar and Judd (1997) pointed out that fixed-point iteration is a cheap alternative to time iteration in high-dimensional applications. Finally, Judd et al. (2010, 2011) and Maliar and Maliar (2014b) show a variant of fixed-point iteration, which performs particularly well in the context of the studied models; we adopt their variant in the present paper. Below, we illustrate the difference between time-iteration and fixed-point iteration methods using the model (1.38)–(1.40) as an example.

Time iteration

Time iteration solves a system of three equilibrium conditions with respect to \widehat{k}' in each point of the Smolyak grid. It parameterizes the capital decision function by Smolyak polynomial $\widehat{k}' = K(k, \theta; b)$, where b is the coefficients vector. It iterates on b by solving for current capital \widehat{k}' given the Smolyak interpolant for future capital $K(\widehat{k}', \theta'; b)$ (it mimics time iteration in dynamic programming where we solve for a current value function given a future value function):

$$u'(c) = \beta E \left[u'(c'_j) \left(1 - \delta + \theta'_j f'(\widehat{k}') \right) \right], \quad (1.41)$$

$$c = (1 - \delta)k + \theta f(k) - \widehat{k}', \quad (1.42)$$

$$c'_j = (1 - \delta)\widehat{k}' + \theta'_j f(\widehat{k}') - K(\widehat{k}', \theta'_j; b). \quad (1.43)$$

The system (1.41)–(1.43) must be solved with respect to \widehat{k}' using a numerical solver. Observe that Smolyak interpolation $K(\widehat{k}', \theta'_j; b)$ must be performed for each subiteration on \widehat{k}' using a numerical solver, which is expensive. Time iteration has a high cost even in a simple unidimensional problem.

Time iteration becomes far more expensive in more complex settings. For example, in the multi-agent version of the model, one needs to solve a system of N Euler equations with respect to N unknown capital stocks. A high cost of time iteration procedure accounts for a rapid increase in the cost of the Smolyak method of Malin et al. (2011) with the dimensionality of the problem.

Fixed-point iteration

We also parameterize the capital function using Smolyak polynomial $\widehat{k}' = K(k, \theta; b)$. Before performing any computation, we rewrite the Euler equation of the problem (1.38)–(1.40) in a way, which is convenient for implementing a fixed-point iteration:

$$k' = \beta E \left[\frac{u'(c')}{u'(c)} (1 - \delta + \theta' f'(k')) k' \right]. \quad (1.44)$$

In the true solution, k' on both sides of (1.44) takes the same values and thus, cancels out. In the fixed-point iterative process, k' on the two sides of (1.44) takes different values. To proceed, we substitute $k' = \widehat{K}(\cdot; b)$ in the right side of (1.44), and we get a different value in the left side of (1.44); we perform iterations until the two sides coincide.⁷

Using parameterization (1.44), we represent the system of equations (1.41)–(1.43) as follows:

$$k' = K(k, \theta; b) \text{ and } k''_j = K(k', \theta'; b); \quad (1.45)$$

$$c = (1 - \delta)k + \theta f(k) - k'; \quad (1.46)$$

$$c' = (1 - \delta)k' + \theta' f(k') - k''; \quad (1.47)$$

$$\widehat{k}' = \beta E \left[\frac{u'(c')}{u'(c)} (1 - \delta + \theta' f'(k')) k' \right]. \quad (1.48)$$

In each iteration, given b , we compute k', k'', c, c' , substitute them into (1.48), get \widehat{k}' and continue iterating until convergence is achieved.

In Appendix D, this approach is extended to a multi-agent version of the model to perform iterations on N Euler equations. Even in the multidimensional case, our fixed-point iterative procedure requires only trivial calculations and avoids the need of a numerical solver, unlike the time-iteration method.

Some theoretical arguments suggest that time iteration may possess better convergence properties than fixed-point iteration. In particular, for some simple models, it is possible to show that time iteration has a contraction mapping

⁷This kind of parameterization was used by Den Haan (1990) as a technique to implement the parameterized expectations algorithm in a model with several Euler equations.

property locally, which is similar to the one observed for value function iteration; see Judd (1998, p.553) for details. However, the local contraction mapping property is not preserved in more complicated models like the multi-agent model studied later in the paper. It is therefore unknown which iterative scheme has better convergence properties in general. Our simple fixed-point iteration method was reliable and stable in all experiments if appropriate damping was used.

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1.7.3 Algorithm

Below, we show a Smolyak-based projection algorithm for solving the model (1.38)–(1.40).

Smolyak-based projection method

Initialization.

- a. Choose the approximation level, μ .
 - b. Construct the Smolyak grid $\mathcal{H}^{2,\mu} = \{(x_n, y_n)\}_{n=1,\dots,M}$ on $[-1, 1]^2$.
 - c. Compute the Smolyak basis functions $\mathcal{P}^{2,\mu}$ in each grid point n .
The resulting $M \times M$ matrix is \mathcal{B} .
 - d. Fix $\Phi : (k, \theta) \rightarrow (x, y)$, where $(k, \theta) \in \mathbb{R}_+^2$ and $(x, y) \in [-1, 1]^2$.
Use Φ^{-1} to compute (k_n, θ_n) that corresponds to (x_n, y_n) in $\mathcal{H}^{2,\mu}$.
 - e. Choose integration nodes, ϵ_j , and weights, ω_j , $j = 1, \dots, J$.
 - f. Construct future productivities, $\theta'_{n,j} = \theta_n^p \exp(\epsilon_j)$ for all j ;
 - g. Choose an initial guess $b^{(1)}$.
-

Step 1. Computation of a solution for K .

- a. At iteration i , for $n = 1, \dots, M$, compute
 - $k'_n = \mathcal{B}_n b^{(i)}$, where \mathcal{B}_n is the n th row of \mathcal{B} .
 - $(x'_n, y'_{n,j})$ that corresponds to $(k'_n, \theta'_{n,j})$ using Φ .
 - Compute the Smolyak basis functions in each point $(x'_n, y'_{n,j})$
 - The resulting $M \times M \times J$ matrix is \mathcal{B}' .
 - $k''_{n,j} = \mathcal{B}'_{n,j} b^{(i)}$, where $\mathcal{B}'_{n,j}$ is the n th row of \mathcal{B}' in state j .
 - $c_n = (1 - \delta) k_n + \theta_n f(k_n) - k'_n$;
 - $c'_{n,j} = (1 - \delta) k'_n + \theta_n^p \exp(\epsilon_j) f(k'_n) - k''_{n,j}$ for all j ;
 - $\widehat{k}'_n \equiv \beta \sum_{j=1}^J \omega_j \cdot \left[\frac{u'(c'_{n,j})}{u'(c_n)} [1 - \delta + \theta_n^p \exp(\epsilon_j) f'(k'_n)] k'_n \right]$.
 - b. Find b that solves the system in Step 1a.
 - Compute \widehat{b} that solves $\widehat{k}' = \mathcal{B}\widehat{b}$, i.e. $\widehat{b} = \mathcal{B}^{-1}\widehat{k}'_n$.
 - Use damping to compute $b^{(i+1)} = (1 - \xi) b^{(i)} + \xi \widehat{b}$, where $\xi \in (0, 1]$.
 - Check for convergence: end Step 1 if $\frac{1}{M\xi} \sum_{n=1}^M \left| \frac{(k'_n)^{(i+1)} - (k'_n)^{(i)}}{(k'_n)^{(i)}} \right| < \varpi$.
-

Iterate on Step 1 until convergence.

1.7.4 Relation to other solution methods in the literature

We now describe the relation between the Smolyak solution method and other numerical methods for solving dynamic economic models in the literature; see Maliar and Maliar (2014a) for a survey of numerical methods for solving large-

scale dynamic economic models. First, the baseline version of the Smolyak method is similar to conventional projection methods in that it relies on a fixed grid, orthogonal polynomials and deterministic integration methods; see Judd (1992), Gaspar and Judd (1997), Christiano and Fisher (2000), and Aruoba et al. (2006), among others. The difference is that conventional projection methods build on tensor-product rules and their cost grows rapidly with the dimensionality of the problem, whereas the Smolyak method uses non-product rules and its cost grows far more slowly. Second, the anisotropic variant of the Smolyak method is similar to solution methods that use different number of grid points for different variables (e.g., few grid points for shocks and many grid points for capital as in Aiyagari (1994), Huggett (1993), Rios-Rull (1997), Krusell and Smith (1998)) and other numerical methods that rely on discretization of shocks in line with Tauchen and Hussy (1991). Third, the variant of the Smolyak method with an adaptive domain is related to simulation-based and learning methods; see, e.g., Marcet (1988), Marcet and Sargent (1989), Smith (1991, 1993), Rust (1997), Maliar and Maliar (2005) and Powell (2011). The advantage of simulation-based methods is that they focus on the relevant area of the state space; the shortcoming is that their accuracy is limited by a low rate of convergence of Monte Carlo integration. The Smolyak method with an adaptive domain does not rely on Monte Carlo integration: it uses simulations only for constructing the solution domain, and it uses projection techniques to accurately solve the model on this domain; in this respect, it is similar to combinations of projection and simulation methods studied in Judd (2010, 2011) and Maliar and Maliar (2014b). Fourth, in contrast to perturbation methods, the Smolyak method is a global solution method: its accuracy does not decline rapidly away from the steady state, and it can be used to accurately solve models with strong non-linearities. Fifth, in our examples, we focus on equilibrium problems, however, the techniques described in the paper can be also used in the context of dynamic programming problems. Winschel and Krätzig (2010) show how to use the conventional Smolyak method in the context of canonical value function iteration, however, the Smolyak method can be used in the con-

text of an endogenous grid method of Carroll (2005) and an envelope condition method of Maliar and Maliar (2013) both of which can significantly reduce the cost of conventional value function iteration. Finally, Brumm and Scheidegger (2013) parallelize a sparse grid method using piecewise local basis functions, and Valero et al. (2013) parallelize a Smolyak method using a global polynomial function. In particular, the latter paper parallelizes the Smolyak method on a desktop computer using multiple CPUs and GPUs and on Blacklight supercomputer; see Maliar (2013) for additional experiments assessing gains from parallelization on Blacklight.

Finally, the anisotropic-grid and adaptive-domain constructions, which we propose in the context of the Smolyak method, will also work for any projection solution method that operates on a hypercube domain including those based on tensor-product rules, e.g., Judd (1992). Also, these construction can be effectively used in the context of low-dimensional problems. However, there are many ways to increase accuracy in problems with low dimensionality, in particular, one can increase the degree of polynomial approximations. In high-dimensional applications, increasing the polynomial degree might be too costly. Anisotropic grid or adaptive domain or their combination may be the only feasible alternative. This is why we advocate these techniques in the context of the Smolyak method applied to problems with high dimensionality.

1.7.5 Implementation details

Our algorithm builds on techniques that are used in the related literature. To approximate expectation functions, we use a ten-node Gauss-Hermite quadrature rule. We find that for this particular class of examples, the choice of the number of integration nodes plays a very minor effect on the properties of the solution, for example, the results will be the same up to 6 digits of precision if instead of ten integration nodes we use just two. We could have used Monte Carlo integration but this would reduce the accuracy dramatically; see Judd et al. (2011) for a discussion.

We consider two mappings $\Phi : X \rightarrow [-1, 1]^2$ that transform each possible value of state variables $(k, \theta) \in X \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$ into a hypercube (which is a square in the two-dimensional case) $(x, y) \in [-1, 1]^2$. One is a conventional rectangular domain for capital and productivity, and the other is a rectangular domain constructed on principal components of simulated series. The rectangles are chosen to enclose the cloud of simulated data as shown in Figure 1.6. (That is, we solve the model two times: we first compute a solution starting from some initial guess about the ergodic range, we then simulate time series, and we finally recompute solutions more accurately using the rectangular domains that enclose the cloud of simulated data). In Appendix C, we provide further details on the construction of the two mappings.

We use extrema of Chebyshev polynomials as unidimensional grid points, and we use a Chebyshev polynomial family as unidimensional basis functions; in this respect, we are similar to Krueger and Kubler(2004) and Malin et al. (2011). We use the damping parameter $\xi = 0.05$, and we use the convergence criterion $\varpi = 10^{-7}$.

Finally, as a measure of accuracy, we report the mean and maximum of unit-free Euler equation errors on a stochastic simulation of 10,000 observations. Our computer code is written in MATLAB 2012a, and we use a desktop computer with Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-2600 CPU (3.40 GHz) with RAM 12GB. At the initial stage of this project, we benefited from consulting the Fortran code of Malin et al. (2011).

1.7.6 Results for the representative agent model

We parameterize the model (1.38)–(1.40) by $u(c) = \frac{c^{1-\gamma}-1}{1-\gamma}$, $f(k) = k^\alpha$ and $\ln \theta' = \rho \ln \theta + \sigma \varepsilon$, where the parameters are fixed at $\rho = 0.95$, $\beta = 0.99$ and $\alpha = 1/3$. We set the benchmark values of $\delta = 1$, $\gamma = 1$ and $\sigma = 0.01$, and we consider variations in γ , σ and δ one-by-one, holding the remaining parameters

Figure 1.8: Accuracy of the Smolyak method under different approximation levels.

at the benchmark values. Specifically, we consider

$$\delta = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0, 0.01, 0.02, 0.025, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05, 0.06, 0.07, 0.08, \\ 0.09, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1 \end{array} \right\},$$

$$\gamma = \{1, 5, 10, 15, 20\},$$

$$\sigma = \{0.001, 0.005, 0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05\}.$$

We use these parameterizations to test the performance of different versions of the Smolyak method introduced in the paper.

Conventional isotropic Smolyak grids under different approximation levels

We first solve the model (1.38)–(1.40) using a baseline version of the Smolyak method under four approximation levels $\mu = 1, 2, 3, 4$. Our baseline version is isotropic, i.e. has the same number of grid points for capital and productivity, and it operates on a rectangular domain in the original system of coordinates. The algorithm was able to converge in a wide range of the parameters and to produce highly accurate solutions.

Figure 1.9: Accuracy of the Smolyak method with anisotropic grid

In Figure 1.8, we report the (unit-free) maximum residuals in the Euler equation (1.44) (expressed in log10 units). The residuals vary from about 1 percent under $\mu = 1$ to 10^{-8} percent under $\mu = 4$. Therefore, the quality of approximation consistently increases with the value of μ .

Anisotropic Smolyak grids

We next consider anisotropic variants of the Smolyak method that use different numbers of grid points for different variables. We consider two possibilities $(\mu_1, \mu_2) = (3, 1)$ and $(\mu_1, \mu_2) = (1, 3)$. With these constructions, we have nine elements in the first dimension and three elements in the second dimension, which results in nineteen elements in total (i.e. nineteen grid points and nineteen basis functions); these are the elements distinguished in Section 1.5.2.

In Figure 1.9, we compare the maximum residuals in the Euler equation with anisotropic grids and isotropic grids. The medium line (the one with triangles) is our benchmark isotropic case $\mu = 2$ that contains 13 polynomial terms.

We observe that if we use more grid points in dimension of capital than in dimension of productivity, the anisotropic Smolyak method produces more accurate solutions than the benchmark isotropic Smolyak method, but if we

Figure 1.10: Accuracy of the Smolyak method with adaptive domain

have more grid points in productivity than in capital, the opposite is true. The difference in accuracy between two anisotropic solutions can be as large as two orders of magnitude. These results illustrate the potential usefulness of anisotropic grids in economic applications.

Adaptive domain

We next assess how the performance of the Smolyak method depends on the choice of the solution domain. We compare the accuracy of solutions of the Smolyak method that operates on the conventional hypercube with that of the Smolyak technique that operates on the adaptive rectangular domain. We compare the maximum residuals in the Euler equation under the conventional and adaptive domains in Figure 1.10.

The maximum residuals in the Euler equation are about a half order of magnitude (i.e. about 5 times) lower under the adaptive Smolyak domain than under the conventional Smolyak domain for the range of values for γ , σ and δ considered. We observe a visible improvement in the quality of approximation

due to an adaptive domain under both $\mu = 1$ and $\mu = 2$. In Section 3.5, we argued that there could be a potentially negative effect of cross term on accuracy after we rotate the system of coordinates. Our numerical results suggest that this effect does not play a significant role in our example except when γ becomes very large.

Computational expense

We finally assess savings due to our more efficient disjoint-set implementation of the Smolyak method (recall that we avoid forming lists with repeated basis functions when constructing the Smolyak interpolant). In the comparison analysis, we apply an isotropic variant of the Smolyak method to the model parameterized by $\delta = 1$, $\gamma = 1$ and $\sigma = 0.01$. To implement the conventional Smolyak method with a nested-set construction, we use software by Gordon (2011), which we find reliable and easy to use; see <https://sites.google.com/site/greygordon/code>.

In our experiments, we also study how the savings depend on a specific iterative scheme, namely, we compare time iteration in line with Malin et al. (2011) to our baseline fixed point iteration, see Sections 1.7.2 and 1.7.2, respectively. To solve for capital choices under time iteration, we use a solver "csolve.m" by Chris Sims. In Figure 1.11, we show the running time for four considered cases referred to as "FPI with disjoint sets", "FPI with nested sets", "TI with disjoint sets" and "TI with nested sets", where FPI and TI stand for fixed-point iteration and time iteration, respectively.

Two tendencies can be seen from the figure. First, the conventional nested-set implementation of the Smolyak method is always more expensive than our disjoint-set implementation. This is true under both time iteration and fixed-point iteration schemes. In the case of fixed point iteration, the savings increase with the level of approximation μ and can reach two orders of magnitude even in our simple two-dimensional example. For the time iteration scheme, the savings are more modest but still visible. Second, time iteration performs faster than fixed-point iteration in our example. This is because the cost of a numerical

Figure 1.11: Running time of the Smolyak method using fixed-point and time iteration with disjoint and nested sets

solver is relatively low for small problems like ours, while the convergence rate of time iteration is higher than that of fixed-point iteration. This finding is in line with the analysis of Gaspar and Judd (1997) and Malin et al. (2011) in which time iteration methods are very fast in small-scale models but their cost increases dramatically with the size of the problem. Fixed-point iteration will be a competitive alternative for larger problems as we will see in the next section, Section 1.7.7.

1.7.7 Results for the multicountry model

We now explore the performance of the Smolyak-based projection method in the context of problems with high dimensionality. To this purpose, we extend the one-agent model (1.38)–(1.40) to include multiple agents. This is a simple way to expand the size of the problem and to have a control over its dimensionality.

There are N agents, interpreted as countries, that differ in initial capital endowment and productivity level. The countries' productivity levels are affected by both country-specific and worldwide shocks. We study the social planner's problem. If agents are identical in preferences, the planner will allocate identical consumption to all agents. However, we do not make use of the symmetric structure of the economy, and we approximate the planner's solution in the form of N capital policy functions, each of which depends on $2N$ state variables (N capital stocks and N productivity levels). We solve for N policy functions $(k')^h = \mathcal{B}b^h$, where \mathcal{B} is a matrix of Smolyak basis functions evaluated in the Smolyak grid points, and b^h is a vector of the polynomial coefficients for $h = 1, \dots, N$. For each country, we use essentially the same computational procedure as the one used for the representative-agent model. The Gauss-Hermite quadrature method builds on product rules and is not tractable in problems with high dimensionality. We replace it with monomial rules combined with Cholesky decomposition; see Judd et al. (2011) for a detailed description of these techniques. For a description of the multicountry model and details of the computational procedure, see Appendix D.

Figure 1.12: Accuracy and running time for the multicountry model

In Figure 1.12, we compare four different solutions to the multicountry model, namely, the conventional solutions with $\mu = 2$ and $\mu = 3$, the anisotropic solution with $\mu_1^h = 3$ for the capital stocks and $\mu_2^h = 2$ for the productivity levels of all countries, $h = 1, \dots, N$ (in the figure, we denote this case as $(\mu_1, \mu_2) = (3, 2)$ which means $(\mu_1^1, \dots, \mu_1^N, \mu_2^1, \dots, \mu_2^N) = (3, \dots, 3, 2, \dots, 2)$). Finally, we report the solution with $\mu = 2$ for the Smolyak method with an adaptive domain.

We observe the following results from the figure. First, the difference between the isotropic solution with $\mu = 3$ and that with $\mu = 2$ is about two orders of magnitude. Second, by using an anisotropic grid, we can make half of the way between $\mu = 2$ and $\mu = 3$ in terms of the average residuals, and we obtain essentially identical maximum residuals. Third, the effect of an adaptive domain is also quite sizeable, namely, we can reduce the residuals up to one order of magnitude. Finally, we should draw attention to the computational expense of our solution method. We observe a clearly concave pattern for the running time in the logarithmic scale. This means that the expense grows slower than an exponential function, i.e. our implementation does not appear to be subject to the curse of dimensionality in the sense of Bellman (1961).

Malin et al. (2011) also solve models with up to 10 countries (20 state variables); in particular, a symmetric specification of Model I in their analysis is similar to the model studied in the present paper. For this model, their cost in seconds is 1, 59, 916, 7313, 38150 when the number of countries is 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, respectively, which grows faster than the exponential function. They use the approximation level $\mu = 2$, and their program is written in Fortran. We differ in two respects: first, we implement the Smolyak method for interpolation by avoiding the repetitions, and second, we use a much cheaper version of fixed-point iteration than time iteration used in Malin et al. (2011). We solve a similar model with 10 countries in about 45 minutes using MATLAB. However, the third-level Smolyak approximation is expensive even for our efficient implementation: we need almost 45 hours to solve a model with 10 countries, which increases accuracy by two orders of magnitude.

Thus, the adaptive domain allows us to make about 1/3 way in terms of accuracy between $\mu = 2$ and $\mu = 3$ without a visible increase in cost. The anisotropic grid with $(\mu_1, \mu_2) = (3, 2)$ gives us essentially the same accuracy as $\mu = 3$ but uses a considerably smaller number of grid points and basis function. However, our current implementation of the anisotropic Smolyak method does not allow us to translate a reduction in the number of Smolyak elements in a sizable cost reduction in this particular example. We first construct an isotropic Smolyak interpolant, and we next remove the terms accordingly to arrive to the target anisotropic construction. This procedure requires additional running time which reduces the savings from anisotropy.

1.8 Conclusion

The Smolyak method is designed to deal with high-dimensional applications. However, the cost of the Smolyak method still grows rapidly with dimensionality of the problem. In this paper, we propose a more efficient implementation of the Smolyak method that reduces its computational expense, and we present extensions of the Smolyak method that allow us to increase its accuracy level

while maintaining a fixed computational cost. The analytical and numerical techniques developed in the present paper are not limited to economic applications but can be used in other fields.

First, we propose a more efficient implementation of the Smolyak method than the conventional one, namely, we avoid unnecessary repeated evaluations of basis functions when forming a Smolyak interpolant. Efficient implementation of interpolation is especially important in the context of numerical methods for solving dynamic economic models in which decision or value functions must be interpolated a very large number of times during the solution procedure, i.e. in each grid point, integration node or time period.

Second, we propose an anisotropic version of the Smolyak grid which allows us to vary the number of grid points and basic functions by dimension. In a typical economic application, we know some properties of decision and value functions, and we may use this knowledge to represent such functions more efficiently using the proposed anisotropic constructions. Maliar et al. (2014) discuss further strategies for improving the performance of the anisotropic Smolyak method.

Third, we show an effective transformation of the state space of a given economic model into a normalized hypercube used by the Smolyak method. We find that the best accuracy of approximations is attained when we use a minimum hypercube that encloses the high-probability set of a given economic model.

The above three improvements are related to interpolation. Our last improvement is concerned with an iterative procedure for solving dynamic economic models. Time iteration used in the existing Smolyak methods relies on a numerical solver while a version of fixed-point iteration used in the present paper involves only a straightforward computation. This improvement, although minor in substance, allows us to achieve substantial economizing on cost, especially, in high-dimensional applications.

1.9 Appendices

This section contains some supplementary results. In Appendix A, we describe how to construct unidimensional Smolyak grid points and basis functions. In Appendix B, we develop the formula for the Smolyak interpolant in the two-dimensional example with $\mu = 2$. In Appendix C, we show an example of constructing adaptive domain. Finally, in Appendix D, we describe the multicontry model and the solution algorithm.

1.10 Appendix A: Unidimensional Smolyak grid points and basis functions

To construct multidimensional Smolyak grid points and basis functions, we must first specify unidimensional grid points and basis functions. Many choice are possible. For example, we can consider a family of ordinary polynomials, $\{1, x, x^2, \dots\}$ and grid points generated by dividing the interval $[-1, 1]$ into 2^{i-1} equal parts, $i \geq 2$ (for $i = 1$ we assume a grid point 0). In this manner, for $i = 2$, we have grid points $\{0, -1, 1\}$ and we have basis functions $\{1, x, x^2\}$; for $i = 3$, we have grid points $\{0, -1, 1, \frac{-1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}\}$, and we use basis functions $\{1, x, x^2, x^3, x^4\}$, etc.

Another possibility is to use Chebyshev polynomials as basis functions and extrema of such polynomials as grid points. Approximations based on Chebyshev polynomials have two useful properties. First, there always exists a unique set of coefficients such that a Chebyshev polynomial function matches M given values at M grid points. Second, approximations are uniformly accurate, and error bounds are established. We stick to this choice in our analysis.

Chebyshev polynomials are defined in the interval $[-1, 1]$ with a recursive relation: $T_0(x) = 1$, $T_1(x) = x$, and $T_n(x) = 2xT_{n-1}(x) - T_{n-2}(x)$ for $n \geq 2$.⁸ Chebyshev polynomial of degree $n - 1$ has n extrema. Let ζ_j^n be a j th extremum

⁸In terms of basis function ψ that was used in the main text and that is used later in Appendix B, we have $T_{n-1}(x) = \psi_n(x)$.

of Chebyshev polynomial of degree $n - 1$ with $j = 1, \dots, n$,

$$\zeta_j^n = -\cos\left(\frac{\pi(j-1)}{n-1}\right).$$

Table 1.6 presents Chebyshev polynomials of degree $n - 1$ and their n extrema (for the polynomial of degree 0, the extremum is assumed to be 0). Note that

Table 1.6: Extrema of Chebyshev polynomials and construction of Smolyak points in the unidimensional case

n	Chebyshev polynomial of degree $n - 1$ $T_{n-1}(x) = \cos\left((n-1)\cos^{-1}(x)\right)$	n extrema of the polynomial of degree $n - 1$ $\zeta_j^n = -\cos\left(\frac{\pi(j-1)}{n-1}\right), j = 1, \dots, n$
1	1	0
2	x	-1, 1
3	$2x^2 - 1$	0 -1 1
4	$4x^3 - 3x$	-1, 1, $-\frac{1}{2}$, $\frac{1}{2}$
5	$8x^4 - 8x^2 + 1$	0 -1 1 $-\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$ $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$

the sequence of unidimensional Chebyshev polynomials and their extrema cannot be used in Smolyak formula (1.5) because such sequence does not satisfy Conditions 1 and 2 of Section 1.3.5, namely, the number of extrema is equal to i , with $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, and not to $2^{i-1} + 1$ as required by Condition 1, and the consecutive sets are not nested as required by Condition 2. However, there is a subsequence of this sequence that satisfies both Conditions 1 and 2, and is suitable for the conventional interpolation formula. Namely, we select a subsequence in which the number of extrema is $m(i) = 1, 3, 5, 9, 17, \dots$ for $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$, respectively (the first three sets of such a sequence are in-boxed elements in the last column of the table).

Therefore, the unidimensional Smolyak basis functions and grid points are as follows: for $i = 1$, a grid point is $\{0\}$ and a basis function is $\{1\}$; for $i = 2$, grid points are $\{0, -1, 1\}$ and basis functions are $\{1, x, 2x^2 - 1\}$; for $i = 3$, grid points are $\left\{0, -1, 1, -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right\}$ and basis functions are $\{1, x, 2x^2 - 1, 4x^3 - 3x, 8x^4 - 8x^2 + 1\}$; etc.

1.11 Appendix B: Smolyak interpolant under $\mu = 2$

We compare two alternative formulas for Smolyak interpolation in the two-dimensional case under the approximation level $\mu = 2$. One is the conventional formula with repeated basis functions and the other is an alternative formula introduced in the present paper.

Conventional Smolyak interpolation formula. We consider the conventional Smolyak formula for interpolation in the two-dimensional case, $d = 2$, under the approximation level $\mu = 2$. Condition $\max(d, \mu + 1) \leq |i| \leq \mu + d$ in (1.5) becomes $2 \leq i_1 + i_2 \leq 4$. We use (1.7) to form p^{i_1, i_2} . In particular, $p^{1,1}$, $p^{1,2}$ and $p^{2,1}$ are given by (1.8)–(1.10), respectively. For the remaining polynomials, $p^{2,2}$, $p^{3,1}$ and $p^{1,3}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} p^{2,2} &= \sum_{\ell_1=1}^{m(2)} \sum_{\ell_2=1}^{m(2)} b_{\ell_1 \ell_2} \psi_{\ell_1}(x) \psi_{\ell_2}(y) = b_{11} + b_{21} \psi_2(x) + b_{31} \psi_3(x) \\ &\quad + b_{12} \psi_2(y) + b_{22} \psi_2(x) \psi_2(y) + b_{32} \psi_3(x) \psi_2(y) \\ &\quad + b_{13} \psi_3(y) + b_{23} \psi_2(x) \psi_3(y) + b_{33} \psi_3(x) \psi_3(y), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} p^{3,1} &= \sum_{\ell_1=1}^{m(3)} \sum_{\ell_2=1}^{m(1)} b_{\ell_1 \ell_2} \psi_{\ell_1}(x) \psi_{\ell_2}(y) \\ &= b_{11} + b_{21} \psi_2(x) + b_{31} \psi_3(x) + b_{41} \psi_4(x) + b_{51} \psi_5(x), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
p^{1,3} &= \sum_{\ell_1=1}^{m(1)} \sum_{\ell_2=1}^{m(3)} b_{\ell_1 \ell_2} \psi_{\ell_1}(x) \psi_{\ell_2}(y) \\
&= b_{11} + b_{12} \psi_2(y) + b_{13} \psi_3(y) + b_{14} \psi_4(y) + b_{15} \psi_5(y).
\end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, $p^{2|}$ and $p^{3|}$ are defined before in (1.11) and (1.12), respectively. A new combination of polynomials with $|i| = i_1 + i_2 = 4$ is given by

$$p^{4|} \equiv p^{2,2} + p^{3,1} + p^{1,3}.$$

Smolyak polynomial function (1.7) for the case $\mu = 2$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\widehat{f}^{2,2}(x, y; b) &= \sum_{\max(d, \mu+1) \leq |i| \leq d+\mu} (-1)^{d+\mu-|i|} \binom{d-1}{d+\mu-|i|} p^{|i|} \\
&= \sum_{3 \leq |i| \leq 4} (-1)^{4-|i|} \binom{1}{4-|i|} p^{|i|} = \sum_{3 \leq |i| \leq 4} (-1)^{4-|i|} \frac{1}{(4-|i|)!} p^{|i|} \\
&= -1 \cdot p^{3|} + 1 \cdot p^{4|} \\
&= -1 \cdot (p^{2,1} + p^{1,2}) + 1 \cdot (p^{2,2} + p^{3,1} + p^{1,3}) \\
&= b_{11} + b_{21} \psi_2(x) + b_{31} \psi_3(x) + b_{12} \psi_2(y) + b_{22} \psi_2(x) \psi_2(y) \\
&\quad + b_{32} \psi_3(x) \psi_2(y) + b_{13} \psi_3(y) + b_{23} \psi_2(x) \psi_3(y) + b_{33} \psi_3(x) \psi_3(y) \\
&\quad + b_{41} \psi_4(x) + b_{51} \psi_5(x) + b_{14} \psi_4(y) + b_{15} \psi_5(y).
\end{aligned}$$

As expected, the conventional Smolyak formula gives us the same thirteen basis functions as distinguished in (1.19).

Smolyak interpolation formula without repeated basis functions Let us now illustrate the use of interpolation formula (1.25) without repetitions. Here, we have $d \leq |i| \leq \mu + d$, which means $2 \leq i_1 + i_2 \leq 4$. We use formula (1.27) to form q^{i_1, i_2} . In particular, $q^{1,1}$, $q^{1,2}$ and $q^{2,1}$ are given by (1.28)–(1.30), respectively. For the remaining polynomials, $q^{2,2}$, $q^{3,1}$ and $q^{1,3}$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
q^{2,2} &= \sum_{\ell_1=m(1)+1}^{m(2)} \sum_{\ell_2=m(1)+1}^{m(2)} b_{\ell_1 \ell_2} \psi_{\ell_1}(x) \psi_{\ell_2}(y) = b_{22} \psi_2(x) \psi_2(y) + b_{32} \psi_3(x) \psi_2(y) \\
&\quad + b_{13} \psi_3(y) + b_{23} \psi_2(x) \psi_3(y) + b_{33} \psi_3(x) \psi_3(y),
\end{aligned}$$

$$q^{3,1} = \sum_{\ell_1=m(2)+1}^{m(3)} \sum_{\ell_2=m(0)+1}^{m(1)} b_{\ell_1\ell_2} \psi_{\ell_1}(x) \psi_{\ell_2}(y) = b_{41} \psi_4(x) + b_{51} \psi_5(x),$$

$$q^{1,3} = \sum_{\ell_1=m(0)+1}^{m(1)} \sum_{\ell_2=m(2)+1}^{m(3)} b_{\ell_1\ell_2} \psi_{\ell_1}(x) \psi_{\ell_2}(y) = b_{14} \psi_4(y) + b_{15} \psi_5(y).$$

Furthermore, $q^{2|}$ and $q^{3|}$ are defined before in (1.31) and (1.32), respectively.

A new sum with $|i| = i_1 + i_2 = 4$ is given by

$$q^{4|} \equiv q^{2,2} + q^{3,1} + q^{1,3}.$$

The Smolyak polynomial function (1.27) for the case of $\mu = 2$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{f}(x, y; b) &= \sum_{d \leq |i| \leq d+\mu} q^{|i|} = q^{2|} + q^{3|} + q^{4|} \\ &= b_{11} + b_{21} \psi_2(x) + b_{31} \psi_3(x) + b_{12} \psi_2(y) + b_{22} \psi_2(x) \psi_2(y) \\ &\quad + b_{32} \psi_3(x) \psi_2(y) + b_{13} \psi_3(y) + b_{23} \psi_2(x) \psi_3(y) + b_{33} \psi_3(x) \psi_3(y) \\ &\quad + b_{41} \psi_4(x) + b_{51} \psi_5(x) + b_{14} \psi_4(y) + b_{15} \psi_5(y). \end{aligned}$$

Again, as expected, our interpolation formula gives the same 13 basis functions as those distinguished in (1.19) for the conventional Smolyak interpolation formula.

1.12 Appendix C: Adaptive domain

We show how to adapt the Smolyak hypercube to the high-probability area of the state space in the context of the representative agent model (1.38)–(1.40). Our objective is to define a mapping Φ that transforms each possible value of state variables (k, θ) into $(x, y) \in [-1, 1]^2$. Below, we show two ways of constructing the mapping Φ , one uses the original coordinates and the other uses principal components of the original coordinates.

Standard hypercube. Consider a cloud of simulated data $\{k_t, \theta_t\}_{t=1, \dots, T}$ shown in Figure 1.6. Let us define $[\underline{k}, \bar{k}]$ and $[\underline{\theta}, \bar{\theta}]$ as intervals for the state variables that we observe in simulation (the rectangle $[\underline{k}, \bar{k}] \times [\underline{\theta}, \bar{\theta}]$ is the larger rectangle shown in Figure 1.6. Consider the following linear transformation of $(k, \theta) \in [\underline{k}, \bar{k}] \times [\underline{\theta}, \bar{\theta}]$ into $(x, y) \in [-1, 1]^2$

$$x = 2\frac{k - \underline{k}}{\bar{k} - \underline{k}} - 1 \text{ and } y = 2\frac{\theta - \underline{\theta}}{\bar{\theta} - \underline{\theta}} - 1. \quad (1.49)$$

By using (1.49) and its inverse, we can move from $[\underline{k}, \bar{k}] \times [\underline{\theta}, \bar{\theta}]$ to $[-1, 1]^2$. Malin et al. (2011) set bounds exogenously at $[\underline{k}, \bar{k}] = [0.8, 1.2]$ and $[\underline{\theta}, \bar{\theta}] = [\exp(\frac{-0.8\sigma}{1-\rho}), \exp(\frac{0.8\sigma}{1-\rho})]$, where the steady state of both capital and productivity level is one. Our own analysis shows that the best accuracy is attained if the intervals $[\underline{k}, \bar{k}]$ and $[\underline{\theta}, \bar{\theta}]$ are chosen to enclose the set of simulated data as shown in Figure 1.6.

Adaptive parallelotope. We now describe how to construct the adaptive (inclined) rectangle in Figure 1.6. To map the state variables into a unit square, we use a principal component (PC) transformation of the time series as described in Section 1.6 and illustrated in Figure 1.7. We first normalize the simulated data $\{k_t, \theta_t\}_{t=1, \dots, T}$ to have zero mean and unit variance by

$$\tilde{k}_t = \frac{k_t - \mu_k}{\sigma_k} \text{ and } \tilde{\theta}_t = \frac{\theta_t - \mu_\theta}{\sigma_\theta}, \quad (1.50)$$

where μ_k and μ_θ are means, and σ_k and σ_θ are standard deviations of capital and shock, respectively. We then compute the SVD decomposition $Y = USV^\top$,

where $Y \equiv \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{k}_1 & \tilde{\theta}_1 \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \tilde{k}_T & \tilde{\theta}_T \end{bmatrix}$, $U \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times 2}$ and $V \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$ are orthogonal matrices, and

$S \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$ is a diagonal matrix of singular values. We find $Z \equiv YV$, where $Z =$

$\begin{bmatrix} z_1^x & z_1^y \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ z_T^x & z_T^y \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times 2}$. Let $[z^x, \bar{z}^x]$ and $[z^y, \bar{z}^y]$ be the intervals for the resulting

principal components $\{z_t^x, z_t^y\}_{t=1, \dots, T}$. We map each $(z^x, z^y) \in [z^x, \bar{z}^x] \times [z^y, \bar{z}^y]$

into $(x, y) \in [-1, 1]^2$ using

$$x = 2 \frac{z^x - \underline{z}^x}{\bar{z}^x - \underline{z}^x} - 1 \text{ and } y = 2 \frac{z^y - \underline{z}^y}{\bar{z}^y - \underline{z}^y} - 1. \quad (1.51)$$

To go back to the state space of the model, we first find (z^x, z^y) that correspond to a given pair (x, y) using (1.51), we then apply an inverse PC transformation to get $(\tilde{k}, \tilde{\theta})^\top = V^{-1}(z^x, z^y)^\top$ and finally, we compute (k, θ) using the inverse of (1.50).

In our experiments, we typically recompute solutions two times: First, we solve the model using the standard rectangular domain in the original system of coordinates for some guess $[\underline{k}, \bar{k}] \times [\underline{\theta}, \bar{\theta}]$. After the decision functions were computed, we simulate the model and use the time series solution $\{k_t, \theta_t\}_{t=1, \dots, T}$ either to refine the guess on the bounds \underline{k} , \bar{k} , $\underline{\theta}$ and $\bar{\theta}$ for constructing the conventional domain or to compute $\mu_k, \mu_\theta, \sigma_k, \sigma_\theta, V, \underline{z}^x, \bar{z}^x, \underline{z}^y$ and \bar{z}^y for constructing the adaptive domain.

1.13 Appendix D: Smolyak-based projection methods for problems with high dimensionality

We describe the multicountry model studied in Section 1.7.7 and provide further computational details about the Smolyak method that was used to produce numerical solutions in that section.

Appendix D1. Multicountry model

We test the performance of the Smolyak-based projection method in the context of the multi-agent model studied in Judd (2010, 2011, 2012). This allows us to compare the performance of the Smolyak method with other approaches tractable in high-dimensional applications.

A world economy consists of a finite number of agents N , interpreted as countries. Each country $h \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ is populated by a representative con-

sumer. A social planner solves the following maximization problem:

$$\max_{\{c_t^h, k_{t+1}^h\}_{t=0, \dots, \infty}^{h=1, \dots, N}} E_0 \sum_{h=1}^N \lambda^h \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \beta^t u^h(c_t^h) \right] \quad (1.52)$$

subject to the aggregate resource constraint,

$$\sum_{h=1}^N c_t^h + \sum_{h=1}^N k_{t+1}^h = \sum_{h=1}^N k_t^h (1 - \delta) + \sum_{h=1}^N \theta_t^h A f^h(k_t^h), \quad (1.53)$$

and to the process for the countries' productivity levels,

$$\ln \theta_{t+1}^h = \rho \ln \theta_t^h + \epsilon_{t+1}^h, \quad h = 1, \dots, N, \quad (1.54)$$

where initial condition $\{k_0^h, \theta_0^h\}_{h=1, \dots, N}$ is exogenously given, and the productivity shocks follow a multivariate Normal distribution $(\epsilon_{t+1}^1, \dots, \epsilon_{t+1}^N)^\top \sim \mathcal{N}(0_N, \Sigma)$ with $0_N \in \mathbb{R}^N$ being a vector of zero means and $\Sigma \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ being a variance-covariance matrix. We assume that shocks of different countries are given by $\epsilon_{t+1}^h = \zeta_t^h + \varsigma_t$, $h = 1, \dots, N$, where $\zeta_t^h \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$ is a country-specific component, and $\varsigma_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$ is a worldwide component. The resulting variance

covariance matrix is $\Sigma = \begin{pmatrix} 2\sigma^2 & \dots & \sigma^2 \\ \dots & \ddots & \dots \\ \sigma^2 & \dots & 2\sigma^2 \end{pmatrix}$.

In the problem (1.52)–(1.54), E_t is the operator of conditional expectation; c_t^h , k_t^h , θ_t^h and λ^h are a country's h consumption, capital, productivity level and welfare weight, respectively; $\beta \in (0, 1)$ is the discount factor; $\delta \in (0, 1]$ is the depreciation rate; A is a normalizing constant in the production function; $\rho \in (-1, 1)$ is the autocorrelation coefficient. The utility and production functions, u^h and f^h , respectively, are strictly increasing, continuously differentiable and concave. We assume that all countries have identical preferences and technology, i.e. $u^h = u$ and $f^h = f$ for all h . Under these assumptions, the planner assigns equal weights, $\lambda^h = 1$, and therefore, equal consumption to all countries, $c_t^h = c_t$ for all $h = 1, \dots, N$.

Appendix D2. Algorithm for the multicountry model

The solution to the model (1.52)–(1.54) satisfies N Euler equations:

$$k_{t+1}^h = E_t \left\{ \beta \frac{u'(c_{t+1})}{u'(c_t)} [1 - \delta + \theta_{t+1}^h A f'(k_{t+1}^h)] k_{t+1}^h \right\}, \quad h = 1, \dots, N, \quad (1.55)$$

where u' and f' are the first derivatives of u and f , respectively.

We approximate the planner's solution as N capital policy functions $K^h \left(\{k_t^h, \theta_t^h\}^{h=1, \dots, N} \right)$. Note that our approximating functions $\widehat{K}^h \left(\{k_t^h, \theta_t^h\}^{h=1, \dots, N}; b^h \right)$, $h = 1, \dots, N$, are country-specific. In effect, we treat countries as completely heterogeneous even if they are identical in fundamentals and have identical optimal policy functions. This allows us to assess costs associated with computing solutions to models with heterogeneous preferences and technology.

Steps of the Smolyak-based projection method. The Smolyak method, described for the representative agent model in the main text, can be readily extended to the multicountry case.

- *Initialization:*
 - (a) Choose the level of approximation, μ .
 - (b) Parameterize $(k^h)' = K^h \left(\{k_t^h, \theta_t^h\}^{h=1, \dots, N} \right)$ with $\widehat{K}^h \left(\{k_t^h, \theta_t^h\}^{h=1, \dots, N}; b^h \right)$ which is a Smolyak interpolant constructed using Chebyshev unidimensional basis functions.
 - (c) Construct a Smolyak grid $\mathcal{H}^{2N, \mu} = \{x_n^h, y_n^h\}_{n=1, \dots, M}^{h=1, \dots, N}$ on the hypercube $[-1, 1]^{2N}$, as described in Section 1.4 and 1.5 for isotropic and anisotropic cases, respectively.
 - (d) Compute Smolyak basis functions $\mathcal{P}^{2N, \mu}$ in each grid point n as described in Section 1.4 for the isotropic case or in Section 1.5 for the anisotropic case. The resulting $M \times M$ matrix is \mathcal{B} .
 - (e) Choose the relevant ranges of values for $\{k_t^h, \theta_t^h\}^{h=1, \dots, N}$ on which a solution is computed. The resulting hypercube is $\left[\underline{k}^1, \bar{k}^1 \right] \times \dots \times \left[\underline{\theta}^N, \bar{\theta}^N \right]$.

- (f) Construct a mapping between points $\{k_n^h, \theta_n^h\}^{h=1, \dots, N}$ in the original hypercube $[\underline{k}^1, \bar{k}^1] \times \dots \times [\underline{\theta}^N, \bar{\theta}^N]$ and points $\{x_n^h, y_n^h\}^{h=1, \dots, N}$ in the normalized hypercube $[-1, 1]^{2N}$ using either a linear change of variables of type (1.49) or principal component transformation of type (1.51); see Section 1.6.

$$\Phi : [\underline{k}^1, \bar{k}^1] \times \dots \times [\underline{\theta}^N, \bar{\theta}^N] \rightarrow [-1, 1]^{2N}. \quad (1.56)$$

- (g) Choose integration nodes, $\{\epsilon_j^h\}^{h=1, \dots, N}$, and weights, ω_j , $j = 1, \dots, J$.
- (h) Construct next-period productivity, $\{(\theta_{n,j}^h)'\}^{h=1, \dots, N}$ with $(\theta_{n,j}^h)' = (\theta_n^h)^\rho \exp(\epsilon_j^h)$ for all j and n .
- (k) Make an initial guess on the coefficients vectors $(b^1)^{(1)}, \dots, (b^N)^{(1)}$.
- *Iterative cycle.* At iteration i , given $(b^1)^{(i)}, \dots, (b^N)^{(i)}$, perform the following steps.

- Step 1. *Computation of the capital choice.*

Compute $(k_n^h)' = \mathcal{B}_n (b^h)^{(i)}$, where \mathcal{B}_n is the n th row of \mathcal{B} for $n = 1, \dots, M$.

- Step 2. *Computation of the consumption choice.*

Compute $\{c_n^h\}^{h=1, \dots, N}$ satisfying (1.53) given $\{k_n^h, \theta_n^h, (k_n^h)'\}^{h=1, \dots, N}$ for $n = 1, \dots, M$.

- Step 3. *Approximation of conditional expectation.*

For $n = 1, \dots, M$,

- (a) compute:

– $\{(x_{n,j}^h)', (y_{n,j}^h)'\}^{h=1, \dots, N}$ that correspond to $\{(k_n^h)', (\theta_{n,j}^h)'\}^{h=1, \dots, N}$ using the inverse of transformation (1.56);

– Smolyak basis functions $\mathcal{P}^{2N, \mu}$ in each point $\{(x_{n,j}^h)', (y_{n,j}^h)'\}^{h=1, \dots, N}$; the resulting $M \times M \times J$ matrix is $\mathcal{B}'_{n,j}$;

– $(k_{n,j}^h)'' = \mathcal{B}'_{n,j} (b^h)^{(i)}$, where $\mathcal{B}'_{n,j}$ are basis functions evaluated in $\{(k_n^h)', (\theta_{n,j}^h)'\}^{h=1, \dots, N}$ using the transformation (1.56) for all j ;

– $\left\{ (c_{n,j}^h)' \right\}^{h=1,\dots,N}$ satisfying (1.53) given $\left\{ (k_n^h)', (\theta_{n,j}^h)', (k_{n,j}^h)'' \right\}^{h=1,\dots,N}$
for $n = 1, \dots, M$;

(b) evaluate conditional expectation:

$$e_n^h \equiv \beta \sum_{j=1}^J \left\{ \omega_j \left(\frac{u_1^h \left((c_{n,j}^h)' \right)}{u_1 \left(c_n^h \right)} \left[1 - \delta + (\theta_{n,j}^h)' f_1^h \left((k_n^h)' \right) \right] (k_n^h)' \right) \right\}.$$

- Step 4. *Computation of the coefficients.*

Find $\left\{ \widehat{b}^h \right\}^{h=1,\dots,N}$ that solves $e_n^h = \mathcal{B}_n \widehat{b}^h$, i.e. $\widehat{b}^h = \mathcal{B}_n^{-1} e_n^h$.

- Step 5. *Updating of the coefficients vectors.*

For each $h = 1, \dots, N$, compute the coefficients vector for the subsequent iteration $i + 1$ using fixed-point iteration,

$$(b^h)^{(i+1)} = (1 - \xi) (b^h)^{(i)} + \xi \widehat{b}^h. \quad (1.57)$$

where $\xi \in (0, 1)$ is a damping parameter.

Iterate on Steps 1–5 until convergence of the solution,

$$\frac{1}{MN\xi} \sum_{n=1}^M \sum_{h=1}^N \left| \frac{\left((k_n^h)' \right)^{(i+1)} - \left((k_n^h)' \right)^{(i)}}{\left((k_n^h)' \right)^{(i)}} \right| < \varpi, \quad (1.58)$$

where $\left((k_n^h)' \right)^{(i+1)}$ and $\left((k_n^h)' \right)^{(i)}$ are the h th country's capital choices on the grid obtained on iterations $i + 1$ and i , respectively, and $\vartheta > 0$.

Computational details. To solve the model, we assume $u(c_t) = \frac{c_t^{1-\gamma} - 1}{1-\gamma}$, $f(k_t) = k_t^\alpha$ with $\alpha = 0.36$, $\beta = 0.99$, $\rho = 0.95$ and we vary γ , δ and σ . We start iterations from an arbitrary initial guess on the capital decision function, $k_{t+1}^h = 0.9k_t^h + 0.1\theta_t^h$ for all $h = 1, \dots, N$ (this guess matches the steady-state level of capital). To approximate integrals, we use a monomial integration rule with $2N$ nodes combined with Cholesky decomposition; see Judd et al. (2011) for a description of these techniques. We set the damping parameter in (1.57) at $\xi = 0.05$, and we set the tolerance parameter in convergence criterion (1.58) at ϖ .

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Chapter 2

Synthetic Control Methods with Statistical Learning Techniques: a Comparison for Labor Market Reforms

2.1 Abstract

The effect of structural reforms is key when evaluating policies. The difficulty is that once the reform has been implemented it is not possible to observe the counterfactual, i.e. what would have happened if the reform had not occurred. By comparing the real series with the counterfactual we can determine the potential effect if any. The need of an evaluation is very important, yet in many cases not possible given the current methodologies. The current literature is dominated by the Synthetic Control (SC) methods. I enhance previous methodology by accounting for over fitting and different model selection procedures, in order to be able to choose the best methodology in each case. The main methodological

contribution is to include alternatives to the previous SC methods; with the main focus on LASSO with cross-validation.

The empirical contribution is to apply the previous methods to two labor market reforms: a) for a reduction of the workweek load, I study Portugal (1996); and b) for a reduction of firing cost, I study Spain (2010). The results show that there is a reduction of unemployment in Portugal, and for the Spanish case the result showed an increase in unemployment rate.

JEL classification : C18, E24, J08, J21, J22

Key Words : policy evaluation, synthetic control methods, labor, statistical learning

2.2 Introduction

The object of study of an economist cannot usually be implemented as a controlled experiment to gather data and test theories, in contrast with other disciplines. However by using statistics, in some cases, conclusions might be still found.

Imagine that a notable event occurs in a country, e.g. a hurricane or a change in law. Some important questions are: What would have happened if there had not been a change? Would there be any difference in a relevant variable? And if so, in what direction? How much? In other words, what is the real effect of a policy or other significant event. To answer this I use Counterfactual Series, i.e: artificial series that have not happened but would have if there had not been a change, one of the cutting edge methodologies is the Synthetic Control methods (hereafter SC), introduced by Abadie and Gardeazabal (2004) and developed by Abadie et al. (2010).

Synthetic Control methods is not the only technique for policy evaluation, see Athey, S. and G. W. Imbens (2017) and Gobillon and Magnac (2015). However,

SC presents an interesting framework when working with countries or regions. For example, working with regions or countries could be challenging when using matching techniques because there are hundreds of them. Yet, if the context is companies instead of countries you could have tens of thousands of companies. Therefore, it is easier to find similar companies than similar countries. In this sense SC could be a reliable way to evaluate policies at a regional and country level or cases where it is difficult to match the units to other units.

In this paper I present alternatives for creating synthetic or counterfactual series, i.e. the potential outcome in the absence of treatment of a treated unit, with a number of potential advantages with respect to the existing SC. The main purpose is to evaluate a policy by predicting a counterfactual series and comparing it with the real one: all else unchanged, any variation between the two series must be due to the policy implementation. Prediction of counterfactual series is well studied in Statistical Learning, which has tools to provide valuable results; I implement these tools for the purpose of this paper.

The closest papers regarding methodology are Gobillon and Magnac (2015) and Doudchenko and Imbens (2016). Both papers suggest and highlight examples when flexibilizing the restrictions of the coefficients of SC. Gobillon and Magnac (2015) show different alternatives to the original SC methods, one of those implementation, called “Interactive Effects Counterfactual” authors proposed flexibilize the restriction that affects the coefficients of the original SC methods. This is shared by Doudchenko and Imbens (2016) and this paper: we both proposed regularized regressions (or as known in the Statistical Learning literature Shrinkage Methods) in particular Doudchenko and Imbens (2016) elastic net and I LASSO. However, as further discussed later there are other techniques that could be quickly implemented for linear cases: Subset Selection, Ridge Regression, Principal Component Regression or Partial Least Square, among others, see chapter 3 Trevor Hastie and Friedman (2009). I select LASSO for its simplicity, still many coefficients are going to be zero as the original SC and it is broadly implemented in many software packages such as Matlab, Python and R. For further discussion see Section 2.3.3.

There are different techniques that can be suitable for modifying the original SC, in particular I study here LASSO with Cross-Validation, which is broadly implemented in software packages and well known in Statistical Learning. Also, in order to prevent overfitting and underfitting I implement a version of "Jack-knife model averaging" by Hansen and Racine (2012) to enhance the original SC.

This paper goes beyond Gobillon and Magnac (2015) and Doudchenko and Imbens (2016) by adding ways to select the best model for each particular case. This is something very common and well understood in the Statistical Learning literature, see chapter seven of Trevor Hastie and Friedman (2009). I will provide two ways to choose among the methods implemented in this paper in Section 2.7.6 and a simple approach in order to calculate the inference of the counterfactual or synthetic series in Section 2.7.5.

theoretical evidence (in general, in terms of minimization of squared errors, predictive ability and the cases where it is applicable), a simple approach in order to calculate the inference of the counterfactual or synthetic series in section 2.7.5 and empirical assessment for model selection in section 2.7.6.

The empirical contribution of this paper includes the employment of both techniques: the SC and LASSO with Cross-Validation in real cases. The cases are two different kinds of Labor Market reforms: a) a reduction of maximum work week hours, for example Portugal in 1996; and b) the reduction of firing cost, the example is Spain in 2010. In previous literature there is no strong evidence that these types of labor reforms were effective or have a macroeconomic impact; further literature on this kind of labor market reform is provided in Section 2.4. The results are that Portugal enjoyed a reduction of unemployment. For the Spanish case the law showed an apparent increase in unemployment.

The structure of this paper is as follows: in section 2.3, the methodology is described. In section 2.4 there is a literature review about the treated points and countries. Section 2.5 depicts the results and section 2.6 the conclusion. There are further appendices which complement and detail particular aspects,

such as data description, section 2.7.1; placebo tests, section 2.7.3; tests to verify the quality of the models, section 2.7.6; an explanation of the trade off between bias and variance and model selection, section 2.7.7; graphical examples of the modifications proposed for SC, section 2.7.4; and the coefficients for the particular cases, section 2.7.2.

2.3 Methodology

I suggest the utilization of prediction techniques borrowed from Statistical Learning to create counterfactual series and make them more robust. Statistical learning has a whole array of techniques with this aim. I illustrate this with the particular case of LASSO with Cross-Validation, the introduction of Cross-Validation in the basic SC method and the implementation of different procedures to select the best way. I will refer to this methodology as Synthetic Controls with Statistical Learning, SCSL

I am going to introduce some terminology and examples in order to illustrate the concepts and I try to write down the problems so the differences are understood and visualized in the constraints. Something identical can be seen in Doudchenko and Imbens (2016). From there I show that LASSO can potentially perform better than PSC.

2.3.1 Terminology, notation and examples

I am going to explain the notation and terminology. For SC I will follow Abadie and Gardeazabal (2004) and Abadie, Diamond and Hainmueller 2010, and for Statistical Learning Hastie et al. 2009. It is useful to keep in mind the next example, which will be studied in detail later. The aim is to create counterfactual series for unemployment in Portugal. Portugal implemented a law in December 1996, to reduce the maximum standard workweek to 40 hours, from, in some cases, 44. The law was implemented in two years and two steps. Unemployment

data is gathered for all OECD countries with available data and applied to one or more SC methods. The units are the countries of the OECD area, and the treated unit is Portugal; the control units will be the rest of the OECD units which do not have idiosyncratic changes. To create the counterfactual series the rest of the control units are used. Models are estimated before the treatment, and the estimates are used to create the counterfactual series after the treatment. By comparing the real series with the counterfactual series it is possible to draw some conclusions.

Units are the subject to study, some examples are regions, firms or cities; here the countries of the OECD. The units can be divided into a treated unit; the one which suffers the change of interest, and the control units¹; which are unaffected and similar to the treated unit. Control units are the selected ones, and after that, they are used to create a counterfactual/synthetic series.

The breakpoint or treatment is when the change happened, i.e. the initial date of a change: 1st of December of 1996.

In SC methods certain measures called predictors are also used, they covariate with the reference variable, which are supposed to help the selection of units. For example given that unemployment is the topic here, some predictors could be the average education of the work force, the average of the proportion of women, the unemployment age composition or unemployment duration. Following Abadie et al. (2010), $J + 1$ is the number of units, T the number of periods, T_0 the number of pre-treatment periods, R the number of covariates or predictors.

In this framework, it is useful to define the next vectors: $Y_1 \equiv$ vector of values of the interesting series of the treated unit, $1 \times T$. $Y_0 \equiv$ the same for the rest of the units, $J \times T$, $Z_1 \equiv$ vector of pre-treatment values of the interesting series of the treated unit, $J \times T_0$. $Z_0 \equiv$ the same for the rest of the units, $1 \times T_0$. $X_1 \equiv$ vector of pre-treatment values of R predictors for the treated unit, $J \times R$. $X_0 \equiv$ the same for the rest of the units, $1 \times R$.

¹In the proposed methodology control units does not necessarily have to be similar to the treated unit.

In Statistical Learning: the data set can be split into training, validation and test sets. The training set is the set where the model is fitted, the validation set is where the prediction error is obtained, the models selected and test set is where finally the selected model is assessed².

2.3.2 Original SC and Pseudo SC methods

In this section I explain briefly how to create counterfactual series by using SC methods; as developed in Abadie and Gardeazabal (2003) and Abadie, Diamond and Hainmueller 2010, and what is called here Pseudo SC methods. Original SC methods can be written as follows:

$$V = \arg \min_{V \in \mathcal{V}} (Z_1 - Z_0 W^*(V))' (Z_1 - Z_0 W^*(V)) \quad (2.1)$$

s.t.:

$$W = \arg \min_{W \in \omega} (X_1 - X_0 W)' V (X_1 - X_0 W) \quad (2.2)$$

2.3.2

s.t:

$$\sum_{i=2}^{J+1} w_i = 1 \quad (2.3)$$

$$0 \leq w_i \leq 1, i = 2, \dots, J + 1 \quad (2.4)$$

where \mathcal{V} is the set of all nonnegative diagonal matrices, $W^*(V)$ is the solution from 2.2 constraint to 2.3 and 2.4, and ω is a set of vectors such as $[w_2, w_3, \dots, w_{J+1}]$. See Abadie and Gardeazabal, (2003), Appendix B. In the same appendix, they also proposed an alternative way, it is referred here as pseudo SC for simplicity:

$$\min_W (Z_1 - Z_0 W)' (Z_1 - Z_0 W) \quad (2.5)$$

²Used here to compare among SC and SCSL

such that constraints 2.3 and 2.4 are met. The authors pointed out that pseudo SC (PSC) could be less appropriate since it does not consider more information about the units, i.e. X_0 and X_1 .

Lemma 1 *MSE of pre-treatment periods is equal or lower for PSC than SC.*

Proof: Because there is a constraint less for pseudo SC. □

After coefficients W are selected post-treatment data is used to create the counterfactual series: Y_0W . The real Y_1 and the counterfactual series Y_0W can be compared to draw conclusions.

In SC it is important not to extrapolate, as seen on page 494 of (Abadie et al., 2010): "Because the weights can be restricted to be positive and sum to one, the synthetic control method provides a safeguard against extrapolation". On page 117, footnote 9, of (Abadie, 2005), the notion of extrapolation is clarified: "The reason to restrict the weights in W to be nonnegative and sum to one is to prevent extrapolation outside the support of the growth predictors for the control regions." I diverge from this avoidance of extrapolation and let the coefficient be nonnegative. To illustrate this point a real case is shown in 2.5.3, where Spain is consistently the country with the highest unemployment; therefore in this example, creating synthetic series requires extrapolation.

2.3.3 Standard Statistical Learning Techniques

With previous ideas in mind, standard statistical techniques are introduced here, mostly following Statistical Learning. From all the possibilities,³ LASSO with CV is chosen in order to compare directly with PSC methods, given that both can be seen as a restricted LASSO case and both are broadly implemented techniques.

I borrow methodology from Statistical Learning: a) different techniques, in this case LASSO, b) the division of the original data in different sets: training,

³There is a large variety of techniques. Only for linear cases: Subset Selection, Ridge Regression, Principal Component Regression or Partial Least Square, at least.

validations and test sets⁴. c) hyperparameter selection, in this case Cross-Validation (CV). CV helps to select the tuning parameter in LASSO: t and d) model selection, for further discussion see Hastie et al. 2009. Model selection helps to decide which model is better, if SC or SCSL.

Here I propose two alternative ways: 1) The Random Points procedure and 2) The Windows procedure, which are applied and explained in Section 2.7.6.

LASSO In Tibshirani 1996 a procedure was created to combine the reduction of variables of Subset Selection (SS) and the smoothness of Ridge Regression: Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator LASSO. It is able to select units in a more continuous way than SS, is less computationally expensive, and broadly implemented in software packages.

With the previous notation, LASSO can be written as:

$$\min_W (Z_1 - c - Z_0 W)'(Z_1 - c - Z_0 W) \quad (2.6)$$

s.t.:

$$\sum_2^{J+1} |w_i| \leq t \quad (2.7)$$

where $t \geq 0$ is a tuning parameter which controls the amount of coefficient shrinkage and c is an intercept and does not account for the constraint 2.7. To provide some insight, consider the OLS estimation coefficients \hat{w}^{OLS} , suppose $t_0 = \sum_2^{J+1} |\hat{w}_i^{OLS}|$, then a $t = t_0 \alpha$, suppose there is a reduction ($0 \leq 1 - \alpha \leq 1$) of $\alpha\%$ on average of the OLS estimated coefficients.

Lemma 2 *MSE of pre-treatment periods is equal or lower to LASSO with $t \geq 1$ than for SC and PSC methods.*

⁴ The basic idea is to split the data into three groups; one for training, another for validation and another for testing. The group sizes may change throughout the literature. The training data is used to estimate the model, if there is need of a hyperparameter, such as λ in LASSO you can use validation. Once the models are estimated you can compare their performances in the test group.

Proof: Constraint 2.7 covers more cases than constraints 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4. \square

With respect to SC and PSC methods, LASSO allows for negative coefficients that may not have interpretation, as in SC methods. However LASSO combined with CV provide counterfactual series more robust to over or under-fitting (they are thought to predict).

LASSO versus Subset Selection (also called Best Subset in Doudchenko and Imbens (2016)): Subset Selection needs to run many regressions, it could be very expensive computationally. The algorithm must check every single combination and select the best. Furthermore, as pointed out in Trevor Hastie and Friedman (2009) Subset Selection tends to have high variance (the variables are either in the model or is discarded). In addition, the more variables you introduce there is the increase of multicollinearity which could make the problem computational intractable. There are different ways to ameliorate this for example, instead of performing the standard least squares algorithms another robust variations as explained in Judd et al. (2011). In many cases a good way to avoid all the previous problems are shrinkage methods. There are two methods which are very common: Ridge Regression and LASSO. I prefer LASSO in this context because the number of coefficients that will become zero is larger than with Ridge Regression. Elastic Nets is a linear combination between Ridge Regression and LASSO and therefore require the estimation of a hyperparameter for LASSO, another for Ridge Regression and the estimation of the best weight for LASSO and Ridge Regression. LASSO looks like a simpler alternative particularly to see clearly the regions where the coefficients are selected. See Section 3.4.3 in Trevor Hastie and Friedman (2009) for a discussion.

Summarising LASSO is a good option to predict counterfactual series. 1) It can be seen as generalization of the original SC or PSC, 2) it has been extensively used for other purposes, 3) some units may be ruled out, making both interpretations easier, and the worry of changes in these units reduced as with SC .

Hyperparameter λ selection

Model selection is based on the selection of a model accordingly, not only with its ability to minimize square errors or other criteria but also its ability to predict new data ⁵ There are different ways to do it, see Chapter 7 from Hastie et al. 2009 for a discussion. There are analytical approaches, such as Akaike information criterion (AIC); Bayesian information criterion (BIC); minimum description length (MDL) and structural risk minimization (SRM). There are also numerical approaches, such as Holdout method; Cross-Validation (CV); or Bootstrap. For a comparison among the last three see Kohavi (1995).

I focus on Cross-Validation, given its simplicity, broad uses and its implementations in software packages, acknowledging that there are others and there are also different CV procedures.

Cross Validation The easiest CV kind to understand is probably k-fold CV. The basic idea could be summarized briefly as follows, but it may change according to the software used:

1. Split the initial data set in a number of sets K .
2. For $i = 1, \dots, K$
 - Use the remaining $K - 1$ to estimate the model or models (training, these subsets form the training set).
 - Evaluate in the set i (called validation test) the previous estimation or estimations.
 - Select the best hyperparameter λ .

Alternatively Monte Carlo could be implemented by repeating 1 (with random splits) and 2 many times. There are more complicated versions, but this is

⁵Without overfitting or underfitting. Considering the Bias-variance trade off, for further details see 2.7.7.

fairly easy to explain; in software packages there may be a different kind, but the idea is roughly the same. The method is sensitive to the number K , given that it determines the size of the training sets. Usual K values are 5 or 10. For further discussion on CV see Arlot and Celisse (2010). Therefore when in LASSO t is chosen is for a reason, it is supposed to be the best option. A similar algorithm is implemented for SC and PSC to avoid the trade-off between bias and variance, as much as possible, but with limited success.

2.3.4 Selection Model

In Section 2.3.3 the hyperparameter λ as been selected once this parameter has been selecting SCSL is ready to be compared with PSC. The comparison will be carry out in the test set, which are not been used before for anything else (neither estimation or validation).

Here I propose two alternative ways: 1) The Random Points procedure and 2) The Windows procedure, which are applied and explained in Section 2.7.6. The idea is to estimate the model whitin the training and validation sets and check the performance in the test set.

2.3.5 Implementation and Robustness: Placebo test

In order to trust the final counterfactual series in line with the literature of SC methods, a placebo test is used. We need to check that the control units are not experiencing any idiosyncratic shock, otherwise the results would not be reliable. Keeping the breakpoint constant, each unit is analysed to be sure that the non-treated units are not suffering strong idiosyncratic shocks, which may affect the results. If the treated unit is the only one which changes in the breakpoint, the results are accepted. If there are units with idiosyncratic shocks, we can remove them from the set of control units and repeat the procedure. Details about the implementation can be found in Section 2.7.3.

2.3.6 PSC vs LASSO-CV: a summary and selection model

I have broadened SC methodology by introducing Statistical Learning. I compare between PSC and SCSL, in particular LASSO with CV; PSC summarizes previous literature and LASSO-CV summarizes the proposal of this paper.

Previously some shortcomings have been shown for SC and PSC. In previous sections advantages of SCSL are discussed (mainly that they have been designed for prediction and are broadly implemented). I also have to use other Statistical Learning techniques within the particular cases of PSC, although it seems that the introduction of a constant can be more helpful than including Cross-Validation. All in all, these modifications have limited impact, see Section 2.7.4 for a particular example.

The inclusion of LASSO can be seen as a generalization of previous SC methods. Statistical learning has different procedures to select different models and specifications, see Trevor Hastie and Friedman (2009) Chapter 7 for a review. The basic idea is to split the data into three groups; one for training, another for validation and another for testing. The group sizes may change throughout the literature. The training data is used to estimate the model, if there is need of a hyperparameter, such as λ in LASSO you can use validation. Once the models are estimated you can compare their performances in the test group. Here I propose two alternative ways: 1) The Random Points procedure and 2) The Windows procedure, which are applied and explained in Section 2.7.6.

2.4 Labor Economics Applications

Changes in labor laws are considered. Firstly, reduction of maximum standard workweek: Portugal (1996). Secondly, a decrease in firing costs: Spain (2010).

2.4.1 Short Literature Review

Reduction of maximum standard workweek

In labor economics there are many studies on the effect of different laws. The literature is vast and complex, given not only the different laws, but the different available data and the very different cases that should be faced. Conclusion at a microeconomic level are broad, for example it could affect married couples in a different way than single individuals (see Askenazy (2003), Rudolf and Seo-Young (2011)). If employees are highly qualified, they would go directly to extra hours (see Askenazy (2003)) and therefore earn more money; people who are already employees could look for a secondary part time jobs (see Askenazy (2003)); or if unions are very strong they claim full salaries and this may lead to maintaining the same salary, undermining possible job creation (see Hunt (1998), for Germany, Raposo and van Ours (2010), for Portugal, Sánchez (2010), for Chile), among other examples. In general, evidence of any sort of change is not found in the long term (see Jacobson and Ohlsson (2000) for Sweden, and Kapteyn et al. (2003) for OECD countries).

Reduction of firing cost

For the second empirical case in this study, Spain in 2010 where the law was oriented to reduce cost of firing. The reduction of firing cost has been generally advocated to make the labour market more flexible. There are models that theoretically support this idea such as Burda (1989). However, other models reduce the effectiveness of the reduction of firing cost on the grounds that the reduction of firing cost directly affects the ability of the firms to fire, but only indirectly the propensity to hire, as in Bentolila and Bertola (1990). There is no absolute consensus in the empirical literature, however restricting to research at a country level, and considering two labor sectors (there is a strong duality in the Spanish job market: temporary and fixed-term employees) it is possible to observe a positive effect. In Dolado et al. (2002) where the Spanish economy is

evaluated after the reform of 1997; there is preliminary evidence regarding the labor market composition: the final average job quality increased. Similarly in Kugler (1999), the Colombian Labour Market Reform of 1990 is studied and she distinguishes between informal and formal workers. There was an overall reduction in unemployment. Furthermore there was an increase of formal job respect to informal, highlighting an improvement in the general quality of the jobs.

2.5 Results

2.5.1 Implementation

Data comes from OCDE. All units are in percentages; for further description see Appendix A.

As pointed out in Abadie et al. (2014), all units should have similar characteristics, and units with similar treatment or with strong idiosyncratic shocks should be excluded if it happened after the breakpoint. Greece is removed given their particular situation since 2008. The breakpoints have been analysed by using placebo tests in Appendix C, in order to guarantee the breakpoints' existence and reliability of the counterfactual series.

A brief description of the law and previous works on the same changes is provided.

2.5.2 Portugal

On the first of December 1996, the maximum standard workweek in Portugal was reduced by law from 44 hours to 40 in two steps; firstly to 42 (those between 42 and 40, to 40), and then by 1997 all of them had changed to 40. As Raposo and Van Our (2010) point out, the main purpose of the law was not to create new jobs or reduce unemployment, but to converge to the European standards. By examining individual data, Raposo and Van Our (2010) found that for the workers involved, this change reduced the job separation rate and increased

hourly wages, keeping monthly earnings approximately constant. The working hour reduction also affected those working less than 40 hours per week; they were more likely to lose their job.

As seen in Figure 2.1, there is a reduction in unemployment with respect to SCSL. PSC does not pass the placebo tests⁶; this is another signal that the usage of PSC is not appropriate, in Appendix B the coefficients are displayed. According to Figure 2.1 SCSL is a good fit. It was apparent that the law started to have a macroeconomic effect promptly and some employment was created, roughly around a 1.57% of reduction in unemployment. The effect is significant at 5% according to bootstrapping simulations, see Section 2.7.5 for details in the creation. It is reported until 1999 because Portugal joined the Euro at this time, therefore it is possible that the "euro effect" started before 1999. A possible shortcoming here is that there is not too much pretreatment data.

Tests are computed in order to compare both methodologies. For the "Random Points procedure" a 10% of the pretreatment sample is always saved to evaluate the estimates; the same procedure is repeated 100 times, and a "Windows procedure" is computed too. In this test a random whole year is removed from the pretreatment sample to perform later evaluations; further details are in Appendix F. From Table 1 we can see that SCSL performs better⁷.

TABLE 1	Random Points procedure		Windows procedure	
	PSC	SCSL	PSC	SCSL
Average	0.5462	0.0585	1.4552	0.8912
Std	0.3739	0.0563	0.2079	0.4016

2.5.3 Spain

The Spanish law, Ley 35/2010, de 17 de Septiembre⁸, had three main goals according to its text: a) a reduction of duality⁹ in the job market, fostering the

⁶Different subsets of control units are used for robustness.

⁷This is not surprising since PSC does not pass the placebo test.

⁸Initially the reform was introduced by Real Decreto-ley 10/2010, de 16 de junio, with effectiveness on June 18th.

⁹The Spanish job market has two main groups in terms of job quality.

Figure 2.1: Portugal 1997 Results

creation of stable and quality jobs; b) increased flexibility as an alternative for firing; and c) increased opportunities for the unemployed. However some articles in the law can be understood as a reduction in the firing costs. This is because cases of dismissal are augmented, and their costs in some cases are reduced in two ways; by the amount of money to pay for the company and because the government pay a proportion of the previously reduced amount¹⁰. The period to consider is between September 2010 until January 2012 when another labor reform is introduced.

Evidently there is an increase in unemployment for the Spanish case of around 2.34%, and the difference between the counterfactual and real series is significant at 5%. Figure 2.2 shows a bootstrap exercise which plots the interval of confidence in order to test if they are significantly different (equivalent to Figure 2.1 is Figure 2.3). It is possible to notice that there is a good fit during the pretreatment periods, despite the sharp increase in unemployment for the financial and construction sector crises. The coefficients are in Appendix B with details, and the placebo tests are in Appendix C.

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¹⁰Excluding the so called "disciplinary dismissals".

Figure 2

From Table 2 it is possible to conclude that SCSL is doing better¹¹ than PSC.

TABLE 2	Random Points procedure		Windows procedure	
	PSC	SCSL	PSC	SCSL
Square Errors	474.5739	3.9732	323.2603	6.4840
Average	147.1721	1.4171	397.1007	6.9255
Std				

Graphs with implementation of variation of the SC methods are reported with an insignificant improvement, see Appendix C. The variations are: a) the inclusion of a constant term in PSC; and b) the use of Cross-Validation to calculate the PSC, as in Hansen and Racine (2012).

¹¹Not surprising since it is an example where PSC is not working.

Figure 2.2: Spain 2010-2012 Results

2.6 Conclusions

This paper contributes to the literature by enlarging SC methods. The main idea is the introduction of Statistical Learning techniques to create synthetic or counterfactual series given their properties for prediction. Their broad implementation is for statistical software packages.

I compare particular cases and show the effectiveness of the proposed methodology step by step. I find a reinforcement for the creation and evaluation of synthetic and counterfactual series and policy assessment.

For the empirical branch of the paper, it was found that unemployment decreased by an average of 1.6%, between 1997 and 1999, in Portugal by reducing the maximum standard workweek hours. In the Spanish case, the reductions of firing cost increased the unemployment around 2.4% on average between June 2010 and January 2012. In neither of these two cases could previous SC have been used, however the proposed methodology works.

Further research is needed with the intention of increasing the inference in the counterfactual series, the improvements of the placebo tests, and tests for model selection.

Other References and Codes

- Spanish labor reform of 2010: Ley 35/2010, de 17 de September, de medidas urgentes para la reforma del mercado de trabajo. BOEt núm. 227, de 18 de september de 2010, páginas 79278 a 79326 (49 págs.)
- I am very thankful to Hainmueller for the code for Abadie et al. (2010), the code it is implemented in Matlab, Stata and R, with useful documentation and data.

Software and Hardware

Code is written in MATLAB 2014a. The computer: Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-2600 CPU (3.40 GHz) with RAM 12 GB.

2.7 Appendices

2.7.1 Appendix A: Data description

- Unemployment: Harmonized unemployment rate, monthly, total, all persons, seasonally adjusted. OCDE.

Countries in the sample Australia (AUSL), Austria (AUS), Belgium (BEL), Canada (CAN), Czech Republic (CR), Denmark (DEN), Finland (FIN), Germany (GER), Ireland (IRE), Italy (ITA), Japan (JAP), Luxembourg (LUX), Mexico (MEX), Netherlands (NET), Norway (NOR), Portugal (POR), Spain (SPA), Sweden (SWE), United Kingdom (UK) and United States (USA).

2.7.2 Appendix B: Tables with coefficients

The further away t is from 1, the more different PSC and SCSL are. Note that even if $t=1$, the models could be different. Although the usage of PSC is not appropriate according to placebo tests results, see Section 2.7.3, I provide the coefficients and graphs.

Portugal

Country	AUSL	AUS	BEL	CAN	CR
PSC	0	0	0.2822	0	0
SCSL	-0.0768	-0.1788	0.7175	-0.1571	0.1089
	DEN	FIN	FRA	GER	IRE
PSC	0	0	0	0	X
SCSL	0.1820	0.0964	0.0944	-0.0630	X
	ITA	JAP	LUX	MEX	NET
PSC	0.1613	0.2392	X	X	0.3173
SCSL	-0.0410	0	X	X	0
	NOR	SPA	SWE	UK	USA
PSC	0	0	0	0	0
SCSL	0	0	0	0	0
	cte				
PSC	0				
SCSL	1.4372				
t	1.7159				

Figure 1 b

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Spain

Country	AUSL	AUS	BEL	CAN	CR
PSC	0	0	0	0	0
SCSL	-0.0626	0.1317	-0.2175	-0.1962	0.4890
	DEN	FIN	FRA	GER	IRE
PSC	0	1	0	0	X
SCSL	0.2758	-0.5556	1.2944	-0.4751	X
	ITA	JAP	LUX	MEX	NET
PSC	0	0	0	0	0
SCSL	0.7008	-0.0434	0.1172	-0.2558	0.1458
	NOR	POR	SWE	UK	USA
PSC	0	X	X	0	0
SCSL	1.4156	X	X	0	0
	cte				
PSC	0				
SCSL	-7.4662				
t	6.3765				

2.7.3 Appendix C: Placebo tests

Placebo tests are common in the SC literature, their implementation here is the same, however a new type is introduced, where only post-treatment square errors are reported; because SCSL usually fits quite well, the pretreatment periods seems better to focus on the post-treatment periods.

The results are portrayed by using gaps between real and counterfactual series. Histograms show the ratio between post and pre-treatment mean square error, therefore, the further to the right is the studied unit the largest is supposed to be the change.

The units with larger errors than the treated unit are removed from the pool, to guarantee they do not affect the counterfactual series. In some cases it is impossible to claim that the treated unit is the one which suffers the largest

shock, therefore it is not recommended use the methodology there. It is possible that by using PSC a unit cannot pass the placebo test, but using SCSL yes for the Portugal case.

The red star in the graphs points out the referred country positions. Portugal is not the country with the largest shock, in the Spanish case, it is the one with the largest shock.

USING PSC TO CALCULATE PLACEBO TEST

Portugal Portugal cannot be study with PSC methodology.

Spain According to the placebo test, Spain could be treated, but according to the gaps in the graphs it is evident that this may not be a good idea.

In other words, by using PSC placebo test the conclusion is that PSC should not be used for both Portugal and Spain.

USING LASSO TO CALCULATE THE PLACEBO TEST

The units with largest errors are removed from the pool.

Portugal It is possible to appreciate, from all three next graphs, that

Portugal is the country which has the largest change in the period.

Spain It is possible to appreciate that Spain is the country which has the largest change in the period.

2.7.4 Appendix D: SC with modifications

Here a case is depicted where PSC is not working. I provide graphical evidence of two modifications with the aim to make possible the use of PSC by adding

a constant, it alleviate the problem. Secondly CV is included to improve the coefficients obtained initially. The concrete algorithm is borrowed from Hansen and Racine (2012), the algorithm is known as "Jackknife model averaging", but no evidence improvement.

PSC Initial case. Only Finland is used.

With a Constant term Spain is composed by a linear combination of

Finland and Ireland.

With Cross-Validation Spain is composed by a linear combination of Finland and Ireland. In this case there is not a large difference in results. The methodology use is known as "Jackknife model averaging" adapted from Hansen and Racine(2012).

2.7.5 Appendix E: Inference

In this section I realize a simple bootstrapping exercise, where the bands around the fit are presented at a 5% significance. Therefore we can infer if there is or not effect.

Spain

The equivalent graph for Portugal is depicted in Figure 2.1.

2.7.6 Appendix F: Model Selection

Random Points Procedure

The schedule of Random Points procedure is as follows:

1. The pretreatment dataset is split in 10 randomly subsample.
2. One is reserved and not used for estimation. 9 subsamples are used for estimation.

Figure 2.3: Spain 2010-2012 results with inference

3. The reserved data is used for assessing the previous estimate.
4. The results are gathered.
5. Previous steps are repeated 100 times.

Here the graphical results are shown for Portugal and Spain.

Portugal The Portuguese case is in Figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4: Procedure comparing PSC and SCSL for Portugal

Spain The Spanish case is in Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.5: Test comparing PSC and SCSL for Spain

Windows Procedure

What I refer to as a "Windows procedure" consists of saving a set of data without been used for estimation, and the estimates are evaluated there. I do that 100 times. For Spain a random window of 12 months is taken each time. For Portugal, 6 months because of data availability. The results show that SCSL performs quite a lot better in these cases than these cases that we already known are not the best to illustrate these tests. The Portuguese case is in Figure 2.6.

Spain The Spanish case is in Figure 2.7.

Figure 2.6: Windows procedures comparing PSC and SCSL for Portugal

Figure 2.7: Windows procedures comparing PSC and SCSL for Spain

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A Placebo Test in time

Here a placebo test is provided, where the breakpoint has been changed to one that doesn't correspond to any known change. The result is that the counterfactual series is fairly close to the real one. Given that the original series has different breakpoints, an intermediate region has been selected. See Figure 2.8.

Figure 2.8: Placebo Test in Time Spain

2.7.7 Appendix G: The Bias-Variance trade-off and Model Selection

It is a well know problem in general. Here, standard notation is used. It can be

briefly summarized as follows: there are x_i points, with $i = 1, \dots, N$, they form the matrix X , for each of the previous values there is a y_i , they form the matrix Y . The data arises from the real but unknown model $Y = f(X) + \varepsilon$, there is a functional relationship $f(\cdot)$, unknown, and a noise ε , with $E(\varepsilon) = 0$ and $var(\varepsilon) = \sigma^2$. The objective is to approach $f(\cdot)$ by $\hat{f}(\cdot)$. After some derivation the expected prediction error is:

$$E \left[\left(y - \hat{f}(x) \right)^2 \right] = Bias[\hat{f}(x)]^2 + Var[\hat{f}(x)] + \sigma^2 \quad (2.8)$$

In expression 2.8 the Bias-Variance trade-off appears, the reduction of bias usually increases the variance and vice versa, both are usually affected by the complexity of the model. Therefore an equilibria should be found among the different models, i.e. Model Selection takes the best model. σ^2 is also known as irreducible error.

In other words, given a data set where a model is fitted, the corresponding Minimum Square Errors (MSE) on the data set are probably smaller than in the population or in another data set from the same source, i.e. with the same true functional relationship $f(\cdot)$ and the other data set checks with the same estimation, i.e. $\hat{f}(x)$, obtained initially. A common problem in these situations is overfitting..

Adapted for our case

$$\hat{f}(x, W, c) \equiv c + xW$$

For all dataset we have, in SCSL case:

$$E \left[\left(Y_1 - \hat{f}(Y_0, \hat{W}^{LASSO}, c) \right)^2 \right] = Bias[\hat{f}(Y_0, \hat{W}^{LASSO}, c)]^2 + Var[\hat{f}(Y_0, \hat{W}^{LASSO}, c)] + \sigma_{Y_1}^2$$

$$E \left[\left(Y_1 - c - Y_0 \hat{W}^{LASSO} \right)^2 \right] = Bias[c + Y_0 \hat{W}^{LASSO}]^2 + Var[c + Y_0 \hat{W}^{LASSO}] + \sigma_{Y_1}^2$$

In the SC or PSC:

$$E \left[\left(Y_1 - \hat{f}(Y_0, \hat{W}^{SC}, 0) \right)^2 \right] = Bias[\hat{f}(Y_0, \hat{W}^{SC}, 0)]^2 + Var[\hat{f}(Y_0, \hat{W}^{SC}, 0)] + \sigma_{Y_1}^2$$

$$E \left[\left(Y_1 - Y_0 \hat{W}^{SC} \right)^2 \right] = Bias[Y_0 \hat{W}^{SC}]^2 + Var[Y_0 \hat{W}^{SC}] + \sigma_{Y_1}^2$$

Chapter 3

Effects from the Implementation of Third European Road Safety Action Program using Synthetic Control Methods and Interactive Effects Counterfactual Approaches

3.1 Abstract

The effect of the Third European Road Safety Action Program (3ERSAP) is studied here, not only with respect to when it started to work but also regarding

what would have happened if it had not been implemented. This is a novel assessment of the 3ERSAP, and helps to distinguish effects coming from European collaboration and within each country. Three methods are compared: synthetic control methods (SC), synthetic control with statistical learning (SCSL) and interactive counterfactual effects (ICE).

The overall view is that the implementation of the road safety program at European level had larger effects than if the countries had continued their own paths. This paper provides quantitative estimates for each country. At European level it is possible to say that the 3ERSAP in the year 2010 helped to avoid between 13,900 and 19,400 fatalities. This finding supports the idea that the 3ERSAP in particular, and the EU or international collaboration in general, provide results that were previously inaccessible for individual countries.

Regarding the different methodologies, an easy way to compare them is provided. In this particular case SCSL tends to perform better than SC and ICE.

JEL classification: C21, C22, K32, R41

Keywords: Road safety policy, European Union, synthetic control methods, policy evaluation, linear factor models

3.2 Introduction

"Over 1.2 million people die each year on the roads, with millions more sustaining serious injuries and living with long-term adverse health consequences. Globally, road traffic crashes are a leading cause of death among young people, and the main cause of death among those aged 15-29 years" according to the "Global Status on Road Safety" report by the World Health Organization in 2015. Furthermore, there are estimated effects of 1.8 % of the GDP in Italy, 0.6 % in Spain or 2.5 % in 2010 as reported by IRTAD (2012b) ¹. However, car accidents can potentially be avoided. Most of the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) countries are already trying to address

¹In Euros: 27.7 billion in Italy. 6.7 billion in Spain. 7.1 billion in Austria.

the problem in one way or another. Policies are very broad: from making some car equipment compulsory to changes in speed limits, education, road improvement, new road signs or advertisements among others. Some of which can be ongoing simultaneously, making assessments challenging² ³.

At a legal level the implementation of the different laws or agreements for road safety within the European Union (EU) can be cumbersome given the difficulties in combining all the different institutions implied in one way or another ⁴ In order to homogenize the transport in the EU the Transport White paper appeared in 2001, the reference for this document is EC (2001); with the initial target of halving the number of road victims by 2010. A target that will appear in the third European Road Safety Action Program (3ERSAP) from 2003 until 2010, which is the main objective of study here. In 2010 the target was not met in all countries but the overall road fatalities decreased by 43% between 2001 and 2010, see TRT et al. (2009), IRTAD (2010), IRTAD (2012a) and IRTAD (2013) for a study of the results and information for each country. However the assessment provide here distinguished between the 3ERSAP effects and each country effects. The questions this paper answers are: was the Third European Safety Action Program (3ERSAP) useful? And how big was its impact?, or is the fight against fatalities better off with a coordination at European level than at country level?

I try to answer those questions by introducing novel methodology that explic-

²It is a challenge for every single possible variable to disentangle the affect the behaviour and security of drivers have on the road. For an example of complexity for young novice drivers and how many different scenarios can be considered see Engström et al. (2003).

³Consider also the example of the advertisement and how not only the money spent on advertising could potentially affect driver's behaviours but the type of advertisement, see Castillo-Manzano and Castro-Nuño (2012) for a discussion.

⁴For example, to be able to drive in a different country with a valid license from another country may look simple, but from the moment it was granted until it becomes perfectly functioning is complex. Although it is possible to drive abroad it took some time until it became possible to punish foreign offenders, as can be seen in MEMO/11/483, from July 2011, in which the addressed the problem.

itly allows for short term comparison, namely synthetic control (SC) methods, synthetic control methods with Statistical Learning (SCSL) and Interactive Effects Counterfactual (ICE) as described in Abadie et al. (2010), Gobillon and Magnac (2015) and Valero (2017) ⁵. The techniques used here try to build, in their own way, counterfactual series making possible the comparison between real and observed data and what would have happened if the law (in this case: if the countries were continuing to carry out their policies at a country level without European level coordination and support) had not changed. The difference is the effect of the law, accounting for the rest of the effects as constants. I find that the methodologies can be useful for the questions posed. There is not one which is better than the other in absolute terms, therefore I recommend testing which is better in each case.

The closest research, I have found, with both similar methodology and within Europe are Campos et al. (2014) and Fernández and Garcia-Perea (2015). In Campos et al. (2014) there is quantification of the variation on GDP per capita for joining the European Union in comparison with their counterfactual equivalent in case those countries were not join. Authors showed a positive effect of around 12%. In Fernández and Garcia-Perea (2015) the inclusion within the Euro Area are studied, in this case the results indicate an overall slight improvement that disappeared through time. The methodology implemented in both is SC, I also include SCSL and ICE here.

Focusing on Europe and the road safety there are two works similar to this one. In Castillo-Manzano et al. (2014b) it is possible to find details about the road safety laws and implementation within the EU until 2009. Authors thought panel data estimation described a positive effect or *Europeanization*, this is: there is negative correlation between the number of years belonging to the EU and the traffic fatalities. There are evidences of the convergence of most

⁵I compare these three methodologies in a practical exercise later, but there are compelling ways to understand some of them as a sub-category of others. I will discuss more in Section 3.4.

of the countries of the EU, as described in Castillo-Manzano et al. (2014a). In this area of study this paper improves the literature by quantifying the effect due to the European intervention (3ERSAP).

The empirical results are that there is an overall positive effect of the 3ERSAP. Most of the countries had a decrease in the number of fatalities larger than what they would have had on their own. SCSL performed better most of the cases.

The structure of this paper is as follows, in Section 3.4 the methodology is explained, in Section 3.3 there more details about 3ERSAP, in Section 3.5 the results are described and in Section 3.6 the conclusions are drawn.

3.3 Third European Road Safety Action Program

3ERSAP spanned between 2003 and 2010. The background of the members were relatively different in general, as were their road safety policies. The free transport of products within the EU is a corner stone of the EU. In order to improve the transport at all level in 2001 the Transport White paper, EC (2001), was delivered. This document had an overall vision of the whole European transport system at the time. In this document appeared, for the first time what later became the 3ERSAP target: to half the number of road victims by 2010. This objective was ratified by the European Parliament and the Transport Council in 2003. In the same year, on the second of June, the European Commission presented the 3ERSAP, (CE, 2003), EUR-Lex - 52003DC0311. In this document the main areas of action and mechanism for evaluation and collaboration within the EU were well defined. It is possible that a country has their own particular objectives within their national plan, and to find a annual survey of most of the European countries within the annual IRTAD reports. Therefore there are records of most of the countries particular targets, policies and evolution.

3ERSAP had different measures and wanted to make it easier to measure

the results and easier to compare with other countries at all levels. The final evaluation of the program is officially TRT et al. (2009) which also helps to create the next (Forth) European Road Safety Action Program.

The 3ERSAP had 15 members in 2003 the beginning and finished with 27 in 2010⁶. From the beginning of 3ERSAP were: Belgium, France, Italy, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Germany, Denmark, Ireland, United Kingdom, Greece, Portugal, Spain, Austria, Finland and Sweden. On the first of May 2004 Hungary, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Slovakia and Slovenia joined. On the first of January 2007 Bulgaria and Romania did it too.

3.4 Methodology

Three methodologies are implemented: synthetic control (SC) methods, synthetic controls with statistical learning (SCSL) and interactive effects counterfactual (IEC).

SC was introduced by Abadie and Gardeazabal (2003) and developed in Abadie et al. (2010). In Valero (2017) the previous methodology is revisited in order to introduce Statistical Learning, the basic difference is how to choose the coefficients of the control units accounting for the bias-variance trade-off. Interactive Effects (IFE) is explained in Gobillon and Magnac (2015) among other techniques and here I follow one of their implementations: "Interative Effects: Counterfactual" (IEC)⁷, because of its simplicity and flexibility to detect effects through periods of time.⁸

Each methodology relies on different ideas: SC relies on the selection of

⁶Corresponding to the number of countries of the EU

⁷also known as Generalized Synthetic Control (GSC) Method in (Xu, 2015).

⁸For SC, software is provided by authors in R, Stata and Matlab, for SCEL it is generally implemented in many coding languages, the author focuses on Matlab. IEC is provided by the authors in R, I also provide a detailed description of the algorithm in the Appendix 3.7.2 as they describe it.

very similar units, therefore when one of them changes the others can still replicate the behavior of the changed one, see Abadie et al. (2010). SCSL use Statistical Learning techniques to select the units that are going to be used. The statistical learning techniques, in this particular case, are LASSO, at the cost of the determination of a complexity parameter, one way to do so is to use Cross-Validation⁹. IEC decomposes the series in factors, takes a number of them, r , according to their importance, to predict the objective series. Therefore IEC needs to select the complexity parameter r , which could be determined in different ways. For example Xu (2015) uses Cross-Validation and Bai and Ng (2002) analytical procedures but there is vast research in order to determine r , or similar parameters, in the literature. With these characteristics in mind it is reasonable to perform tests in each particular scenario to identify which could be the most suitable method. I do that by following Test 1 like in Valero (2017) but there are more possibilities within Statistical Learning.

For IEC it is very simple to introduce more than one treated unit (with caution given that r may be different). For SC and SCSL it is not as straight forward; one possibility is to apply the methodology to each country individually. However it is important to keep in mind that even if these cases are easy to implement in IEC, they may affect the results equally, if not account for them fully. As mentioned before, SCSL and IEC both require the specification of complexity parameters.

3.5 Results

Section 3.5.1 is a description of the data, implementation details are in Section 3.5.2 and the results with detail in Section 3.5.3.

⁹as explained in Valero (2017) and broadly implemented in software packages, such as Matlab, Stata, Python or R.

3.5.1 Data

The data comes from the International Road Traffic and Accident Database, IRTAD, from the OCDE. The variable used is fatalities per million inhabitants of each country¹⁰. There is annual data for Australia, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, Croatia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Korea, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Moldavia, Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, United Kingdom and United States, between 1970 and 2014. Here it is used from 1991 forward, given that in many cases, such as Germany. For an example see the data from Estonia in Figure 3.7, appears a pick within 1989 neighbourhood.

3.5.2 Implementation

I use the same countries and period of time for all the methods. The countries used as controls are: Australia, Canada, Croatia, Georgia, Iceland, Japan, Korea, Moldavia, New Zealand, Switzerland, Turkey, and United States. The number of latent factors, r , is chosen by using the lowest of different methodologies, a) Cross-Validation as in Xu (2015) and b) as in Bai and Ng (2002)¹¹. SC is applied here without a preintervention outcome, as in Valero (2017) with the so called Pseudo Synthetic Control method, to make it more comparable with the other methods, however still I will label it here as SC for the sake of simplicity. SCSL is implemented here via LASSO and Cross-Validation; to select the complexity parameter for LASSO I use Cross-Validation. I select as a starting point 2001, although the 3ERSAP was formally created in 2003, the reason is that countries started the negotiation even before 2001 and it could affect their policy.

¹⁰This variable summarizes summarized very well the success of the policies. It does not vary with migration, the construction of new road or droved kilometers as some countries use as a target making it very changing and dependent on unrelated factors.

¹¹although this is not particularly thought for this use.

3.5.3 Results

Selecting between SC, SCSL and ICE

Figure 3.1: Austria

One example is tracked here with detail; Austria. Austria's data is shown in Figure 3.1 (a). The rest of the countries' graphs are in "Appendix: Graphical Results". The graph also shows the real and counterfactual series depending on the methodology and when the change happened (the vertical line). By using a procedure I select a particular methodology, see "Appendix: Model selection" for details. For the case of Austria see Table 3.2.

The idea behind the test is that there are three different methodologies and it is necessary to select the one which yields the best results. To do that I consider the pre-treatment data and split it in 3 different random folds. From these 3 folds I use 2 to estimate (training and validation) the model and 1 to measure the effectiveness by calculating the MSE. I repeat the process many times and with the different methodologies. I select the one which provides better results

according to this procedure. The results of the evaluations are in Table 3.2 ¹².

Confidence Intervals

Once the best model is selected it is necessary to know if the difference between the counterfactual and the real series is significant. Figure 3.1 (b) depicts the selected approach with the interval of confidence at 95% probability. In the Austria example the real series lies outside the interval of confidence of the counterfactual, meaning that they are different with a 95% probability.

Effects

The results of all the countries with data are presented in Table 3.1. The first column shows the real effect; this is the difference between the number of fatalities per million inhabitants in 2000 and 2010. The name of the column is 'Real'. The second and third columns illustrate the effect due to the country alone according to the selected methodology. The name of the columns are 'Counterfactual Min' and 'Counterfactual Max'. 'Counterfactual Min' represents the lower bound of the confidence interval at 95% probability and 'Counterfactual Max' represents the upper bound of the confidence interval at 95% probability. In other words, 'Counterfactual Min' represents the minimum effect due to the country alone and 'Counterfactual Max' the maximum. The last two columns show the difference between the real and counterfactual columns. This shows us the effect not due to the country's normal patterns: the treatment effect; the effect of 3ERSAP. The idea is that if the effect cannot be totally explained by the counterfactual, then the remaining effect must have been caused by the 3ERSAP, given that the 3ERSAP is the largest factor that can affect them at a country level.

Continuing with Austria, the first column 'Real' of Table 3.1 in 2010 saw a reduction of 53 fatalities in comparison to 2001. The meaning of columns 'Counterfactual Min' and 'Counterfactual Max' is the number of fatalities which

¹²Also I provide the same table using the whole period of time available Table 3.3

Country	Real	Counterfactual	Counterfactual	3ERSAP Effect	3ERSAP Effect
		Min	Max	Max	Min
Austria	-53.1000	-16.5175	-37.6676	-36.5825	-15.4324
Belgium	-67.5000	-21.2371	-44.0819	-46.2629	-23.4181
Bulgaria	-28.4000	28.0629	4.5994	-56.4629	-32.9994
Denmark	-34.4000	-3.8710	-12.2144	-30.5290	-22.1856
Estonia	-84.1000	-242.3243	-332.5719	158.2243	248.4719
Finland	-32.8000	-3.2053	-5.0627	-29.5947	-27.7373
France	-71.6000	-29.2573	-30.7190	-42.3427	-40.8810
Germany	-40.1000	-15.3870	-23.2009	-24.7130	-16.8991
Greece	-58.9000	43.5884	23.3535	-102.4884	-82.2535
Hungary	-47.6000	-40.3154	-55.8506	-7.2846	8.2506
Ireland	-59.8000	22.2000	2.8000	-82.0000	-62.6000
Italy	-55.1000	-10.1630	-18.2271	-44.9370	-36.8729
Latvia	-117.3000	127.8000	-5.4000	-245.1000	-111.9000
Lithuania	-106.9000	36.3268	-32.0739	-143.2268	-74.8261
Luxembourg	-95.4000	-31.6016	-70.6803	-63.7984	-24.7197
Netherlands	-29.0000	0.5079	-5.8345	-29.5079	-23.1655
Norway	-18.4000	5.7628	-4.7852	-24.1628	-13.6148
Poland	-42.0000	43.1897	16.6033	-85.1897	-58.6033
Portugal	-72.7000	-9.2908	-39.2520	-63.4092	-33.4480
Romania	-16.7000	-12.9392	-22.7261	-3.7608	6.0261
Slovenia	-72.2000	-8.7681	-34.3872	-63.4319	-37.8128
Spain	-82.2000	-6.4756	-19.5170	-75.7244	-62.6830
Sweden	-37.1000	-1.8571	-14.3247	-35.2429	-22.7753
United Kingdom	-30.5000	-6.7164	-9.2677	-23.7836	-21.2323

Table 3.1: Effects decomposition. The units are fatalities per million inhabitants.

can be attributed to the country alone. If the expectation was a reduction between 16 ('Counterfactual Min') to 37 ('Counterfactual Max') fatalities, then there are between 15 and 36 fatalities due to an extraordinary circumstance that cannot be explained by the previous effort or behaviour of Austria. The last one will be the meaning of columns '3ERSAP Effect Max' and '3ERSAP Effect Min'. If we assume that there is no other source of changes than the 3ERSAP then this is a proxy for the 3ERSAP effect in each country. For Austria the 3ERSAP helped to save between 15 and 36 fatalities in 2010.

In the large majority of countries the effect was positive in 2010, apart from in Romania and Hungary. Following Table 3.1, multiplying the last two columns by the population of each country in 2010, it is possible to estimate the total number of fatalities avoided in the European Union in 2010 thanks to the 3ERSAP: between 13,900 and 19,400. In "Appendix: Graphical Results" I show the rest of the graphs with some comments for each country. This finding supports the idea that the 3ERSAP in particular, and the EU in general, provide results that were previously inaccessible for individual countries. This finding is in line with previous literature which studies the effects of belonging to different European multicountry level institutions, see Campos et al. (2014), Castillo-Manzano et al. (2014a) and Castillo-Manzano et al. (2014b).

Discussion about mechanisms

It is difficult to quantify exactly the mechanism that made the 3ERSAP successful overall. There are at least four factors that could have had a positive influence: A) the technology of the cars, given that it appeared as an aim of the project, and it makes sense given that the EU is a market with a population of around 500 million inhabitants. B) the creation of European institutions makes it easier to track, measure and compare the effect of the policies between countries. C) A better regulation of heavy transport could make the road more secure in general. D) The EU guidelines promote the participation of different stakeholders within each country. The study of each of the previous factors are

very interesting and the weight of each of them in the process remains unknown.

3.6 Conclusion

The coordination at European level fostered by 3ERSAP has yielded very positive results. The effect of 3ERSAP just in the year 2010 helped to save between 13,900 and 19,400 lives: lives that could not have been saved by the standard pre-3ERSAP mechanisms, i.e. countries' policies alone.

This finding also supports the idea that international collaboration helps to achieve goals which were previously out of reach of the countries on their own. In this particular case the European Union offers new possibilities otherwise unavailable for their members.

Regarding the different methodologies, an easy way to compare them is provided. In this particular case, SCSL tends to perform better than SC and ICE.

Acknowledgements

I am thankful to Rebecca L. Gidman for helping to put the words together. I am thankful to Lilia Maliar, Sergei Maliar and Gabriel Pérez Quirós for guidance and advice. I am grateful for comments by the Economics Department of the University of Alicante and financial support from FPU grant from Ministerio de Educación de España. I acknowledge comments from Pedro Albarrán, M. Angeles Carnero, Juan Mora, Trino-Manuel Niguez, Anna Sanz-de-Galdeano and Francesco Serti. I am very thankful to Hainmueller for the code for Abadie et al. (2010), the code is implemented in Matlab, Stata and R, with useful documentation and data. I am very thankful for the code provided by Bai and Ng, in order to reproduce (Bai and Ng, 2002) and (Bai, 2009). I am very grateful for the code provided by Gobillon and Magnac which allowed me to reproduce their tables in (Gobillon and Magnac, 2015).

3.7 Appendices

3.7.1 Appendix A: Model selection

In order to select a methodology or model there are ways to proceed, i.e. here I select between SC, SCSL and IEC. The idea behind model selection is that the original data can be split into three samples: training, validation and test. In the training sample I estimate the model, in the validation sample we can select hyperparameters and in the test sample I check the model, namely, I collect the Minimum Square Error (MSE). This procedure is repeated many times with different subsamples for training and validation and I select the procedure that is performing better. See Hastie et al. (2009) Chapter 7 for model selection. A possible procedure presented here is created following Valero (2017).

1. The pretreatment dataset is split in 10 random subsample.
2. One is reserved and not used for estimation. 9 subsamples are used for estimation.
3. The reserved data is used for assessing the previous estimate.
4. The results are gathered.
5. Previous steps are repeated 100 times.

Now the implementations are presented:

Table 3.3 and 3.2 show the quality of each technique for each country. It is worth noting that in both of them the best performer is SCSL. However, if we compare both tables in Table 3.2 the average MSE of PSCM and IEC are generally lower than in Table 3.3 but for SCSL it is higher. Although I should carry out further analysis, a preliminary explanation could be that because of the reduced amount of data PSCM and IEC tend to overfit, and SCSL is the only one able to not overfit. Furthermore, given that the values do not vary largely between 1991 and 2001, the prediction provided by SCSL could be very close to the real values.

Country	PSCM	SCSL	IEC
Austria	672.8516	49.9442	905.8705
Belgium	1016.7752	96.4328	1063.4076
Bulgaria	365.3885	24.9208	331.7244
Denmark	267.1754	81.4481	274.8566
Estonia	786.4097	74.5357	1527.3937
Finland	375.8887	9.5709	779.3942
France	496.0311	14.8141	516.6491
Germany	206.9307	16.0817	639.3450
Greece	452.5167	15.1635	384.9974
Hungary	25.8500	22.9947	90.4573
Ireland	432.8669	29.8386	829.9228
Italy	273.4653	37.7710	989.7348
Latvia	191.5752	23.7611	516.2557
Lithuania	356.0446	25.7626	643.8630
Luxembourg	179.9113	8.2983	122.6469
Netherlands	328.2812	85.2358	183.9618
Norway	668.0415	54.6026	1267.5781
Poland	20.8294	4.5822	149.1722
Portugal	435.9936	23.0702	476.1649
Romania	249.4321	30.4851	295.8966
Slovenia	722.8240	54.2572	3051.8251
Spain	120.4970	34.6778	583.1715
Sweden	522.3973	6.3388	475.9046
United Kingdom	628.7318	32.0475	942.9635

Table 3.2: Average MSE of Tests Results, from 1991.

Country	PSCM	SCSL	IEC
Austria	390.0937	111.1100	278.1585
Belgium	333.8025	132.2507	192.0267
Bulgaria	365.3885	111.1955	230.0088
Denmark	401.9245	81.4481	274.8566
Estonia	311.7073	134.4901	269.6181
Finland	395.1161	128.9533	268.9100
France	355.4734	148.5134	259.3455
Germany	358.9410	107.2037	261.1106
Greece	232.8575	130.8027	128.6379
Hungary	386.9384	96.7191	277.0625
Ireland	306.9154	122.9463	202.0129
Italy	183.8511	133.0463	158.1646
Latvia	258.8718	122.7386	234.6319
Lithuania	266.7859	92.7233	336.8504
Luxembourg	351.5627	166.3138	312.0127
Netherlands	328.2812	85.2358	183.9618
Norway	413.4671	119.0103	293.4153
Poland	316.7277	120.1840	180.9688
Portugal	293.8257	107.0625	295.0649
Romania	340.3578	126.4816	188.6755
Slovenia	310.6930	144.3393	235.1552
Spain	316.3529	119.5048	201.0235
Sweden	335.3099	147.2768	259.0514
United Kingdom	362.7593	130.5770	258.8786

Table 3.3: Average MSE of Tests Results, from 1970 .

3.7.2 Appendix B: Interactive Effects

Alternative methodologies exploit the panel data structure of the generic problem, which properties are well known, see (Pesaran, 2006) and (Bai, 2009). As a factor model:

$$y_{it} = \lambda_i' f_t + x_{it} \beta + \epsilon_{it} \quad (3.1)$$

with $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ and $i = 1, \dots, N$. where x_{it} is a $p \times 1$ vector of observable regressors, β is a $p \times 1$ vector of unknowns coefficients, λ_i is $(r \times 1)$ is a vector of factor loading, and F_t is $(r \times 1)$.

- which dimension are $\frac{FF'}{T} = I$ and $\Lambda\Lambda'$ is diagonal.
- Note that: $\lambda_i' = (\hat{\lambda}_i, 1)'$ and $F_t = (1, \hat{F}_t)'$. Equivalent to have **Additive Effects**.
- Identification: $\frac{FF'}{T} = I$ and $\Lambda\Lambda'$ is diagonal.

Two Scenarios

Following the notation of Gobillon and Magnac (2015): there are at least two natural cases: a) IFE, treatment dummy and b) IEC counterfactual. IFE, treatment dummy will introduce a dummy for the treatment (i.e. $x_{it1} = 1$ if i is treated in period t , and $x_{it1} = 0$ if i is not treated in period t). However here I am interested in the evolution of the effect across time, therefore I do not use this approach. And b) it is carefully explained in the next subsection

Appendix: Interactive Effects Counterfactual Estimation

Here I provide a clear way to estimate Interactive Effects Counterfactual Algorithm:

- Step 1: Work with the untreated units. Obtain $\hat{\Lambda}^{Untreated}$, \hat{F} and $\hat{\beta}$.

$$Y^{Un} = \Lambda^{Tr} F + X^{Un} \beta + E_{it}$$

- Step 2: Work with the treated units in the pre-treatment periods. Obtain $\hat{\Lambda}^{Tr}$. *Until here*, GSC by (Xu, 2015).

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\Lambda}^{Treated} &= \underset{\hat{\Lambda}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left(Y^{Tr} - \hat{\Lambda}\hat{F} - X^{Tr}\hat{\beta} \right)' \left(Y^{Tr} - \hat{\Lambda}\hat{F} - X^{Tr}\hat{\beta} \right) \\ &= \left(\hat{F}\hat{F}' \right)^{-1} \hat{F} \left(Y^{Un} - X^{Tr}\hat{\beta} \right)\end{aligned}$$

- Step 3: Create Counterfactual for treated units: \hat{Y}^{Tr} .
- Step 4: Re-estimate using the real data of untreated units and the counterfactual of treated units obtaining: $\hat{\Lambda}$, \hat{F} and $\hat{\beta}$, for a more efficient solution.

Asymptotic Properties

As pointed out in (Gobillon and Magnac, 2015), there are various asymptotic properties:

- If N and T tend to $+\infty$, then $\hat{\Lambda}^{Un}$, \hat{F} and $\hat{\beta}$, for the untreated are consistently estimated see (Bai, 2009).
- If additionally the T_0 tend to $+\infty$, then $\hat{\Lambda}^{Tr}$ is consistent.
- If N, T and T_0 tend to $+\infty$, then $\hat{\Lambda}$, \hat{F} and $\hat{\beta}$ are consistent.

3.7.3 Appendix C: Graphical Results

Here are the graphics the results for the countries with are having effects.

Austria

[H]

Figure 3.2: Austria

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According to Figure 3.2 Austria benefited from 3ERSAP. According to IRTAD (2012a) Austria did not reach their target in 2010, i.e. 500 deaths was the target, Austria had 552. Their reference year was 2009. The key measures of the Austrian Road Safety Programme 2002-2010 were: the introduction of second-phase driver education; the demerit point system; alcohol screening; coaching for drunk drivers and seat belts campaigns.

Belgium

[H]

Figure 3.3: Belgium

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According to Figure 3.3 Belgium benefited from 3ERSAP. According to IRTAD (2013) Belgium did not reach their target in 2010, i.e. 750 deaths, in the whole country, was the target, Belgium had 840. As shown in IRTAD (2010) some of the measures included a reduction of maximum speed limit for heavy load trucks, new breath tests and analyses, creation of a Road Safety Task Force among others.

Bulgaria

[H]

Figure 3.4: Bulgaria

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Bulgaria joined the EU in 2007. According to Figure 3.4 Bulgaria benefited from 3ERSAP.

Denmark

[H]

Figure 3.5: Denmark

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According to Figure 3.5 Denmark benefited from 3ERSAP. According to IRTAD (2010) Denmark set up their goal for 2012: 300 deaths in the whole country, however they had to alter it down to 200, given they reached it in 2007. Their main focus were young drivers, drink driving, bicycle safety and speeding.

Estonia

[H]

Figure 3.6: Estonia

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Estonia does not appear to benefit from the 3ERSAP according to Figure 3.6. This is probably due to the strong reduction of fatalities per million inhabitants since 1999. If the years considered are extended we can appreciate that Estonia benefited, as depicted in Figure 3.7.

[H]

Figure 3.7: Estonia with data starting in 1970

Finland

[H]

Figure 3.8: Finland

According to Figure 3.8 Finland benefited. As it is possible to appreciate in Figure 3.8, from the year 1991 until 2001 the fatalities per million inhabitants was almost constant, and the 3ERSAP helped to break this tendency. Finland has their own very successful system, they set up their own target in shorter intervals (every four years) than most of the other 3ERSAP countries. They aimed for 250 deaths in 2010 in the whole country but unfortunately this was not reached, with 279 fatalities. They set this goal in 2006. Their target for 2025 is 100. For further detail see IRTAD (2010), IRTAD (2012a) and IRTAD (2013).

France

Figure 3.9: France

According to 3.9 the tendency of reduction of the fatalities was increased after the 3ERSAP. France has their own target, the closest one to this paper is 3000 fatalities in the whole country in 2012. It was established in 2007. They did not have a specific road safety programme. Their policy since 2007 has been oriented

towards having compulsory reflecting jacket and triangles in the car, as well as the reduction of alcohol intake when driving. the installation of interlock in the cars of driver has given positive BAC (blood alcohol concentration), mandatory for school buses and compulsory reflecting jacket and triangle. Particularly important were the implementation of graduated licensing system between 2007 and 2007 and the incrementation of seeped cameras in 2003. For further details see IRTAD (2010), IRTAD (2012a) and IRTAD (2013).

Germany

Figure 3.10: Germany

According to 3.10 the tendency of reduction of the fatalities was increased after the 3ERSAP. Germany did not have any explicit numerical target but is well recognised for their effort and their results have been named as one of the most important contributors for road safety in Europe, see IRTAD (2010). Particularly praised for their road network, their road policy vision of transport climate (e.g. aggressiveness) and technological importance.

Greece

[H]

Figure 3.11: Greece

It is possible to validate 3.11 by comparing with a longer period of time as in Figure 3.12. Therefore the 3ERSAP helped to reduce the fatalities, however it is necessary to point out that Greece started a few years earlier to modernize their road security plan, therefore the effect of 3ERSAP could be combined. Greece had two road safety strategic plans in the considered period. a) Between 2001-2005: with the aim of reduction of a 20% the fatalities. It was almost achieved: 19%. b) Between 2006-2010, it aimed to achieve the 50% European target however they achieve a reduction of 37% at a national level. During this period of time were implemented the first basic measures in Greece in order to face the road safety issue. Still there is a lag of policies to be implemented, such as lack of coordination and monitoring, see IRTAD (2010) and IRTAD (2013).

[H]

(a) Comparison

(b) With Interval of Confidence

Figure 3.12: Greece with break in 2001, starting in 1970

Hungary

[H]

(a) Comparison

(b) With Interval of Confidence

Figure 3.13: Hungary

According to Figure 3.13 Hungary did not benefited from 3ERSAP in 2010. In 2002 in terms of fatalities, Hungary established a reduction of 30% by 2010 and 50% by 2015, taking as a reference 2001. The main policies were child seat obligation (2002), stricter demerit point system (2008) and higher technical requirements for child restraints (2009). Hungary reached its goal for 2010 and almost the equivalent for the proposal in 3ERSAP.

Ireland

Figure 3.14: Ireland

According to Figure 3.14 Ireland benefited from 3ERSAP. Ireland had a Road Safety Strategy 2007-2012. In terms of fatalities the main target was to reduce to 60 fatalities per million inhabitant by 2012. They reached it in 2010. Between 2000 and 2010 they reach almost a 50% reduction of fatalities. Their policy went from education in schools, enforcement, engineering and evaluation of their initiatives, see IRTAD (2012a).

Italy

[H]

Figure 3.15: Italy

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According to Figure 3.15 Italy benefited from 3ERSAP. Italy almost reached its 50% reduction target. Italy invested more than 920 million Euros and implemented more than 1600 local projects, as can be seen in IRTAD (2013).

Latvia

[H]

Figure 3.16: Latvia

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According to Figure 3.16 Latvia benefited from 3ERSAP. Latvia reached the 50% reduction target.

Lithuania

[H]

Figure 3.17: Lithuania

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According to IRTAD (2012a), Lithuania reached their goal, in line with 3ERSAP.

Luxembourg

[H]

Figure 3.18: Luxembourg

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According to Figure 3.18 Luxembourg benefited from 3ERSAP. Luxembourg did not reach the 50% reduction target, but shaved a decrease of around 34%.

Netherlands

[H]

Figure 3.19: Netherlands

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According to Figure 3.19 Netherlands benefited from 3ERSAP. The Netherlands did not follow the generic target of a 50% reduction. They had their own target for 2010 of 750 traffic fatalities. The target was reached by 2007. In 2008 they placed a new target of 500 for 2020, for further details see IRTAD (2010).

Norway

[H]

Figure 3.20: Norway

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According to Figure 3.20 Norway benefited from 3ERSAP. Norway did not have a particular target in terms of fatalities. They adopted a "Vision Zero" goal in their National Plan of Action for Traffic Safety 2002-2011. The "Vision Zero" involves the entire transport policy, however they made their priority the reduction of head-on crashes and collisions with pedestrians. They established a new goal for 2020, equivalent to the 33% with 2010 as a base year, i.e. 775. for more details see IRTAD (2012a).

Poland

[H]

Figure 3.21: Poland

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According to Figure 3.21 Poland benefited from 3ERSAP. Poland has a National Road Safety Program for 2005-2017, called GARMBIT 2005. It is a "Vision Zero" plan with the particular target of a reduction of 50% fatalities in 2013 with respect to 2003, i.e. 2800. See IRTAD (2012a) for further details. This target was not reached as shown in ITF (2015).

Portugal

[H]

Figure 3.22: Portugal

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According to Figure 3.22 Portugal benefited from 3ERSAP. Portugal also has similar but not exactly the same goals as in 3ERSAP, for more detail of Portugal goal see IRTAD (2010). In particular taking as base year 1998-2000 they had 1748 fatalities and they wanted to reduce them by 50%. In 2008 they reached their target with 776 (-55%).

Romania

[H]

Figure 3.23: Romania

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Romania joined the EU in 2007. In Figures 3.23 and 3.23 it is possible to see results from 2001 and 2007. There is no evidence that in 2001 the 3ERSAP had started affecting Romania.

[H]

(a) Comparison

(b) With Interval of Confidence

Figure 3.24: Romania

Slovenia

[H]

(a) Comparison

(b) With Interval of Confidence

Figure 3.25: Slovenia

According to Figure 3.25 Slovenia benefited from 3ERSAP. Slovenia's target was 124 fatalities and the goal was almost reached.

Spain

Figure 3.26: Spain

According to Figure 3.26 Spain benefited from 3ERSAP. Spain reached their target reduction in line with the 3ERSAP and even better reaching a reduction of 55% in 2010. For further details see IRTAD (2010), IRTAD (2012a) and IRTAD (2013).

Sweden

[H]

Figure 3.27: Sweden

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According to Figure 3.27 Sweden benefited from 3ERSAP. Sweden has a "Vision Zero" policy and a very developed system that made them have one of the lowest ratios fatalities per million of inhabitants. For further details of their systems in particular cases that occurred in the considered periods see IRTAD (2010), IRTAD (2012a) and IRTAD (2013).

United Kingdom

[H]

Figure 3.28: United Kingdom

According to Figure 3.28 United Kingdom benefited from 3ERSAP. United Kingdom has its own program and target. In particular their target for 2010 was a reduction of 40% with respect to 1997-98. They reached their target with a reduction of 49%. For further details see IRTAD (2010), IRTAD (2012a) and IRTAD (2013).

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